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**What is the complete journey that festival memories take,
from their creation to their impact on engagement?**

A qualitative study based on Generation Z festival-goers

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“No part of this memoire has been submitted for any other award. All work is original with the exception of cited work where full references are given.”

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This thesis is the result of independent research and personal reflections, with properly cited references to support the analysis. The usual disclaimer applies.

Abstract

It is difficult to exist in an increasingly competitive music festival sector. The major challenges posed by modern issues continue to multiply. We are seeing a change in consumer habits and a drastic increase in production costs that make it difficult for organizing structures to survive.

In order to respond to these issues, it is no longer possible to simply offer events or concerts one after the other; festival-goers are looking for real experiences that are thought out and considered to be as memorable as possible. Thus, memorability becomes a key aspect to consider when we want to generate strong and lasting engagement among festival-goers.

The objective of this thesis will be to capture the nuances of what represents a memorable memory by chronologically tracing the complete journey that Generation Z's festival memories take. Thus, this path will begin with their creation and will end by addressing the impact they can have on post-festival engagement.

To address these issues, I interviewed 21 festival-goers during semi-structured interviews about their memories, their evolution, and their involvement with festivals. Among these festival-goers, some have already been volunteers, artists, or service providers during these events. These different points of view will allow me to obtain a global, complete, and objective spectrum of what a memorable experience represents.

The study allowed me to understand the levers that allowed an event to remain anchored in memory. Also, this research highlights the major role played by the community, through remanence, recitation, and socialization in the evolution of memories. Finally, post-event engagement is examined to understand what drives it or hinders it.

The study confirms a large number of previous studies such as Durkheim's on collective effervescence, Collins's on the importance of rituals, or Pine and Gilmore's, who propose a conceptual model for creating memorable experiences. The theoretical implications of this study will be discussed in order to provide concrete practical managerial advice to music festival organizers.

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PART 1 – Introduction

The world of music festivals has been experiencing unprecedented growth for several years. The number of these events across the country is exploding, accompanied by increasingly fierce competition between organizers. Today, there are more than 7,200 festivals in France, compared to 600 in 1990 (Cour des Comptes, 2023). In a modern context, where production costs continue to rise, the behavior of different audiences is changing, and the expectations of younger generations continue to evolve, festivals must no longer simply stand out and maintain their longevity. They must now offer memorable and engaging experiences.

Because while a festival can attract an audience through its lineup, image, or reputation, it is the experience itself that will determine and greatly impact the lasting attachment, loyalty, or desire to recommend it of festival-goers who have attended. In this logic, the memorability of these events must be considered and placed at the heart of the organization. Pine and Gilmore (1999) consider that a memorable experience must be able to anchor itself permanently in the mind of the consumer, even long after the moment has passed. This experience must be based on precise scripting, strong sensory immersion, powerful emotional intensity, and the ability to provoke a feeling of rupture or transformation, according to Ellis et al., 2017 and Wood & Kinnunen, 2020.

In the field of events, numerous studies have sought to understand the levers that can trigger these memorable experiences. In this study, we will observe the sensory dimensions (De Geus et al., 2015), the importance of collective dynamics (Collins, 2004; Durkheim, 1912), and all the processes of subjective recollection (Wood, 2015). But, although these studies have laid the foundations for essential concepts and theories, they are often quantitative. This methodology has therefore failed to answer a key question by capturing all its nuances. This question will be addressed in this thesis using new methods. This question is: "What is the complete journey that festival memories take, from their creation to their impact on engagement?" At a time when audience loyalty is becoming difficult to build, a better understanding of the role of memories in the relationship with events seems fundamental.

This thesis seeks to address this need. For greater clarity, it focuses on a very specific audience: members of Generation Z. These individuals, born between the late 1990s and the early 2010s, appear to have a particularly strong relationship with emotion, community, and immediacy. Thus, through a qualitative approach, this work seeks to trace the journey of festival memories, from their genesis to their impact on return, recommendations, attachment, volunteering, etc.). It is based on 21 semi-structured interviews conducted with young people who attended at least one festival. Some were artists, volunteers, or service providers, offering a particularly rich and comprehensive diversity of perspectives.

Through the analysis of their narratives, several dimensions emerge: the role of individual and collective emotions, the importance of the venue and scenography, surprise, social relationships, but also the retrospective transformation of memories, their reactivation, their narration, and the pride they can inspire. These data allow us to both confirm existing theories,

such as those of Collins and Seligman, and offer new insights, particularly on the impact of the "first festival," the role of micro-spaces, and bodily memory.

To answer the central question guiding this research, this dissertation adopts an inductive approach based on thematic analysis, exploring the participants' narratives without seeking to constrain them within overly rigid frameworks. The objective is to give meaning to their memories, to understand what they reveal about expectations, the transformations experienced, and the levels of engagement that can be mobilized. This thesis is organized as follows: First, it will begin with a literature review presenting the main concepts mobilized and presented in the existing literature. We find, for example, theories concerning the economy of experience, experiential intensity, collective emotions, subjective memory or even post-event engagement. A second part will detail the qualitative methodology adopted. Then, we will proceed to the analysis of the results which will be articulated in six main parts, following the journey of the memory from its birth to its effects in a chronological manner. Finally, the discussion will cross-reference the results with existing theoretical contributions, before concluding on the contributions, the managerial implications, the limitations of the study and the avenues for future research.

PART 2 – Literature Review

A. Theoretical Foundations: What makes an experience memorable and engaging?

1. The Experience Economy

The concept of the "experience economy," introduced by *Pine and Gilmore (1999)*, constitutes an essential theoretical basis for understanding how organizations can create value beyond standard products or services. According to these authors, the modern economy is evolving towards the staging of unique experiences, where consumers seek, above all, to experience memorable moments. This logic is based on four fundamental dimensions: entertainment, education, aesthetics, and escapism. These dimensions intersect along two axes: participation (passive to active) and the level of absorption or immersion, allowing experiences to be classified according to their intensity.

In the event industry, this theory has been widely used to create attendee experiences. *Manthiou and al (2014)* demonstrate that aesthetics and entertainment are the dimensions most strongly associated with memorability (while education and escape have a greater influence on immediate gratification). They demonstrate that these components are not isolated but interconnected in the formation of a lasting memory, particularly when the visual and audio environment is designed to immerse the visitor in a coherent atmosphere.

Ellis and Rossman (2008) expand on this perspective by emphasizing the importance of "staging," or the staging of the experience. They argue that the value felt by attendees depends on the organizers' ability to orchestrate a harmonious combination of emotional, aesthetic, and symbolic stimuli, with the aim of provoking strong affective reactions. This scripting requires a genuine intentionality in the way services are delivered and careful attention to the environment, the narrative of the event, and the social interactions associated with it.

This attention to environmental quality is also highlighted by *Chou, Huang, and Mair (2018)* in the field of festivals. They show that the physical and social components of the festivalscape (such as atmosphere, aesthetics, and interactions) can generate a sense of well-being and strengthen emotional attachment to the venue. Although rather resident-centered, their approach highlights the importance of spatial and relational experience in building memorable memories.

Finally, the contribution of technology to this experiential logic has been explored by *Tom Dieck and al (2017)*, who demonstrate, in the context of certain festivals, that the use of augmented reality can strengthen certain dimensions of this model. Their study reveals, in particular, that AR-enabled aesthetics act as an entry point to immersion, making the environment more visually engaging.

Thus, the Experience Economy provides a solid framework for analyzing the creation of experiential value at festivals. It highlights the crucial role of sensory design, active participation, and storytelling in building an immersive, engaging, and unforgettable experience.

2. Experiential Intensity

While the Experience Economy has laid the conceptual foundations for memorable experiences, understanding what makes an experience intense requires further study. Experiential intensity refers to the way in which an individual engages cognitively, emotionally, and physically in a situation. The stronger this engagement, the more memorable the experience is likely to be.

Ellis and al (2017) propose a structured theory of experience according to which any meaningful experience follows a dynamic in several phases: preparation, participation, immersion, and resonance. Immersion here refers to a state of total concentration, in which the individual is absorbed by what they are experiencing to the point of forgetting their external environment. Resonance, on the other hand, describes the prolonged effect of the experience after it has taken place. This model emphasizes the need to design experiences that activate multiple levers of engagement simultaneously (sensory, emotional, mental).

Along these lines, *De Geus, Richards, and Toepoel (2015)* developed an Event Experience Scale (EES), which assesses the intensity of the experience across four dimensions:

- Physical engagement: active participation, mobility, dancing, etc.
- Emotional engagement: affective reactions, excitement, euphoria.
- Cognitive engagement: reflection, intellectual stimulation, focused attention.
- Novelty: feeling of experiencing something rare or new.

This approach explains how different forms of engagement can combine to create a powerful experience.

Oklevik and al (2021) extend this line of thought by showing that the event context also influences the intensity of the experience. Through a survey of attendees at different types of events, the authors demonstrate that affective and cognitive engagement is higher in settings where the environment is immersive and where attendees perceive a strong coherence between the atmosphere, the content offered, and their expectations. Experiential intensity is therefore not solely linked to the individual: it is also triggered by the event's design.

Calvo-Soraluze and Viñals Blanco (2014) take a similar approach, examining strategies aimed at stimulating leisure experiences at music festivals. They identify several levers for intensification, such as sensory stimulation, immersive scenography, the variety of artistic offerings, and also the opportunity to act (dancing, interacting, creating).

In this context, *Tran and Vu (2021)* emphasize that co-creative behaviors, such as active participation, sharing experiences, or interacting with other festival-goers, play a key role in audience engagement. Their study highlights that these behaviors reinforce the perceived value of the event and foster stronger emotional and cognitive involvement, conditions required for high experiential intensity.

Finally, *Marković (2019)* highlights the link between the perceived quality of the experience and its intensity. Using a multidimensional approach, the author emphasizes that quality is not only based on logistical organization or programming, but also on subjective and experiential criteria such as the atmosphere or the level of wonder evoked. These elements contribute to

strengthening attention, emotion, and involvement, creating conditions for an experience perceived as intense.

In short, experiential intensity is constructed at the intersection of several dimensions of engagement and depends on both individual and contextual factors. It constitutes a logical continuation of the foundations of the Experience Economy (1.1) and the specific mechanisms of memorization and engagement that will be explored later. Understanding how intensity manifests itself and can be stimulated therefore constitutes a central lever for creating truly impactful and memorable experiences.

3. Emotional Dimensions

Emotion constitutes a central dimension of experience, particularly in the context of festivals where audiences are confronted with a high concentration of sensory, social, and symbolic stimuli. It acts as an intensification mechanism, but also as a vector of memory and social connection. While the previous section showed how multisensory engagement contributes to the intensity of the experience, it is now necessary to understand how emotions shape the quality and depth of the experience.

In the field of positive psychology, *Martin Seligman (2011)* proposes the PERMA model, which identifies five fundamental components of sustainable well-being: Positive Emotion, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, and Accomplishment. The first of these components, positive emotions, acts as a trigger: feeling joy, wonder, or gratitude contributes to an immediate state of well-being, but also promotes the consolidation of a positive memory in the long term. This model provides a useful theoretical framework for understanding how experiences can generate lasting emotions by acting simultaneously on multiple levels (aesthetic, relational, narrative).

This emotional dynamic is reinforced by social mechanisms. In *The Elementary Forms of Religious Life (1912)*, *Émile Durkheim* developed the notion of collective effervescence. This concept refers to an intense emotional state generated when a group of individuals gathers in a ritualized situation, marked by common symbols and a shared temporality. Effervescence produces group cohesion and leaves a strong emotional imprint on individuals. Applied to festivals, this idea explains why certain moments (songs, mosh pits, shared silences) become highly significant because they activate a sense of unity.

Randall Collins, extending *Durkheim*, proposes the theory of "interaction ritual chains": collective emotions arise in synchronized social rituals that generate lasting emotional energy (elation, belonging). This dynamic fuels attachment to the group and the desire to relive the experience.

Emotional synchrony, defined as the perception of having felt the same emotions at the same time as others, reinforces this phenomenon. *Emma H. Wood (2019)*, in her study *I Remember How We All Felt*, shows that this experienced synchronization increases the depth of collective memory and contributes to a shared social memory. This feeling of emotional connection, although subjective, amplifies the significance of the event. It also allows for emotional

replaying of the experience afterward, particularly through storytelling and sharing among participants.

Finally, *E. Wood and Maarit Kinnunen's (2020)* study on festivals highlights the fundamental role of emotions in the recollective value of memories: the stronger and more shared the emotion, the more easily the memory is activated and communicated.

Thus, emotions play a pivotal role between the intensity of the experience and its persistence over time. They constitute an emotional foundation on which memorability, attachment, and meaning are built. Far from being mere passing reactions, they are entirely anchored in what the festival experience represents.

4. Memorability and Meaning

One of the fundamental objectives of experience creation is to promote memorability, that is, the ability to generate a lasting and lasting memory. But this memory is not simply a passive trace of the past: it is reconstructed, interpreted, and imbued with meaning. After exploring intensity and emotion as levers of immediate engagement, we will now focus on the temporality of memory and how it is integrated into a personal or collective narrative.

Harmon and Dunlap (2017) propose a structured approach to the leisure experience through three temporal phases: expectation, participation (experience), and recollection. According to them, the recollection phase plays a central role in the overall perception of the experience. The latter is often reconstructed after the fact, influenced not only by what was experienced, but also by the emotions felt, the significant moments, and the meanings attributed to them. One of the key elements of this process is the "peak-end rule," a concept derived from the work of *Daniel Kahneman (cited by the authors)*, according to which individuals judge an experience primarily based on its most intense moment and its conclusion. This means that memory does not faithfully reflect the entire experience, but extracts certain key moments of high emotional or symbolic value.

This distinction between experience and memory is also developed by *E. Wood (2015)* in her article *How We Think We Felt*. The author highlights the gap between the "self-in-the-moment" (the self in the experience) and the "remembering self" (the self that remembers). The memory of an experience is a mental construct influenced by factors such as personal narrative, the social context of recollection, and how the individual wishes to perceive themselves. Understanding this dynamic is essential for analyzing why some festivals leave a deep mark while others fade quickly: it's not so much what objectively happened that matters, but what we remember about it, what we tell ourselves about it, and how we want it to fit into our identity.

Kesgin and al (2020) identify two forms of authenticity in memorization: object-based (tangible elements) and existential (personal alignment). In festivals, existential authenticity takes precedence: a sincere moment or a strong connection based on the festival-goer's feelings becomes a lasting memory.

This existential significance of memory is confirmed by the work of *Harrington and al (2020)*, who demonstrate a direct link between the perception of a memorable experience, its memorability, and a higher level of life satisfaction. According to them, the most powerful

memories are not only those that provided pleasure in the moment, but also those that left a lasting mark on the individual's personal trajectory.

Finally, *Kinnunen and al (2023)* emphasize that shared memory reinforces the meaning of a memory and facilitates its emotional consolidation, particularly through narratives or social media. It doesn't simply transmit an experience: it transforms it into a story, a personal or collective myth.

Thus, memorability depends not only on intensity or emotion, but also on how an experience is structured over time, subjectively reconstructed, valued for its authenticity, and shared socially. This complex process of memory formation constitutes a logical progression between lived experience and long-term engagement.

These conceptual contributions constitute the theoretical foundations necessary for analyzing the experience. In the following, we will use them to understand how music festivals activate these levers and produce lasting memories. Before that, we will now try to explain the festival context in France.

B. Context: The Music Festival Market

1. Overview of Music Festivals

Music festivals now occupy a key place in the contemporary cultural landscape, at the intersection of artistic, economic, tourism, and social logics. Their diversity in terms of formats, stakeholders, audiences, and territories makes them a complex subject of study. Understanding this plurality is essential to situate the festival experiences analyzed in this thesis in their context of production and evolution.

In France, music festivals constitute the leading category of cultural events identified: nearly 45% of the festivals identified in the live performance sector fall within the musical field (*Cour des Comptes, 2023, cited in Festivals et Territoires*). The number of festivals has grown exponentially, from 600 events in 1990 to over 7,200 in 2022, with a notable acceleration since the 2000s. This growth has been accompanied by a diversification of formats: large commercial festivals, free events run by local authorities, small-scale community initiatives, and even traveling festivals.

The typology of festivals is not limited to size or reputation. The *Festivals and Territories* report distinguishes several essential parameters: recurrence (annual or exceptional), artistic specialization (classical music, contemporary music, world music), the legal form of the organizer (associations, local authorities, businesses, hybrid structures), and capacity. This complexity makes any rigid categorization difficult, especially since many festivals operate at the boundary between cultural, tourism, and festive events, blurring traditional boundaries. The study also highlights the territorial imbalance of offerings, concentrated in tourist areas or cultural metropolises already equipped with infrastructure (e.g., Paris, Lyon, Aix-en-Provence). This reinforces inequalities in access to culture and calls into question the logic of public support, particularly in the post-COVID period, where issues of resilience, proximity, and sustainability are becoming central.

It is in this context that critical alternatives to large commercial festivals are emerging. The article, "*From "Clone Towns" to "Slow Towns,"*" analyzes the development of small-scale festivals, embedded in a "slow culture" approach, in opposition to the dynamics of standardization and mass consumption. These festivals, often centered on a strong local identity, prioritize conviviality, community participation, and a pace adapted to the territory. They embody a desire to slow down leisure time to foster a more authentic, relational, and rooted experience. Although the study focuses on food festivals, it opens up a perspective that can be transposed to certain niche music festivals that boast alternative programming and a strong connection with their local community.

Finally, the line between cultural festival and active leisure practice sometimes tends to blur. The article *Reframing Mass Participation Events as Active Leisure* proposes broadening the definition of a "participatory event" to include hybrid forms combining cultural, sporting, or civic activities. This allows for the inclusion of events such as "neighborhood parties," "participatory festivals," or even "musical marathons," where participants are not just spectators but also co-actors in the experience. This reading indirectly feeds into the discussion on the co-creation of experiences, which will be explored in greater depth in the rest of the literature review.

Thus, the music festival market, far from being homogeneous, is composed of a mosaic of initiatives with varied ambitions, structures, and audiences. This diversity lays the necessary foundations for analyzing experiences lived in such varied contexts.

2. Stakeholders, Production, and Festival Operations

Behind every festival experience lies a complex organization involving a diverse range of stakeholders. Understanding who produces festivals, according to what logics, and with what tools, allows us to anchor the analysis of the festival experience in its concrete production conditions. Contrary to the romantic image of the "out-of-this-world" festival, it is in reality an ecosystem structured by artistic, economic, political, and technological logics.

In France, festivals are organized under extremely varied legal statuses, ranging from cultural associations to public limited companies, including local public companies (SPL), public institutions, and hybrid structures. This diversity reflects the coexistence of heterogeneous economic models, but also governance that is sometimes difficult to smooth out. The Festivals and Territories report (*Cour des Comptes, 2023*) identifies this plurality as a source of wealth, but also as a source of imbalances, particularly in terms of access to funding and institutional recognition.

The nonprofit model remains dominant, particularly for medium-sized or territorial festivals. These organizations are often run by a small team, heavily dependent on volunteer commitment, but they can benefit from strong local roots and significant symbolic capital. In contrast, some festivals structured as businesses or simplified joint-stock companies (SAS) have significant resources, are driven by economic performance, and can leverage powerful private partnerships. This contrast, although schematic, reveals a divide between a general interest and market-driven approach, which is also reflected in audience expectations and the types of experiences offered.

Local authorities play a decisive role, whether as direct organizers, logistical partners, or funders. This involvement is part of a cultural planning approach, but it can also be strategic: festivals then become levers for outreach, tourist attraction, and urban marketing. This is demonstrated by the article *City Festivals* (Johansson & Kociatkiewicz, 2011), which analyzes how some municipalities use festivals as tools for symbolic city staging. From this perspective, the event aims not only to celebrate an artistic form, but also to produce a territorial image, often controlled, harmonized, and depoliticized to attract audiences, media, and funders.

This strategic positioning directly influences the festival value chain. The article *Information and Communication Technology in Event Management* (Winkle & Bueddefeld, 2020) describes this chain as a sequence including planning, logistics, audience management, communication, and event evaluation. At each stage, digital technologies play an increasingly important role. These include ticketing and accreditation software, security systems, flow control systems, CRM (customer relationship management) tools, and post-event analysis platforms. These tools condition how the experience is produced, measured, and promoted.

Digitalization has also expanded the skills expected of organizers. They must now integrate digital marketing functions, often centralized around social media. Although this point will be elaborated on later, it is worth emphasizing here, as indicated by the study *Social Media Activity in a Festival Context* (MacKay and al, 2017), that monitoring social media posts is now integrated into production tasks: community management, anticipation of attendance peaks, real-time response, etc.

At the intersection of culture, public policy, tourism, and logistics, festival production thus appears to be a constantly evolving multi-stakeholder system. This structural complexity directly influences the type of experience offered to participants, the values embodied by the event, and the conditions under which engagement can be expressed. It also allows us to better understand why certain festivals, depending on their nature and their actors, favor authenticity, personal transformation or, on the contrary, organizational efficiency and profitability.

3. Challenges and Opportunities

The music festival landscape is currently facing a series of challenges that are profoundly redefining organizational practices, audience expectations, and forms of engagement. Whether it's the consequences of the health crisis, demands for sustainability, the integration of digital technology, or the saturation of offerings, festivals must now deal with increased complexity. These constraints can nevertheless be seen as opportunities for transformation, provided they are integrated into a renewed vision of the festival experience.

The COVID-19 crisis has both revealed and accelerated already latent changes. Faced with mass cancellations, loss of revenue, logistical uncertainty, and the emergence of new digital habits, many festivals have had to rethink their models. The article *Reframing Mass Participation Events as Active Leisure* invites us to move beyond a purely event-based vision of the festival to reclassify it as an active leisure practice, that is, a voluntary, engaging, physically or emotionally mobilizing activity. This redefinition paves the way for hybrid

formats that are more flexible, participatory, and potentially more resilient in the face of various constraints.

In this dynamic of change, the question of sustainability has become central. It is no longer limited to waste management or carbon emission reduction. It now extends to the cultural, emotional, and social value of the experience. The study *How the Experience Designs of Sustainable Festive Events...* shows how experiential design can integrate sustainability objectives, for example, by promoting local collaborations, respect for cultures, or limiting environmental impact. The recommended approach now rests on a balance between immediate pleasure and lasting meaning. This tension must be integrated by the organizers in their choices of programming, scenography and communication.

This concern for sustainability is consistent with the thinking put forward in *From "Clone Towns" to "Slow Towns,"* which contrasts two approaches to territorial development: the "cloned city" (standardized, commercialized, consumable) and the "slow city," based on quality of life and authenticity. In this context, festivals can become agents of cultural transformation by offering slower, more community-based event models. This movement challenges the constant quest for growth (ever bigger, ever faster) in favor of an experience refocused on relationships and sustainability.

Alongside these ethical requirements, festivals must contend with the increasing digitalization of their operations. The article *"Volvelles, Domes and Wristbands..."* illustrates this evolution through the integration of tangible digital devices (interactive wristbands, personalized objects, connected stands, etc.) into the visitor experience. These technologies are not mere gadgets: they allow for mapping engagement, personalizing interactions, and opening spaces for remembering and extending the experience. However, their deployment requires technical skills, ethical reflection on the data collected, and real added value perceived by the audience.

Saturation of the offerings is another major challenge. In a market where festivals are multiplying, competition is no longer based solely on headliners, but on the ability to offer an original, engaging, and coherent experience. The article *"Stimulating Attendees' Leisure Experience..."* emphasizes the need for festivals to stimulate several dimensions simultaneously: sensory, social, and symbolic. This requires the ability to read audience expectations, but also to anticipate them.

Finally, these changes raise the question of loyalty, beyond simple commercial retention. The study, *"Linking Engagement at Cultural Festivals to Legacy Impacts,"* shows that participant engagement can produce lasting impacts on local areas, as well as forms of community around the event. To achieve this, festivals must be able to establish a lasting relationship with their audiences by activating emotional, symbolic, and participatory levers. Loyalty then becomes a side effect of a deeply lived and shared experience, not an isolated marketing objective.

Thus, the current challenges facing festivals cannot be addressed individually. They require a systemic vision capable of articulating technological innovation, cultural sustainability, and strategic adaptation. These tensions shape the framework within which the design of a memorable festival experience is currently taking place.

C. Memorable Festival Experiences: Mechanisms and Drivers

1. Immersion and Experiential Design

One of the most powerful levers in creating a memorable festival experience lies in its ability to immerse attendees in an environment distinct from their everyday lives. This immersion relies on experiential design, which leverages scenography, sensory stimulation, and storytelling to generate a sense of change of scenery, engagement, and sometimes even transformation. It's not simply a matter of decorating a venue; it's also about designing a space-time in which the audience has an embodied, affective, and meaningful experience.

In their analysis of the transformative experience at the Burning Man festival, *Neuhofer and al (2021)* emphasize that experiential design goes far beyond aesthetic or logistical considerations: it constitutes an intentional process aimed at orchestrating immersive elements to provoke a change in perception of oneself or the world. This process is based on three pillars: sensory coherence, which aligns stimuli to create an enveloping atmosphere; the narrative structure of the space, which guides the participant through a symbolic journey; and active participation, which involves the festival-goer as co-author of the experience. These principles take on their full meaning at Burning Man, where the desert becomes an imaginary territory populated by immersive artistic structures, ephemeral installations, and community rituals. The experience relies less on a traditional artistic program than on the staging of an alternative world, in which the visitor becomes a true protagonist.

This active relationship with the environment is also central to the gameful design approach developed by *Raftopoulos and al (2013)*. This concept refers to the integration of game mechanics (such as progression, surprise, implicit rules) into the event design. Applied to festivals, gameful design strengthens audience engagement by introducing logics of exploration, quest, or playful interaction. The result is a more dynamic experience, in which festival-goers are no longer mere spectators but rather actors immersed in a scripted universe.

This notion of staging the experience is at the heart of the integrated model proposed by *Ralston and al (2007)* in *Staging Memorable Events and Festivals*. The authors identify several key dimensions of immersive design: the theming of the space, sensory stimulation (lights, sounds, textures), the management of flows and transitions, and the personalization of interaction. This model offers a valuable analytical framework for understanding how the physical and symbolic design of a festival determines the quality of the experience.

For its part, the article by *Neuhofer and al (2020)* on transformative experiences emphasizes the importance of the experience pushing us to question the world or ourselves in order to be truly memorable. This can occur through an unexpected environment, a disconcerting atmosphere, or a powerful narrative message. Thus, immersive scenography not only pleases, it questions, disrupts, and is emotionally anchored.

The study *Rethinking Music Festivals as a Staged Event (Pegg and Patterson, 2010)* complements this perspective by showing that festival-goers increasingly expect "theatrical" environments, coherent and identifiable, allowing them to enjoy an exceptional and shareable experience. The festival space thus becomes a place for the expression of identity, where scenography plays a key role in building memories and motivating return visits. This is

consistent with some observations from *Event Design in Outdoor Music Festival Audience Behavior* (Robertson and al, 2018), which note that the spatial organization of a festival directly influences the perception of freedom, community, and engagement. Finally, it's worth noting that trends such as environmental storytelling and immersive devices are increasingly being identified as key levers by event professionals (*Leverage Trends for a Memorable Experience, 2020*). However, their effectiveness largely depends on their overall coherence and their ability to integrate with the festival's identity.

Thus, festival immersion is not simply a matter of decor or ambiance. It relies on intentional design, where each sensory or spatial element is conceived as a vector of emotional engagement and meaning. This experiential staging encourages a shift toward more personal dimensions of the experience, which we will discuss in the following subsection.

2. Emotional Transformation

While immersion and experiential design lay the foundation for a memorable experience, it is often the emotion experienced that constitutes the main catalyst for transformation. In the context of festivals, emotions are not simply passive reactions to a sensory environment: they play a structuring role in the construction of memories, self-redefinition, and sometimes even in the participant's personal trajectory. The literature highlights the extent to which the emotional intensity experienced on-site is a major lever for personal development, memory anchoring, and lasting attachment.

Oliva's (2023) article proposes an analytical model of festival emotions, which distinguishes several emotional dimensions influencing the overall evaluation of the experience: stimulation (excitement, euphoria), tenderness (emotional connection), nostalgia, and overall satisfaction. These emotions are not homogeneous: they can be felt successively, or even simultaneously, depending on the sequences experienced during the event. This model highlights the idea that the emotions experienced at festivals are not trivial: they contribute to the construction of meaning and the perception of the personal value of the event.

This notion is consistent with *Seligman's PERMA model (2011)*, cited above. Applied to festivals, this model helps us understand how an intense emotional experience can extend beyond the event framework to influence life trajectory. Festivals provide a framework conducive to the expression of the model's five dimensions. In this way, they can play a role in the subjective transformation of individuals, generating a feeling of alignment with oneself or with others.

The search for personal transformation often occurs through collective emotional synchrony, as shown in the study by (*E. Wood, 2015*). The concept of "perceived emotional synchrony" refers to the feeling of being emotionally aligned with a group at the same time. This emotional synchronization fosters a sense of community and reinforces the idea that what is experienced is unique and worthy of being remembered. At festivals, this synchrony can manifest itself particularly during musical performances or moments of silence or shared jubilation.

This phenomenon is further explored by *Kinnunen and al (2023)* in *Shared Festival Tourism Experiences*, who analyze shared memory as an essential dimension of the experience. They

show that emotional transformation is not only individual but also relational and collective. Remembering together, reliving a moment through the eyes of another, or recounting an experience shared together helps prolong and strengthen its transformative effect. This social memory strengthens attachment to the festival and the community it represents.

Emotion also plays a role in festival-goers' values after the event, as shown by *Yen and al (2022)* in their study on sustainable festivals. They show that certain emotions linked to ecological awareness, admiration for environmentally friendly design, or a form of cultural awakening can induce a transformation in future behaviors (consumer choices, civic engagement, etc.). Thus, emotional transformation is not necessarily spectacular: it can also result in a discreet but lasting shift in attitudes and values.

At a more conceptual level, *Harrington and al (2020)* show that the emotions experienced during the event can also influence overall life satisfaction, leaving a lasting positive imprint. *Pegg and Patterson (2010)* suggest that festival-goers' initial motivations, such as the search for rupture or transformation, condition how these emotions will be experienced and integrated. Finally, taking a more critical approach, *Jamieson and Todd (2019)* analyze transgressive festivals as spaces of symbolic reversal, where emotional intensity is cultivated as a form of social and political emancipation.

Thus, emotion is not simply a "bonus" of the festival experience: it is at the heart of the process by which a moment becomes meaningful, impactful, and even transformative. Emotional intensity, collective synchrony, and personal resonance together contribute to making the festival a space-time of symbolic reconfiguration. This emotional transformation, when anchored in a shared memory and resonating with the individual's deep values, sets the stage for lasting engagement, which we will explore in the next section.

3. Socialization and co-creation

The festival experience is not limited to the passive reception of artistic content; it is also shaped by interactions between participants, the collective creation of meaning, and the feeling of belonging to a temporary community. This social dimension, often spontaneous and informal, is at the heart of many memorable accounts, as it conditions the intensity experienced and the perception of the festival as a unique moment.

One of the keys to this dynamic lies in what *Collins* calls "interaction ritual chains." According to this sociological theory, intense collective experiences (such as singing together, dancing together, sharing a powerful moment) generate shared emotional energy, which fuels feelings of solidarity and strengthens social bonds. These ritualized moments, even informal ones, leave a lasting impression, notably through shared symbols, codified memories, and a perception of having "experienced something together." At a festival, these ritual interaction chains are omnipresent. They are built in crowds, queues, camps, or even moments of musical communion.

These interactions contribute to what some researchers describe as co-creation logics of experiential value. In their article on tourism, *Andrades and Dimanche (2014)* propose a behavioral approach to co-creation, emphasizing that individuals do not simply absorb an

experience: they are co-producers, mobilizing their expectations, behaviors, and social interactions. This co-creation is based on three conditions: active participation, freedom of interaction, and the ability to affect the unfolding or meaning of the experience. In the festival context, this translates into the ability for festival-goers to interact with the environment, other participants, or even the organizers in a formal (workshops, stage participation) or informal (collective atmospheres, spontaneous practices) manner.

This logic is particularly visible in events where participants are invited to play an active role in the festival's progress. This is what *Kjeldgaard and Bode (2017)* demonstrate through their study of brandfests, gatherings around brand universes, where festival-goers deploy what the authors call "ludic agency." This concept refers to the ability to voluntarily engage in playful, creative, and even performative practices that contribute to enriching the event's atmosphere. At music festivals, this manifests itself through costumes, improvised collective singing, shared dances, and even festive repurposing of everyday objects. Far from being trivial, these practices fully contribute to constructing the meaning of the event for participants.

Added to this is digital co-creation, as *Kyungsik Han and al (2015)* demonstrate in their study of arts festivals. The authors demonstrate that content published by festival-goers on social media, particularly encouraged by organizers, strengthens the connection between participants. They extend the experience beyond the event and contribute to the creation of a collective narrative. These media practices are not neutral; they select, enhance, and ritualize certain moments that then become emblematic for the community. The use of hashtags, filters, or collaborative platforms can thus be considered a contemporary form of social ritualization, fueling both a sense of belonging and memorability.

Thus, socialization and co-creation are not "sidebars" of the festival experience; they are integral dimensions. Spontaneous interactions, playful gestures, and digital contributions are all ways for festival-goers to feel involved in their own experience. These mechanisms contribute to the construction of a fleeting but powerful sense of community, which gives the event increased emotional and symbolic value. It is precisely these dynamics that fuel the collective memory of the festival, and which can ultimately influence the long-term commitment of participants. This will be the subject of the next section.

4. Digital extension and memory sharing

In line with co-creation dynamics, contemporary festivals are increasingly adopting a logic of digital extension of the experience, beyond the time and space of the event itself. This extension relies on the use of social networks, immersive technologies, and the creation of digital or physical artifacts that foster memories, contribute to the construction of a shared narrative, and strengthen emotional attachment.

The study conducted by *MacKay and al (2017)* on social activity in a festival context shows that the temporality of digital sharing plays a key role in the experience. The authors identify three phases: before the event (expectation, screening, teasing), during (capture and sharing in real time), and after (review, commemoration, delayed sharing). This last phase is particularly important for memorization. Posted content (photos, videos, and stories) serves to structure

individual memories and also to promote the experience to others, thus consolidating the social dimension of the event.

This extension of the experience via digital means is not limited to traditional social platforms. It can also be facilitated by immersive technologies, as shown in the study by *Olya and al (2020)* on the use of augmented reality (AR) in science festivals. By superimposing layers of information or narration on top of physical reality, AR can intensify visitor engagement in the moment while providing them with personalized memory support. These hybrid experiences, half-virtual and half-real, generate memories rooted in emotion and surprise, often more lasting than traditional interactions. Although initially focused on a different type of event, this study offers interesting avenues for thinking about the emotional appropriation of the digital experience at a music festival.

This logic of extending engagement is also visible in the use of tangible and connected artifacts, as *Nissen and al (2014)* argue. The authors analyze how certain objects (RFID wristbands, interactive badges, artifacts manufactured on site) become vectors of emotional attachment. These objects, often personalized or associated with key moments of the event, are part of what could be called an engagement trajectory, where the object becomes an interface between the experience, the memory, and the post-festival narrative. Their function is twofold: to anchor the memory in the concrete (preventing its evaporation) and to provide a medium for personal or collective storytelling.

This ability of digital technology to extend the experience has also been explored by *Velt and al (2015)*, who introduce the notion of "festival viewing extension." They show that the ability to rewatch performances, share archives, or follow a festival remotely (via streaming platforms, multi-camera devices, or scripted replays) contributes to the continuous mediatization of the festival. This transforms the event into an extended narrative process, where the boundaries between before, during, and after are blurred. This temporal reconfiguration encourages a longer, often shared, attachment that can foster loyalty.

Finally, *Winkle and Bueddefeld (2020)* point out in their work on event technologies that these digital tools are not neutral: their design, implementation, and accessibility directly influence the level of engagement, the nature of participation, and the quality of the memory generated. While they can strengthen interaction and memory, if misused, they can also create a fragmented or superficial experience. It is therefore essential to think of these devices not as mere gadgets, but as elements integrated into the overall design of the festival experience.

Thus, social networks, immersive technologies, and physical artifacts are not peripheral additions to the festival experience: today, they are integral components, capable of extending, intensifying, and memorializing the event. By structuring the memory, facilitating its narrative, and fostering a sense of ongoing belonging, they contribute to building a lasting bond between the participant and the festival. This emotional and narrative connection constitutes a privileged gateway to post-event engagement.

D. From memory to engagement and loyalty

1. The link between memory and engagement

The memory of a festival is not simply an emotional trace: it acts as a behavioral lever, influencing how attendees talk about the festival, return to it, or develop long-term emotional attachments. Several empirical and theoretical studies agree on a strong link between the memorability of the experience and post-event engagement, whether in the form of positive word-of-mouth, revisit intentions, or emotional loyalty.

In their study on attendee loyalty through the lens of the experience economy, *Manthiou and al (2014)* show that festivals that successfully generate lasting memories achieve higher retention rates. The authors point out that in *Pine & Gilmore's (1999)* model, the final step in the hierarchy of experiences is the "memorable memory," considered the culmination of successful experiential design. This memory acts as an emotional anchor, influencing not only immediate satisfaction but also the intention to relive a similar experience, sometimes several years later.

This relationship is confirmed by the quantitative study conducted by *Mohamed and al (2022)* at the Jerash Festival (Jordan), which established a statistically significant link between the perceived memorability of a festival and the intention to revisit. This link is all the stronger when festival-goers felt a form of personal attachment to the festival, reinforced by positive social interactions. The article also highlights the importance of shared emotional memories as vectors of loyalty.

Beyond the intention to return, satisfaction generated during an event plays a key role in loyalty, as demonstrated by *Özkan and Yıldız (2024)* in their analysis of the link between festival satisfaction and destination loyalty. The authors introduce the notion of destination loyalty, that is, attachment not only to the event itself, but to the entire setting in which it is held. This finding is particularly interesting for festivals that play a role in the image or attractiveness of a region.

Bagheri and al (2023) provide another perspective by showing that satisfaction and loyalty also stem from an overall sense of well-being generated by the experience. Their study proposes a model where the memory of a moment of happiness or fulfillment, beyond simple one-off satisfaction, creates a deep attachment to the event. Perceived well-being thus becomes a mediator between the emotion experienced and future engagement, whether behavioral (revisit) or discursive (recommendation to others).

From a psychological perspective, *Harrington and al (2020)* provide additional insight by studying the case of Oktoberfest. They show that highly memorable experiences, those that stand out from everyday life through their intensity and uniqueness, are correlated with increased life satisfaction and a greater likelihood of re-engagement. The experience does not remain confined to the event; it becomes part of a broader personal narrative, making it more valuable and more valuable in the long term.

From a sociological perspective, *Sterchele (2019)* uses the theory of ritual interaction chains to explain how memorable collective experiences (characterized by emotional synchrony and shared attention) foster membership in a symbolic community. These memories, conveying shared emotions, reinforce the feeling of having been an "actor" in a unique moment, which

increases the likelihood of re-engagement, particularly in collective practices related to the event.

Finally, *Kinnunen and al (2023)* emphasize the social dimension of festival memory. In their study of shared memories, they show that the collective narrative (i.e., the way in which participants recall the event together) plays a decisive role in emotional attachment to the festival. These memories, whether mediated or not, foster a sense of belonging and reinforce the perceived value of the event, beyond its simple logistical or artistic quality.

Thus, the memorable memories generated by a festival are not passive traces, but activatable resources, both emotional and social. They fuel post-event engagement processes that manifest in various forms: revisitation, recommendation, and emotional attachment. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for thinking about loyalty beyond transactional marketing, as a relational, narrative and emotional process, anchored in individual and collective memory.

E. Research Gaps and Justification of the Study

1. Gaps in the Existing Literature

Despite an abundant literature on the festival experience, several blind spots remain in understanding memory processes and their role in post-event engagement. First, the majority of existing research adopts a quantitative approach, focused on measuring satisfaction or perceived memorability, often through predictive models or standardized scales. These studies offer valuable insights into the effects of a memorable experience but remain limited in their analysis of the subjective and evolving dynamics of memory.

Few studies examine how participants actively construct their memories of a festival, through their narratives, their lingering emotions, or their social interactions. This memory reconstruction, although central to attachment to an experience, remains largely unexplored in its qualitative dimensions: what does a participant truly retain? How is this memory reformulated, shared, and transformed over time?

Another gap concerns our understanding of memory narrative processes. Festival memory is not only individual; it is also collective, shaped by interactions with others, preserved objects, or content shared online. However, most existing models approach memory as a fixed variable, rather than as a dynamic process embedded in social and emotional logic.

Likewise, the issue of post-event engagement is often addressed through stated intentions (revisit, recommendation), without taking into account the emotional, existential, or identity depth that certain memories may have. This lacks a more nuanced understanding of the links between the quality of the memory, the meaning it takes on for the person, and the forms of engagement it can generate over time.

Finally, none of the existing literature addresses this topic by focusing exclusively on members of a single generation. Existing literature tends to generalize, as if the experience of a Generation Z representative must necessarily be the same as that of a Generation X representative. Times evolve, and so do their representatives.

Faced with these limitations, this research proposes a qualitative approach centered on the narratives of Generation Z participants. It aims to explore the characteristics (sensitive, evolving, and socially situated) of festival memories, to better understand how they can foster lasting engagement with the event and the community associated with it.

2. Research Proposal and Research Sub-Questions

In light of the theoretical contributions mobilized in this literature review, this research aims to trace the complete journey of Generation Z's festival memories, from their creation to their impact on engagement. To achieve this mission, it relies on qualitative interviews aimed at exploring in depth the narratives, emotions and social dynamics associated with the festival experience.

Five main themes emerge as priority areas of investigation, directly linked to the concepts identified above:

2.1. Memory Narration and Reconstructed Memory

- How do festival-goers recount their festival memories?
- What narrative elements make a memorable moment?

This theme draws on the work of *Wood (2015) and Harmon and Dunlap (2017)*, which shows that memories are reconstructed after the event and filtered by narratives, lingering emotions, and the meaning individuals wish to give to their experiences.

2.2. Sensory Immersion and Perceived Transformation

- To what extent do immersive devices (scenography, ambiance, aesthetics) influence memorability?
- Do the experiences produced produce a sense of rupture or personal transformation?

Inspired by the Experience Economy model (*Pine & Gilmore, 1999*) and the contributions of *Neuhof and al (2021)*, this dimension questions the festival's ability to offer a meaningful, potentially transformative interlude.

2.3. Experienced Emotions and Emotional Synchrony

- What role do emotions play in the persistence of memory?
- Does the feeling of having shared an emotion with others strengthen attachment to the moment experienced?

This question refers to the contributions of *Seligman (PERMA model)*, *Durkheim (collective effervescence)*, and *Wood & Kinnunen (2020) on emotional synchronization*.

2.4. *Social Memory and Digital Extensions*

- How are memories revived or transformed through sharing (stories, photos, social media)?
- To what extent do these sharing practices extend the experience?

This theme is rooted in the notions of shared memory and digital artifacts (*MacKay and al (2017), Velt and al (2015)*), exploring the role of digital media in consolidating or replaying memories.

2.5. *Memory and Post-Event Engagement*

- How does a memorable memory influence post-festival behavior (revisit, recommendation, community engagement)?
- What differentiates a lasting memory from a simple good time?

This dimension is based on the work of *Manthiou and al (2014), Mohamed and al (2022), and Bagheri and al (2023)*, who identify a strong link between memorability, perceived well-being, and loyalty.

These themes will guide the construction and analysis of the interviews, with the aim of shedding light on the subjective processes that transform a lived experience into a meaningful memory, capable of fueling the participant's future commitment to the festival.

PART 3 – Methodology

To carry out this thesis, a qualitative research approach will be particularly relevant. This method, which stands out from most existing research on this topic, will allow us to explore in depth the different personal and subjective memories of Generation Z festival-goers.

Exploring these memories often requires an open and free approach because they are shaped by numerous factors that vary depending on the individuals interviewed or the content of the experience. Thus, an individual's experience, their attachment to festivals or music, the relationships formed during the event, the emotions felt, and many other factors greatly impact the satisfaction and memorability that a festival-goer will retain from an event.

This study method will allow us to make sense of subjective experiences and interpret narratives. This will give us an idea of festival-goers' expectations beforehand, the challenges they encountered, the various key points that shaped each experience, the varied behaviors and reactions of festival-goers, and much more. This will allow us to understand the key elements of a memorable festival experience. This will provide detailed information that can enrich academic understanding and practical applications in the event and music industries.

We will also attempt to measure the impact of external advantages, both to the event itself and to the organizers, on the memories festival-goers take away from the experiences. These include the relationship festival-goers have with the people they shared the event with, the emotional connection to the venue or certain artists, their frequency of participation in this type of event, etc. This will provide a more comprehensive view of the components of music festival experiences.

Furthermore, by adopting a qualitative approach, we will also be able to understand the link between memorable memories and post-festival engagement. Open-ended interviews will help us discern and explore the different types of attachment and commitment that an individual can develop towards a festival, whereas a quantitative method too often tends to focus on numerical data, sometimes generalizing. In short, this methodology will allow us to better understand all the nuances and richness of festival experiences.

During my research, I will explore various fundamental concepts in order to answer my research question as comprehensively as possible.

First, the concept of reconstructed memory and subjective memories. This is a key element that will be important to study throughout the analysis. Several authors have already drawn on it. Among them, Wood. In her articles "How We Think We Felt" and "Shared Festival Tourism Experiences," she emphasizes the distortion of post-experience memories and the role of shared memory in loyalty. Other authors, such as Harrington in "Experience Perceptions, Memorability, and Life Satisfaction," examine how the quality of an experience can generate well-being afterward and, therefore, engagement.

Another important aspect to explore concerns the memorability of festival experiences. Understanding what can make an experience memorable is essential for analyzing the narratives of the people I will interview. We will explore the affective, sensory, social, playful, and

symbolic components of events. Some studies can serve as a basis for our analyses. For example, Ellis et al. in "Staging Memorable Events and Festivals" attempted to propose an integrated model of memorability factors. Others, such as De Geus et al. in "Event Experience Scale," sought to structure the different dimensions of a lived experience. Finally, some studies attempt to study memorability through more specific lenses. This is the case, for example, of Olivia in "An Emotional Perspective of Music Festival Experience Evaluation," which emphasizes the emotional analysis of musical experiences.

A recurring theme in literature, and one that will play an important role in my work, is that of social interactions and emotional synchrony. Indeed, many authors believe that memories are shaped by collective interactions and moments of emotional unity. This social synchrony is believed to be a powerful vector of memorization, engagement, and transformation. This is particularly the case for Wood & Kinnunen in "Emotion, Memory, and Re-Collective Value," who emphasize emotional synchrony. Others, such as Castro-Santos, who draws on the work of Collins, believe that interactional rituals greatly shape festival experiences. Finally, Rihova et al., in "Co-creation of Experience Value," place great importance on co-creation between visitors as a source of memorable value.

The last of the founding concepts of this thesis will be post-event engagement. I will seek to understand how memories can impact the different forms of engagement after a festival (loyalty, sharing, attachment, volunteering, etc.). This is the behavioral and emotional consequence that I want to link to memory. Some authors have already attempted to link satisfaction with loyalty, such as Özkan & Yıldız in "Effect of Festival Satisfaction on Destination Loyalty." Others, such as Manthiou et al. in "The Experience Economy Approach to Festival Marketing" or Al-Azzam et al. in "The Influence of Memorable Festival Experiences," link memorable experiences with attendee loyalty.

The objective will therefore be to understand how the dimensions of memorable experiences addressed in the literature review can lead to the creation of lasting memories that can, in turn, lead to increased engagement with a festival. At the end of this analysis, we should be able to identify the important levers to consider in order to sustainably influence festivalgoers' behavior toward the event through memories.

A. Data Collection Method

As explained previously, I believe a qualitative approach is the best methodology to apply to my topic. More specifically, I decided to conduct semi-open interviews structured around various specific and interrelated themes.

This method will allow me to quickly develop a profile of the interviewees (their number of festivals, their frequency of participation, their motivations for attending these types of events, etc.). This information could directly influence the individuals' experience and thus prove useful during data analysis.

The open-ended questions will allow me to allow the individuals to develop their memories and allow their subjective nature to emerge. This will allow me to identify which characteristics of the experience anchor the memorability of each of the stories told.

I will also pay particular attention to how the memories are recounted and shared. The reconstruction of memories and the emotions associated with them are essential aspects to explore in order to understand and draw conclusions. The evolution of these can be complex, and it will be interesting to let individuals tell their stories as they remember them.

Finally, post-event engagement can take many different forms. Questions will be asked to identify the interviewees' own unique experiences and, subsequently, to explore what may have triggered these different types of engagement.

There will also be some questions regarding the communication channels used by festival-goers, and they will be able to put themselves in the organizers' shoes to offer suggestions and recommendations.

The use of semi-open interviews is therefore a perfectly appropriate strategy. I will interview a diverse panel of festival-goers from Generation Z. The only restriction will be that they have already attended at least one festival, but for the panel to be representative, they must have attended a very different number of festivals. Therefore, there will be both repeat and occasional festival-goers.

I will strongly favor face-to-face interviews. However, if the need arises, I will have tools like Zoom or WhatsApp at my disposal. The plan will be more descriptive and exploratory to give individuals free rein to recall their subjective memories and explain their opinions. We will analyze and explore recurring themes that emerge from the qualitative data. Information such as context, emotional state, and even festival-goer experience will be taken into account.

For these in-depth interviews, data will be collected based on 21 interviews I conducted with Generation Z festival-goers from diverse backgrounds. For this purpose, an interview guide has been designed, but the freedom to expand on a given answer will be preserved in the event that doing so could lead to interesting or important data to consider. Particular care will be taken not to induce or influence the interviewees' responses. The interviews last between 28 and 58 minutes. The interview guide was written and formulated in French. The latter reviews the different themes addressed in this thesis. It includes 3 introductory questions necessary to draw up a profile of the festival-goer (and thus, subsequently, see if this could have influenced their answers.) 17 questions addressing themes such as the memory of the experience, shared memory or even post-event engagement. 3 questions concerning the recommendations that the individuals interviewed would like to make to festival organizers. And finally, 2 quick concluding questions.

B. Interview Guide

The interview guide used for this thesis was carefully designed to generate in-depth, nuanced, and sometimes complex responses about memorable experiences at music festivals. This guide was structured by specific themes, and the order of the questions was carefully considered to ensure clarity and understanding for the interviewees. The interview will begin with three introductory questions that will be valuable in developing festival-goer profiles of the individuals interviewed. This profile may prove valuable when analyzing the responses to determine whether certain perceptions or patterns are repeated depending on the type of profile

being interviewed. Subsequently, six questions will focus on the memory of the festival experience. During this section, interviewees will be able to take the time to explore and recall their memories. We will listen to them and try to learn more about the context, the evolution of these memories, and their subjective meaning. Then, five questions on sharing memories will be asked. We will then attempt to determine whether memories are often rekindled and in what ways. Following this, two questions will reveal practical information about how festival-goers follow and experience the communication surrounding these events. The final major section, concerning post-festival engagement, will be explored in four questions. Here, we will learn more about the transformational impact left by a memorable festival, the different types of engagement our interviewee may experience, and how their relationship with festivals may have evolved. Respondents will also have the opportunity to put themselves in the organizers' shoes during three questions aimed at formulating personal recommendations. These general questions will provide organizers with answers they might need to further improve customer experiences. Finally, there will also be two quick closing questions so that individuals can offer me any comments or information they may have. This logical order will allow me to delve deeper into each person's personal experience. Choosing this interview method will also promote a fluid dialogue, which will encourage participants to open up calmly without holding back from giving details or sharing even more in-depth thoughts. I will also be able to delve deeper into themes when I deem it necessary or interesting. Thanks to this structure, the richness of the data collected will be greatly optimized and I will then be able to obtain and draw up a complete assessment of the memorable festival experience and its role in post-event engagement.

C. Sampling

To conduct my study, I need to interview a large number of festival-goers from Generation Z and from diverse backgrounds. Ideally, I would like to interview people for whom festivals have different meanings and symbolism. I want to find individuals who attend festivals several times a year and others only occasionally. People for whom festivals are an unmissable event every year and others who only go when a good opportunity arises. Some are willing to travel very far just to enjoy the event and others prefer small, local festivals. In short, different personalities, as long as they have already attended several festivals. This difference in experiences could translate into varied points of view, expectations, patterns, and responses that will be interesting to observe in order to adapt advice and recommendations to specific types of festivals. Although this study is based on Generation Z, it is important to have a representative panel that I find people of different ages, sexes, cities and social and professional categories. This study will offer a more global vision, with people from different backgrounds and experiences, and the fact that it will focus mainly on the French-speaking world and a specific generation will represent a definite advantage in obtaining more precise and specific data. Having myself participated in the organization of several festivals (such as *Rétro C Trop*, *Samarock*, *Make Somme Noise* or *Somme'r Time*), it is a real opportunity to be able to address this subject. In addition, my experience as a recurring festival-goer for almost 10 years will be an opportunity to better identify and understand the answers I will receive. As the study focuses on a festival market, which is larger in France than anywhere else, competition is very tough.

In addition, financial difficulties and consumer behavior are forcing this sector more than ever to reinvent itself in order to guarantee the creation of memorable experiences to retain customers year after year. Thus, different types of festivals, differing in style, ambition, size or even location will be mentioned. This will allow me to obtain a range of different and important responses because the festival-goers themselves will be different. The profile of the festival-goers interviewed is drawn up in a table in the appendix.

D. Sampling Design

In order to obtain a representative sample and varied responses, I will use a purposive sampling method. This non-probability sampling practice is ideal for qualitative research. It is effective for selecting individuals whose responses can be rich in information and aligned with the study's objectives. I will select 21 people from Generation Z with different festival-going backgrounds so that the responses are varied and representative. I am not required to select people who have been to a festival very recently, as my goal is also to identify the types of memories that truly leave a lasting impression.

There will be numerous specific selection criteria. First, I will select people between the ages of 13 and 28, to represent the generation I am targeting. Next, they obviously need to have already attended at least one festival (although I hope that the vast majority of interviewees have attended several.) For the rest, I will opt for a maximum variation sampling to ensure a wide diversity of interviewees. Next, I will look for people with different demographic characteristics (age, professional social categories, place of residence and life path, gender, etc.). I also want to find people for whom festivals don't represent the same thing, people willing to travel to other festivals for a festival, and others who only occasionally go to those close to home.

I will contact the ideal people using various methods. First, I will use my network to directly approach several potential interviewees. Then, I plan to attend certain music-related events such as release parties, festivals, or performances by independent bands to find more specific and interesting profiles to interview. Finally, using snowball sampling, I could ask the initial participants in my study to recommend rarer and more targeted profiles among their acquaintances (for example, people who have volunteered for festivals, people who have organized festivals or artists who have already performed on festival stages and who may have a different perspective on these events). By relying on personal recommendations with snowball sampling, the participation and response rates are much higher because interviewees are more inclined to participate when a trusted person has recommended them. The homogeneity of my sample will be guaranteed by the generation and that of the common life path (an attraction to music and festivals). A table summarizing all participants will be attached.

E. Data Analysis Methods

1. Data Transcription and Editing

The qualitative method I plan to use will allow me to be flexible in data analysis and collection. This will allow me to uncover, explore, and elaborate on unexpected findings that could

influence the outcome of this study and deepen my knowledge in this area. I plan to anticipate potential problems by carefully planning interviews in advance. Furthermore, I will adopt a follow-up approach based on follow-ups if there is any doubt about whether an interview will be conducted. This way, I will avoid inconveniences and missing answers.

My interviews will be conducted verbally, so it will be essential that I be able to record them. I will use the "voice recorder" app on my phone. Transcription will be an essential and necessary aspect of my work in order to subsequently analyze all the data collected. An accurate transcription will allow me to ensure that nothing is forgotten and that everything is recorded. This will also allow me to have multiple readings of my interviews and gain perspective on what I've been told. Connections between different responses from opposing people may emerge as the analysis progresses, which is why I will transcribe all the interviews. My transcriptions will be as accurate as possible, but when necessary, I will not hesitate to correct grammatical or syntax errors, repetitions, or hesitations. The transcriptions will then be reread at the same time as the audio is listened to to ensure maximum reliability. The audio will also be kept and listened to again during the analysis to capture the emotional overtones placed on certain points. Thus, throughout the analysis, a constant comparison will be made between the audio and written material to compare the data and extract as much interesting information as possible.

An initial analysis will be conducted immediately after I finish conducting an interview. I will note trends and key keywords from the responses I have just received. If some of the points have already been raised by other people, or if an emotional accent was observed in a similar place compared to another interviewee, it will be interesting to note this without further delay.

Next, thematization will be a crucial step in my post-interview analysis. At this point, I must absolutely identify recurring themes, words, and trends that can help me answer my research question and its implications. What memories are particularly memorable at festivals? How do these memories evolve over time? What impact do they have on engagement? These questions are asked in a way that will be understandable to the interviewees, and the responses will be organized into themes for analysis.

Another part of the analysis will then be to identify the frequency with which certain words, concepts, or ideas recur in the responses. Some of the codes were pre-established, but thanks to the method I chose, I will be able to identify many of them as the interviews progress and in the post-interview analysis. Ultimately, we will obtain a set of key codes and themes that will answer my research question and provide comprehensive academic information that may be useful to professionals in this sector. All of this will be further explored through quotes from my interview participants.

2. Coding Method

To begin the interview analysis process, I would start by rereading all of my transcripts. This would allow me to clarify my understanding of the topic and the responses obtained. Once this was done, I would begin the coding process. This method involves identifying and highlighting key points, themes, words, or recurring phrases in my interviews. These will then be labeled based on how they respond to the questions and their relevance. For example, when asked "How

do you feel when you remember your festival memories?," if the word "nostalgia" comes up among the majority of interviewees, then it is essential to classify it.

To carry out this step, I would multiply the tables, both on paper and in Excel, in order to process and clarify a large number of lines of text. In this way, the classification will be simpler and I will then know which ideas to develop during my analysis. The tables will allow me to indicate the names of the people who expressed certain ideas. Thus, I could select the most appropriate quotes to illustrate each of my points. Generating graphs based on common themes can greatly help in the visual representation of the ideas I wish to develop. Once the coding has begun and the tables are completed, it will be my responsibility to develop and group together each of the codes sharing a common idea, concept or theme in order to capture the essence and hidden meaning of the different responses. Examples of the tables produced will be included in the appendix.

I have therefore decided to group all the responses obtained under 13 codes which, taken together, should allow me to clearly, pertinently, and chronologically trace the entirety of how festival memories are constructed, evolve, and have a lasting influence on engagement. The 13 codes are as follows: Participant profile, significant sensory moments, personal emotions experienced, collective excitement, memories retained as significant, perceived transformation, reconstructed memory, evolution of memory, post-festival sharing, social attachment to the festival, forms of post-festival engagement, influence of memory on engagement, and finally, limits to engagement. These themes will encompass, in chronological order, what the festival experience is like from the perspective of memorability and engagement.

The next step will be to refine the identified codes in order to structure the thematic analysis in a rigorous and faithful manner. This will involve grouping certain codes into broader categories if logical links or overlaps emerge, or, conversely, splitting overly generic elements to reveal nuances. To ensure the consistency and reliability of the results, particular attention will be paid to the traceability of the selected excerpts, the link between the data and the theoretical concepts drawn from the literature review, as well as the repetition of themes. I will also strive to improve the organization and quality of the collected data, particularly by cleaning up quotes from the transcripts (rewording, summarizing, and correcting any typos). All of these operations will aim to structure and contextualize the analysis of the interviews. This will allow me to precisely answer the research question by highlighting significant dynamics, regularities, or tensions in festival-goers' relationship to their memories and post-event engagement.

To conclude, a methodology based on semi-structured interviews will allow me to conduct in-depth interviews with Generation Z festival-goers with varied backgrounds and feelings, using open-ended questions. I allow myself the freedom to adjust my interview and to bounce off the responses of the interviewees. An analysis will aim to group the information gleaned by theme and, if necessary, this information will be grouped or split through different coding cycles. Subsequently, a refinement will allow these codes and themes to be grouped within several broader points in order to avoid redundancies. This will therefore allow for a faithful representation of the data. The purpose of this analysis will be to interpret, explain and develop the ideas that emerged within structured paragraphs.

PART 4 – Analysis of Results

In this analysis of the results, we will trace the complete journey of festival memories based on the responses of a panel of individuals from Generation Z. We will follow a chronological order to follow the path, from the creation of memorable memories to their impact on engagement. I invite you to begin your reading by starting with a short but essential section that deals with the profile of festival-goers of this generation.

A. The profile of the festival-goers interviewed

To accurately understand how memories created at music festivals are constructed and evolved for Generation Z, it's essential to examine the profiles of the festival-goers we surveyed for this study. Attending this type of event is an action whose value differs for each individual. This has the effect of influencing the memories that emerge from these experiences. It's therefore important to conduct a quick review of our respondents' expectations and the festivals they attended.

1. Practices and motivations

First, let's analyze our sample to understand how music festivals are anticipated. This section will be based primarily on statistics; the following sections will focus more on quotes from the interviews.

We note that among our 21 interviewees, 14 reported attending festivals more than once a year. Seven others said they attend occasionally, when the opportunity arises. Each person who responded to my interviews was fond of music and this type of event; otherwise, they would not have been selected. It's worth noting that the vast majority of respondents struggle to define themselves as having extensive festival experience, regardless of the number of festivals attended. *"I haven't been to a lot of festivals," Lucas said.*

Another interesting statistic: 14 reported having already traveled outside the region to attend festivals. And these are not necessarily the people who attend this type of event most frequently. This type of travel is sometimes planned, but can also be more spontaneous, dictated simply by the desire to be there: *"In Bourges, we took the bus with a friend even though we didn't know where we were going to end up" - Mathilde.* Among the people interviewed, most of these trips were to Belgium or Paris. Sometimes for specific events like New Year's Eve for *"the biggest New Year's festival in the world" - Antoine.* Moreover, going to a specific location for an event can also be a criterion and a motivation: *"It's special, though. Seeing so many people come from who knows where to spend New Year's together." - Adrien.* Thus, travel doesn't really seem to be a major obstacle for Generation Z.

It is also interesting to look at festival preferences. For this analysis, I tried, based on the transcripts, to discern the most memorable type of festival for each of the interviewees, based on the names mentioned. We then see a great disparity.

6 of the 21 people surveyed seem to be more influenced by local and small festivals.

5 people seem to be more affected by larger festivals.

And finally, 10 people mentioned names of both small and large festivals.

The size of festivals is an important point. Some people, like *Marius*, prefer to go to smaller festivals for their conviviality: *"I would prefer to go to a lot more smaller festivals, with lesser-known bands, and a good atmosphere, a bit of conviviality."* This is also the case for *Alex*. He says he prefers this type of festival for their *"family"* aspect and for the people he meets there: *"Really, a great atmosphere. There were a lot of people chatting. Because Zik en Brousse is a lot of people in their 40s and 50s. And we really saw people I knew who were rather solitary, going on the dance floor, dancing with people they didn't know at all."* - *Alex*.

Everyone has their own preferences when it comes to the festivals they want to attend. Some will be more attracted to large-scale festivals. Often, these people will be impressed by their immensity. This is the case for *Lucas*: *"Les Ardentes really left a lasting impression on me. Because I saw all the biggest rap artists of the moment. Also for the size of the festival, with all the stages, the crowds there."* The number of people present or the size of a venue seem to be important factors in memorability. This is also what *Adrien* says: *"Really memorable. Let's say it's going to be the Fucking New Year. In Brussels. First time I've been surrounded by so many people. There are always people. Huge venues."*

Another point that deserves analysis lies in motivations. It is accepted that our expectations regarding an event will directly impact our satisfaction afterward and therefore, by extension, its memorability. Here, I undertook to analyze the different motivations that can drive Generation Z festival-goers to attend this type of event.

Based on the transcripts, I separated these motivations into four distinct categories:

- First, hedonistic motivation. This refers to the search for immediate pleasure, relaxation, and entertainment.
- Second, social motivation. This is linked to the need for social interaction, sharing, and group cohesion.
- Musical motivation. This is centered on the music itself. It can be driven by the desire to see favorite artists live, the desire to discover new styles, etc.
- Finally, experiential motivation. This encompasses the desire to live a unique sensory or immersive experience. This can include the scenography, the atmosphere, the additional activities, the venue, etc.

By analyzing the responses of the various people in the interviews we conducted, we can define Generation Z's motivations when attending festivals. For almost all festival-goers, we found a bit of each of these reasons.

Twenty of the 21 people interviewed suggested they had hedonistic motivations. Going to a festival means no longer worrying about tomorrow. Simply living in the present moment and seeking immediate pleasure. With this in mind, *Anaïs* declared, *"It's an adrenaline rush. You don't know what's going to happen during the festival... you let go."* This idea is also echoed by *Mathilde*: *"You immerse yourself in a bubble, in a mood. [...] It's another world."*

Social motivations were mentioned for all festival-goers. Sharing and the search for collective excitement are clearly expressed expectations when attending festivals. With this in mind, *Pauline* declares, *"It's mainly the sharing of music, the sharing of musical tastes. [...] The symbiosis of festival-goers and the general euphoria."* Festivals are also an opportunity to meet people with the same interests as us. *Léane* seems particularly sensitive to this fact: *"There's this whole festival atmosphere [...] a place that allows us to meet people with the same passion as us."* *Alex* will utter a sentence that sums up the social nature of festivals quite well: *"For me, it's really like a living social network."*

Musical motivation also seems to be unanimous among these 21 festival-goers. This is not surprising because, when you go to a festival, it's an opportunity to see artists and performances that you would never have thought of experiencing live. The artists and the shows seem to be the most memorable point for *Léane*: *"What I remember most is seeing big headliners, especially international ones."* Even if seeing international artists is a real source of satisfaction, going to a festival can also be a way to reconnect with past moments through music. This is what *Riad* expresses when asked to name the festivals that have had the greatest impact on him: *"The Yellow Festival [...] They were all artists from my youth, from my adolescence."*

Finally, 20 of the 21 individuals said they were motivated by the experience itself. A festival, unlike a concert or most events, is a complete and varied experience. Going there often means disconnecting for a while and living to the rhythm of the place, the general atmosphere and the activities on offer. This diversity of offer is understood through *Antoine's* testimony: *"There are more artists, more things to listen to, more things to see. I see it a little bit like an attraction."* But he is not the only one to feel transported by going to a festival. When we listen to *Adrien*, we understand that he, too, enjoys going with the flow when he goes to a festival: *"Seeing smiles, seeing the light, hearing music... The fact that it moves, that it gets you moving."* This all-inclusive and comprehensive aspect is also mentioned by *Élisa*: *"You pay for your ticket and you enjoy everything there is, you help yourself, you play, you have fun."*

A festival is a complete and engaging event that isn't limited to simply providing a few services or performances. They are experiences in their own right, designed to meet all the demands and desires that festival-goers might have within a defined time frame. Thus, it's not surprising to see that expectations and motivations are numerous when attending a festival.

Finally, we can note that, in the transcripts, a large number of festival-goers cited their first festival experience as one of their most memorable festivals. In total, this represents 17 of the 21 people interviewed. Sometimes this memory goes back several years, but for these people, it is still clear. When asked what his most memorable festival is, *Lucas* immediately replies: "*Urb'Am because it was my first.*" This sanctification of the first festival is also observable in *Wathek*. For him, the simple fact that his first festival served as his first experience explains its memorability: "*It's the first real festival [...] that's why it really left a mark on me.*" This is where the concept of memorability is introduced. This will accompany us throughout our analysis.

B. The experience of the moment

This first section serves as an introduction to our analysis. This is where the retrospective journey of festival memories will begin. This section will focus on how festival-goers experience their experiences in the moment. Here, we will examine what participants retain while at the festival. This section will serve as a basis for understanding the events that can become defining moments.

1. Sensory immersion

Here, we'll look at how memories are recorded through the different senses and immersion. The way interviewees described their memorable memories speaks volumes about the intensity with which they capture their environment, whether it be sound, visual, or spatial.

Several festival-goers described a sound and visual environment that particularly captivated them as a memorable memory. This is particularly the case for *Lucas*, who says, "*It was starting to get dark, so only the stage was lit up. All of Ziak's fans were starting to take out their headbands. I had also brought a black headband, so I put it on too. I was surprised by the number of fans wearing headbands. It really created a particular mood, a very dark mood. I loved it.*" The fact that this memory was described so precisely reveals the sensory impact it may have had on the interviewee. Others say that all it takes is a well-managed visual environment to transport them and transform any moment into lasting memories. "*The play of light, the brightness, the outdoors, they all play a big role. I remember small scenes in alleys that are rather dark but which, through a play of light, manage to grab us.*" - *Wathek*

A festival is an event where one can quickly find oneself physically challenged. These memories, although sometimes mixed when they concern fatigue, pain (in crowd movements), or other aspects like hunger or thirst, are nonetheless memorable. For example, *Lina* will say, "*So, let's say, yes, between the hunger and the leg pain, I know I was suffering enormously.*" And *Lola* will go so far as to declare, "*I thought I was really going to die*" recounting an anecdote in which she explains that she was gassed. But fortunately, the physical sensations experienced at a festival are not only negative. During my interviews, 7 of the 21 people interviewed explicitly cited adrenaline as a significant sensation that anchored their memories. When asked what will make a memory memorable, *Léane* replied: "*What will play a role will mainly be the adrenaline of the moment, the fact that we are well surrounded.*" Similarly, when *Wathek* was asked what made a memory of pogo still clear in his memory today, he replied, "*I*

don't know if it's a biological mechanism that made me have an adrenaline rush at the time or something like that. Such an emotion that made it stay anchored in me." A strong physical engagement can lead to certain memorability. While he was recounting that a meaningful piece of music that he particularly likes was being played live, *Quentin* said, *"I cried. But, I think it's the first and last time I cried at a festival."* At festivals, it's also common for music to make us feel sensations directly in the body. Whether through its strength, the power of the bass or even through increases in power, some people interviewed describe this sensation: *"The fact of hearing the music not in my headphones or in a speaker, but of feeling it, that it vibrates."* - *Adrien*, *"It vibrates a little in the body with the bass, the music."* - *Clémentine*

A fundamental aspect of festivals is directly linked to the environment. The venue where the event takes place directly impacts the perception and artistic direction of the festival. We note that certain places can even directly arouse emotions in festival-goers.

The first reason, which seems to recur, is when the venue stands out for its immensity. This is particularly the case for *Adrien*, *"It's the first time I've been surrounded by so many people. There are always people. Huge rooms"* or for *Axelle*, *"It seemed quite big to me [...] it seemed immense."*

Another reason that seems important is when the venues are designed and striking for their beauty. They are often described in memorable memories when they coexist in harmony with natural aspects of the environment. *"It was still in the countryside [...] you have the trees around [...] at the Jardin Électronique it was in a garden, but still quite a few trees."* - *Lison* *"It was by the sea, and the weather was nice."* - *Axelle*.

A place can also be memorable for its symbolism. If it's a site we've heard about for a long time, such as a historic site or a square that's mostly closed, then we'll tend to remember it better. *"The Main Square is at the citadel of Arras; it's the place that makes everything happen, because it's a historic site."* - *Audrey*

We notice in the interviews that the interviewees tend to be particularly touched to see a place they're used to being developed for a festival. Rediscovering it through this lens seems to be a significant moment for anyone who's experienced it. This is particularly the case for *Anaïs*, who sees the Vaour festival take over a small village she's known since childhood : *"The place I love most in the world is really Vaour."* or *Alex* who answers *"It's on a long palm field [...] seeing this field filled with 500 people, it warms the heart."* when asked if a festival location had particularly marked him. In total, the 8 interviewees who had the experience of participating in a festival on a field that was familiar to them all said that they had been marked by the layout of this location.

Even if it's not the entire venue itself, it's also common to see a defined space within the festival that can make a statement. Often, these are themed areas or corners set up for resting between concerts (*"A place where you could take naps... very pleasant."* - *Leila*), or places that seem inaccessible most of the time, like backstage or VIP areas *"It was only people who had the means, who were invited as VIPs... that made an impression on me."* - *Leila*

Scenography could be defined by the art of presenting and arranging the space. In a festival, this art can be characterized in different ways. First of all, through the artists. Each one comes

to present their show and is free to cultivate their stage presence. On the other hand, the festival must consider the artistic direction it wants to bring to its own scenography. What decorations? What styles of music on which stages? What overall atmosphere should we try to convey? What should we show festival-goers to evoke emotions? All of these points are worth considering and, if handled well, can leave indelible memories for festival-goers.

Analyzing the interview transcripts, we realize that a significant number of interviewees explicitly cited memorable memories related to the points discussed above. Seven of the 21 people cited memorable memories directly related to the festival’s artistic direction. This is particularly true for *Lola*, who says she prefers techno festivals, particularly because they have strong artistic direction. She gives examples of *Madame Loyal*, a circus-themed festival, and another that had a profound impact on her, a Halloween-themed one. This underlines the importance of visual immersion. Festivals can also focus on a specific stage and arrange it in a unique way to increase the memorability of a moment. *"There was a kind of cave [...] a secondary stage where a small band was playing."* - *Marius*. But festival scenography can also be based on details that add value and a significant atmosphere. *"They had sofas on the floor, it was very cozy."* - *Marius*

Six of the 21 people interviewed spoke of a memorable memory related to the scenography of one or more artists. This is particularly the case for *Lina*: *"She was in the air, playing the violin... The lights always matched her outfit."* Or for *Axelle*: *"I thought Disiz had great scenography, you know, compared to Luidji, who just had a small red light, and had brought his entire set, and those are things that really left an impression on you."* She even describes a "Wow!" effect: *"I remember when he came on stage, we were like, 'Oh yeah! He brought what he needed, right?'"*

Another, less controllable but equally essential aspect of memory is circumstantial. At festivals, we are often confronted with climatic and natural conditions that cannot be regulated. However, the latter are essential for memorability. Thus, 17 of the interviewees recounted memories related to the weather or the nature of the festival venue itself.

While these meteorological memories are often positive (beautiful weather, a starry night, a sunset), in some cases, they can be more mixed. *Lina* explains that, during the queue, it was raining heavily. Only this memory ultimately turned positive when it allowed her to meet and talk to someone who had an umbrella: *"It was raining [...] but the support of the people [...] she spent all morning covering me with her umbrella."* Ultimately, at festivals, individuals seem more resilient and less bothered by hassles like rain or gray skies. The only truly negative memory that emerges is when *Leila* saw her festival experience disrupted because of this: *"They canceled (one day of the festival) because there was going to be a storm."*

As for nature, the testimonies received are positive: *"It's nice when it's in nature, in a park, with a pond... it makes it cozy."* - *Audrey*, *"It was in a garden but still quite a few trees. I remember that sometimes, it was a bit like little passages: you don't know where you're going."*

Ultimately, circumstances can also be enough to create an indelible memory when they come together. This is what *Quentin* tells us with emotion. He explains that, as the sun rose and everyone was gathered on the ruins of a castle, he saw two horses running free burst in and run towards them. This allows us to transition to the next point discussed, regarding memory creation through sensory immersion. The final factor that can create meaningful memories appears to be unexpected sound and visual elements. Surprise stimulates the senses, which anchors memories. This can be reflected in the points reviewed previously. One can be surprised by a clap of thunder, by a stunning stage design, or simply by discovering a festival venue.

By analyzing the interview responses, I realized that the element of surprise was the trigger for memorable memories for 20 of the 21 festival-goers interviewed. Whether it was a grand finale, the appearance of horses, a change of mood during a concert, an atmosphere that develops before an artist, or unexpected encounters, almost all of them cited moments they hadn't anticipated or hoped for among their most memorable ones.

Finally, by analyzing the memories shared by festival-goers, I was able to discern which of the five senses could leave the most lasting impressions.

Regarding sight, 100% of festival-goers recounted memories in which it played a central role. Whether it was through the sight of unexpected events, epic shows, or simply the sight of their loved ones. Not a single festival-goer failed to mention things they had seen.

The same goes for hearing. Again, in a festival context, it's not surprising that 100% of those surveyed recounted memories in which hearing played an important role. This sense is central to social interactions and the music we listen to.

Regarding touch, 90.48% of individuals mentioned it in one way or another. During pogos, fatigue-related pain, crowd movements, or even a large number of social interactions, touch is very often present.

For taste, this value drops to 61.9% of respondents. This means that, among the memorable memories or mentions festival-goers shared with us, only a little over half included an aspect related to taste. This may seem surprising given how carefully organizers curate their refreshment and food offerings.

Finally, the least prominent sense at a festival is smell. Only 19% of interviewees mentioned any kind of smell or scent.

Seeing that the senses are so stimulated in so many different ways isn't necessarily surprising given the composition and content of modern festivals. However, before continuing, it's interesting to note which senses leave the most memorable memories for Generation Z.

2. Individual emotional intensity

Although awakening and stimulating the senses is a powerful factor in immersion and memorability, it's not the only factor that helps anchor memories. It's important not to overlook individual emotional intensity. This represents all the emotions a person feels related to who they are. These emotions can therefore be influenced by the experience of the person experiencing them, by the relationships they have with the people around them, or by their perceptions. These are strong emotions that can leave a lasting impression.

When we analyze the interview responses, we realize that individuals recall feeling many emotions at the time. One of the emotions that seems to recur in particular is euphoria: *"It was really always in this spirit of euphoria"* - Pauline, *"at the time, we're really very, very, very euphoric"* - Antoine. We also note that most festival-goers remember being captivated, transported, or swept away by certain events, such as concerts or unexpected happenings. Excitement also comes up several times: *"I was like crazy because it was exceptional"* - Riad, *"A DJ Snake finale that really got me going, it really left a mark on me."* - Audrey. Still others, like Anaïs, will recount feeling a sense of calm and total immersion: *"It was super*

exciting. It was very profound.", "It's just a crazy excitement and a pretty exceptional feeling too."

We also note that festivals can be prone to very strong personal emotions, as *Lina* testifies: *"For two months, I was like a madman, saying to myself, 'Wow, I really have to go now!' [...] I had trouble sleeping; the music was in my ears all the time."* Here, we note that the overexcitement caused by a festival can leave a strong mark. That's not all, some festival-goers also reported having cried during stage performances: *"I cried [...] the music was incredible"* - *Quentin*. Finally, some also reported feeling literally stunned by artists: *"I got a huge slap in the face."* - *Adrien*, or having felt a real crush on them: *"I had an artist crush."* - *Mathilde*. Finally, emotions such as feeling hypnotized or going wild were also mentioned in the interviews: *"I love this kind of atmosphere so much [...] it almost hypnotizes me."* - *Maxence*, *"Everyone goes wild and doesn't think about anything else."* - *Wathek*.

The emotions that each person feels are also impacted by the personality or experience of the person experiencing them. Therefore, it is important to understand the contexts in which these factors can influence a festival-goer's feelings and experience. First of all, it comes up several times that having already seen an artist somewhere before will reinforce the wow effect when you see them at a festival. *"It's someone I saw on TV... it does something to you."* - *Wathek* (talking about MB14.)

Also, the anticipation of seeing a favorite song or artist perform that you've been listening to for a long time will create excitement and then a powerful effect when the long-awaited moment arrives: *"It's the anticipation of the present moment [...] seeing Vald in concert [...] his favorite music, that we stream"* - *Pauline*, *"I was a real fan of B.B. Jacques [...] I knew almost all of his songs"* - *Antoine*

Finally, the impact of an outing as engaging and comprehensive as a festival can take on a completely different symbolism depending on the person's experience. *Axelle* particularly remembers one of her experiences because *"It was our first evening where you dance, where you meet people."*

A memory can also be made memorable by the attachment and relationship you have with the person you share it with. This can have a strong personal impact and intensify the emotions felt. Along these lines, *Axelle* recounts how she herself started to cry when she saw her best friend's tears in front of an artist she adores. *"She made me cry, like seeing her cry."* This idea of emotions heightened by loving the person you share them with is also echoed by *Pauline*: *"It's when you meet your friends' eyes, you say, 'Yeah, this is crazy,' what we're experiencing, you realize. It's a bit like a trance, a little trance where you say, 'Yeah, we're experiencing this together.'"* It's interesting to note that 100% of the festival-goers surveyed expressed, implicitly or not, having felt rare or unusual emotions. These include total fulfillment, a trance, a sense of letting go, a feeling of harmony, or even fear: *"I was scared [...] I thought I was really going to die"* - *Lola*, *"just letting go, all the letting go [...] we're celebrating"* - *Clémentine*, *"These moments are rare, I find, in everyday life."* - *Wathek*. Festivals therefore leave no one indifferent from Generation Z and serve to convey feelings that are not found elsewhere.

Finally, by analyzing the transcripts of my interviews, I realized that festivals can also be a vehicle for feelings of pride. Indeed, there are many events intrinsic to festivals that can provide a sense of personal accomplishment.

When you listen to an artist frequently, it's not uncommon to feel close to them, like part of their privileged community. Seeing him in concert can be a kind of finalization and a source of pride for someone who appreciates the artist's work. This is the case for *Clémentine*: "*Tiff, I'd been waiting a long time to see him, and he did one of my favorite songs, Hinata, and it's always nice to listen to your favorite music live.*" Another feeling of pride can come when you see an artist and feel like you know their entire discography perfectly: "*So, they're there. It's cool. I know all their music.*" - *Lina*. Finally, another moment that can cause pride is introducing one of your favorite artists live to your friends and seeing them love it: "*I had already seen him [...] seeing him in Amiens made me happy, especially since my friends had never seen him.*"

Other unexpected events can give us pride during the festival. For example, being photographed for a newspaper: "*I have one in particular that stands out for me, it's that I was photographed with my friends for a newspaper.*" - *Riad*, getting a tattoo on a whim with her friend "*And so, we've been friends since childhood, we've known each other for a really long time [...] And so, we wanted to get a small tattoo. That's it. Quite simply [...] Spontaneously. Without thinking too much about it*" or even, playing on a small stage unexpectedly like *Marius*: "*I sit down on the piano, a little shy [...] There were other people who weren't with us at all. And it was a great moment, it was actually my first jam session because I wasn't used to playing with other musicians like that [...] It was quite a magical moment [...] And then, that way, I was able to go see my family and say that I played at R4.*"

Finally, 76.19% of those surveyed had strong memories of moments where they felt feelings close to pride or personal accomplishment during a festival. Thus, we see that individual emotional intensity plays an important role in the memorability of memories. But, now that we've talked about personal emotions, it's time to address a central point in festival memorability. This point concerns collective intensity.

3. Collective intensity

We have reviewed how the senses and the inherent experience of the festival-goer can contribute to creating lasting memories; there is still one essential point to analyze. This concerns collective intensity and synchrony. These are all the rituals and social interactions that, taken together, shape the festival experience and greatly impact memories and their memorability. The festival is a social space, or rather, "*it's really like a living social network,*" as *Alex* puts it. It is therefore normal that connection with other members of the audience, whether acquaintances or strangers, is also present in these interviews and deserves its own subsection.

First of all, most of the festival-goers interviewed engaged in social rituals at festivals. These practices, typical of festivals, include a wide variety of things. They can be pogos, shared chants, crowd movements, or even giant caterpillars. These actions are initiated spontaneously and are often catalysts for memorability. Among these memorable memories, *Maxence*, for

example, recalls: *"the artists would come right into the pit and dance with us, they would do the caterpillar, etc..."* Lison, too, talks about dancing. Not specifically with the artists but with strangers: *"I dance, I'm with my friend... there are guys who are there in the mode they start to dance with us."* One of the most typical social rituals of festivals are the pogos, there too, several interviewees mention them in their memories: *"Afterwards when people did pogos, with the dust, all that was fun."* - Audrey. Although there are a large number of typical actions and it would be impossible to list them all, it is impossible to end this point without talking about the unison songs which seem to have the effect of often being memorable: *"We all started to sing Lujipeka... We were like a big choir, all together."* - Alex, *"we sang with them, only the drummer was still playing in the background"* - Antoine. And even for some who recounted experiences working at festivals, these rituals remain at the heart of the experience: *"I work while singing, while dancing, and I do that with the people who are waiting for their order."* - Riad. Finally, in all my interviews, only one person did not explicitly mention one of these rituals in their memorable memories. This proves the importance of the general atmosphere and collective synchrony in this type of event.

Another phenomenon whose memorability seems to be high, based on the transcripts, is that of merging with the rest of the audience. When the crowd becomes one and the individual seems to fade away in favor of the collective, these are often powerful moments that leave a lasting impression and transport the festival-goer. For example, *Wathek* seemed amazed to feel this phenomenon: *"That's what strikes me, a crowd that becomes one in front of someone, that becomes one in front of a center of attention."* This idea of gathering around something can be found in what *Léane* says: *"as we all love music, it's really a place that brings people together."* This idea of union can be impressive and some people even talk about an energy that emerges from this kind of observation: *"We still share the same energy, we're on the same wave."* - Riad, *"there's a bubble around people, that's what's created"* - Quentin. For *Adrien*, when you go to a festival, you *"feel a little less alone [...] you share something with people."* and this idea of not feeling alone and being part of a community is also found in *Lucas* who explains: *"There really wasn't a single person who wasn't singing them." [...] The community was singing along and screaming.* So, thanks to this fusion of audiences when you go to a festival, *"you feel like you've experienced the same thing."* - Lola

The crowd also has the power to transform seemingly ordinary moments into truly memorable memories. This is the case for *Lina*, who explains that, during one concert, she was quite far from the stage and couldn't see the artist particularly well, but the simple sight of the immensity of the crowd in front of her etched this memory in her mind. Similarly, *Audrey* explains that leaving the festival was one of the most memorable moments because of the crowd all moving in the same direction: *"And when everyone was leaving the festival [...] it's a moment I remember well."* For *Riad*, it's the fact of conversing and having fun with the customers that makes working at festivals more stimulating: *"Even if they're customers and I'm working, we can enjoy ourselves together."*

Regarding interactions with strangers, it is important to note during this analysis that many festival-goers recounted exchanges, often brief but spontaneous, that particularly struck them. These are, most of the time, surprising and reinforce the idea of a friendly living together and fully participate in the festival experience. In this context, for Generation Z, it is normal to

talk with people around *"We talk in the pit with our neighbors" - Pauline*. Festival-goers go through a whole range of emotions and mutual aid is a natural way that greatly promotes encounters *"a group of girls [...] completely panicked [...] we sympathize with them" - Adrien*. This idea where everyone can talk and exchange without barriers of age or language is strongly echoed: *"I remember dancing with random children." - Élisabeth*. And sometimes, there's no need for the excuse of dancing, proximity, or mutual support; the festival atmosphere is enough to spark conversions. *Alex* tells us that, at a festival, he sat in a circle on the grass with his friends, and many strangers walked by and sat with them just to chat. *"People could come in, they came to chat with us. It was a really great time."* Ultimately, 76.19% of respondents detailed interactions with strangers as their highlight at a festival.

But community at a festival isn't just about strangers or the crowd. It also includes the people with whom we decide to attend the event. And, for Generation Z, going to a festival is mostly done with friends. All respondents said they had already attended a festival with their circle of friends. Some, however, say they've already been there with their families, but for most of them, these memories date back to when they were younger and not necessarily as independent as they are today. Sharing this type of experience with loved ones helps you get the most out of it and also has a reassuring quality.

Coming with friends or family also seems to be an excellent way to create lasting memories. *Marius* tells us that with his friends from the music workshop, he decided to go on stage to play a jam session. Even today, it seems to be one of his best memories: *"We were warming up to go there [...] we agree on what we're playing [...] You realize how well it works when you play together."* By analyzing the results, I realized that phrases such as *"with my girlfriend and her friend [...] we were right at the front with my friends" - Leila*, *"plus I was next to a friend of mine" - Lola* or *"We really liked it with our friends" - Léane*, came up very often. As if, after telling an anecdote or a memorable memory, specifying that we shared it with our friends further accentuates its positive side. From this principle, we can deduce that the people interviewed associate positive emotions with the people who shared them. This shows that coming to a festival with people we love accentuates the happiness generated and the memorial quality of the memories taken away. Finally, when we ask festival-goers directly what, in their opinion, made a memory memorable. Some, like *Maxence*, respond that it is the people who were with them *"the people I came with."*

Coming with friends can also give rise to specific and very strong interactions. These are often very intense and remain in the memory for a very long time. Festivals give rise to a reinforced complicity, frequently mentioned as superior to that which can be experienced otherwise. This is the type of experience that *Clémentine* tells us about: *"A friend who was with me was particularly touched too and we just looked at each other and without really speaking, we understood each other."* These moments can be experienced as a couple but also with an entire group. This is what *Axelle* remembers with emotion: *"when you really have a good time, you laugh and you look at your friends. You know you're going to remember it. Yeah. You know you're going to remember that moment."* But these particularly intense moments of complicity can also give way to specific actions as was the case for *Lola*: *"we've been friends since childhood [...] we wanted to get a little tattoo [...] it remains a great*

memory for me." These types of moments are particularly memorable, but they're quite rare. Festivals seem to be the perfect place to create them with people close to us.

Finally, this type of event is also the perfect place to strengthen or renew bonds. Several festival-goers interviewed mentioned specific situations in which attending a festival allowed them to get closer to someone. *Élisa* tells us how coming to a festival that had been planned for a long time with her old friend allowed them to reconnect. She explains that at one point, they wanted to take *"a best friend photo, in front of the stage."* According to her, *"It was the moment when it was natural to take a photo together."* Ultimately, the festival and actions like these allowed them to get closer: *"It erased the argument [...] it was kind of the festival that made us reconnect."* Festivals can also make people more aware of the value and qualities of those around them. We find this idea in *Léane's* testimony, who recounts what happened when one day of the festival was cancelled due to bad weather: *"My friend was trying to put things into perspective for me [...] You have to find the right person to go with."* For people who participated in the co-creation of the festival in one way or another, the awareness of the bonds that unite us with the other festival-goers seems even more marked: *"all together, it was crazy, it was crazy [...] we built something all together for a week and a half" - Quentin.* Finally, for some people like *Anaïs*, going to a festival was a way to get very close to one of her acquaintances, to the point that she has now become one of her best friends: *"one of my current best friends, I met her at R4. It wasn't necessarily planned at the start and we ended up meeting up."*

Thus, by analyzing the transcripts of the interviews conducted during this study, we were able to draw up a fairly comprehensive picture of what Generation Z identifies as memorable at festivals. By examining the issue through the prism of sensory immersion, personal emotional intensity, and collective intensity, we clearly identified the different factors that can impact memorability at this type of event. However, to further this analysis, we will now examine the meaning and perception that festival-goers gain from these experiences.

C. Meaning and perception of the experience

Everything we experience or feel is bound to evolve in our memory. We attach meaning to all the events that happen to us. Sometimes, we like to reinvent ourselves through stories of things that have happened to us. We perceive our experiences arbitrarily, influenced by the person we would like to be. Festival memories are no exception. In this section, we will examine what festival-goers consider to be memorable memories, what allows them to detach themselves from the world around them, and the memories that can trigger lasting transformations in them.

1. Elements perceived as memorable

Although our analysis reveals a lot about what seems to make a festival memorable, it's interesting to get the perspective of other festival-goers. During my interviews, I asked festival-goers to tell me what they think makes a festival truly memorable. I'm going to delve into their answers to understand how they perceive their festival experiences.

First of all, one of the most common responses is the overall atmosphere of the festival. For *Adrien*, it's essential that *"the audience be there."* He knows a festival will be great if *"no one comes to ruin my flow or my vibe."* For *Axelle*, too, atmosphere is the first thing that comes to mind when asked: *"A good atmosphere, if everyone is in a good mood, if nothing serious happens, or anything like that."* For *Maxence*, too, atmosphere is the key factor: *"the atmosphere of the festival-goers."* If you don't have it, it can be well organized, have the best music in the world, but it can only be disappointing.

Another idea that comes up particularly often about what a memorable festival should be is regarding the stage and the artists. Many of the festival-goers interviewed attach significant importance to this point. This is particularly the case for *Lina*: *"the staging they have, the outfits, what's happening, the choreography if there is any, the artistic stuff. So yeah, really the general atmosphere of what's happening on stage."* But she's not the only one hoping to see a live show. In this spirit, *Lucas* declares that for him, the important thing is: *"The atmosphere, the mood that the artist manages to create in terms of the scenography, in terms of the venue where the concert takes place, and the atmosphere that the artist's fans will manage to create."* Does the rapper have a good fan base, does he know the lyrics well, will he be able to sing throughout the concert and therefore create a good atmosphere? In summary, and to echo *Riad's* words, the important thing for a good festival is: *"that the artists know how to create a good atmosphere. They know how to do their job, and a good audience too, of course. But that's up to the artist to build, I think."*

The artistic direction of the venue and its layout also seems to be a recurring point. *Mathilde* clearly states that to make a festival memorable, you have to take care of the decor: *"the venue itself, like the decorations, the site itself."* This idea is largely echoed by *Élisa*: *"the design, the decor, if the stage is beautiful, it's decorated. If the booths are decorated as well, the stage, the poster, the wristband, the same."* For many of the people who responded, taking care of the design or the artistic direction seems to be an inherent concept of memorable festivals: *"the best would be to have a strong artistic direction [...] It's not just the artistic performances, there's also the event, what's around the festival besides the music. The catering, the refreshments, the activities or other things offered."* - *Pauline*.

Another central element mentioned by many festival-goers concerns the people with whom we share the experience. For a large number of respondents, this is an essential factor in making this type of event memorable. For *Antoine*, it is even the most important point: *"First of all, it's really the group of people we go with. If the group of people is really up for listening to this kind of music, spending the same kind of time together, really that's the best."* This observation, he shares with *Léane*, when asked what aspect is essential for a truly memorable festival, she replies: *"being well surrounded. Not with a friend like that, really with your best friends with whom you really want to discover artists and do things. Friends also who are in the same organization as us."* But friends are not the only people we meet at festivals, for *Marius*, this is the case but also: *"the meetings you make, the friends you go with, that kind of thing."*

Regarding the perception of memorable moments experienced at festivals, *Quentin* develops an idea. He defines the concept of *"entre-sort."* That is to say: *"little unplanned, somewhat*

random events that leave a crazy mark. [...] There's a guy who starts playing the sax and people dance around him. It's improbable, things like that aren't planned, a bit like entre-sorts." For him, "It makes a festival more lively, more memorable, more intimate. You get closer to the festival with these things. People too." Anaïs echoes this idea, referring to "madness in the broadest sense, improbable things, the unexpected" as vectors of strong sensations. Finally, by analyzing these interviews, I realize that, even if it is not necessarily mentioned in the memorable memories because it is surely too little visible during a festival, logistics and organization are perceived by the majority of respondents as a necessary basis for a festival to be memorable "it needs good organization so that everyone feels good, everyone feels safe, there are measures in place in case things go wrong" - Riad. With this in mind, Lucas tells us about a festival that particularly disappointed him because of logistical issues: "what can make it memorable on the negative side will be the quality of the speakers, of everything that has to do with sound. I remember a festival I did in Belgium, it was called Fucking New Year. There were big problems with the speakers [...] it really lowered the quality of the experience. Even the artists themselves, we could see that it surprised them, that they weren't comfortable with the sound quality. And so, that was disappointing, hearing bad sound when you came to listen to music. It's true that that can be memorable in a bad way."

Now that we've seen what Gen Z festival-goers believe are the most important for a successful festival, let's conclude this aspect of anchoring memories by looking at the meaning and importance they can have.

2. Feeling of rupture and escape

Festivals, more than any other event, seek to provoke a disconnection in their customers. Festival-goers, for their part, are looking for this disconnection. Coming to a festival is a commitment. In terms of energy, time, and money. Festival-goers therefore seek to make the most of the event by completely cutting themselves off from the rest of the world. We will now examine this point and see what results from the analysis of our interviews.

One of the striking aspects noted in the interviews is the strong feeling of escape that the festival experience can provide. Many festival-goers used the term "timeless." For them, these events are a break from everyday life. *Adrien* describes it very well: *"It was a place outside of time, outside of space, a bubble of music with people, alcohol, partying, light... I felt like I was in another dimension."* This disconnection is even sought by several interviewees: *"That's often why I go, to finally break away from everyday life" - Lola, "That's kind of what I'm looking for, actually" - Mathilde* (talking about being in another world.) This escape allows you to forget the worries of everyday life *"So, you have all your problems that you might have had outside that are... that don't exist, let's say, for evenings of a few hours anyway." - Maxence*, or the routine that can sometimes be difficult: *"I find it's a bit out of time, where you get out of your daily life, which can be a bit boring" - Lison*

This search for escape can also be put into perspective with the desire to live in the present moment to the fullest. Several festival-goers mention a change in their relationship to the present when they are at a festival. *Anaïs* also expresses it very well when asked what gives her the feeling of being in another world: *"Maybe the key to all this is because you are in the*

present moment. [...] You don't need to be in contact with the outside world because you are in the experience of a moment that is happening before your eyes." This reflection is also shared by *Wathek*: "Every second that passes, we live it. We don't wonder what will happen in 10 minutes, what happened 20 minutes ago. It's really what is happening now, what I just experienced a few seconds ago." For *Riad*, what triggers this feeling is being overwhelmed by the sensations he experiences throughout the festival: "There are so many emotions, so much stimulation from all around that you actually completely forget what's going on in your life, you're just 100% in the present moment, and that's so good."

The festival's spatial setting seems to reinforce this sense of disconnection. Being physically present and immersed in a rather extraordinary environment that takes you away from your daily routine is seen by many festival-goers as a factor in the sense that you feel transported. For *Élisa*, the festival feels like a "parenthesis in your life, in your week. You're there, you're fully there. You're not managing emails, your work, you're not doing your homework; you're there, and you're enjoying yourself." This idea is extended by *Audrey*: "it's a change from your daily routine of metro-work-sleep. It's different, you feel like you're living a moment outside of time, you're in another world, you feel the music, you feel the bass in your heart." This disruption of the spatial framework can also be disorienting: "you just have this space, and there's nothing else, the city doesn't exist." - *Adrien*. The setting of a festival is very different from what we know. When you're a festival-goer, you live to the rhythm of the concerts, not to the rhythm of the day or the night: "you're set up like that, it's like you're set up in the middle of nowhere, and you have lots of stages. There's also an atmosphere when it starts to get dark" - *Leila*

Of course, it's not just the spatial setting and the break from being in the present moment that can be a vector of transport to another world. Music can also play a big role. Fully experiencing an anticipated concert can even be a motivation to want to disconnect completely. *Quentin* says he was even completely transported during the *Disiz* concert: "It's incredible. And you're transported because you know [...] I cried. But, I think it's the first and last time I cried at a festival." This testimony can be linked to a state of trance or that of putting oneself in a "bubble," it reveals a strong impact. He is not the only one to have been able to fully enter a concert. *Axelle* tells us that her friend appreciated an artist so much that she also shed tears from the emotion. This idea of a "bubble" is echoed in several testimonies, such as *Alex*'s: "Lujipeka, with my friends surrounded by the crowd, like in a bubble where everyone sings. It's truly exceptional."

For some, festivals are also a political and social escape. The festival setting acts as an alternative world, outside of societal codes and norms. *Lison* compares festivals to rave parties: "I find it a bit timeless [...] it's a bit of a protest space, and where you put yourself somewhat apart from the rest of the world." This shows that this type of event can act as a temporary zone of emancipation where everyone is free to exist and express themselves as they see fit.

Finally, during my analysis, I was surprised to see that several of the people I interviewed spoke to me about their own desire to completely disconnect by not using their phones or social media. Cutting themselves off from these channels seems to allow them to gain greater

memorability and satisfaction from a festival. Anaïs explains: *"I know that when I'm at a festival, especially when I'm a volunteer, I'm never on my phone, also because in Vaour there's no connection [...] but you don't need to be in contact with the outside world because you're in the preparation when you're a volunteer or in the experience of a moment that's happening before your eyes."* This disconnect allows her to better anchor herself in the present, which is also the case for Éliisa: *"I try to be on my phone as little as possible, not to answer my messages, it's something I really try to do, to create this festival world."* Lison expresses that beyond the simple phone break, what she is looking for is above all to cut herself off from negative information coming from outside *"You are not going to follow everything that is happening, finally all the news in the world which is a little distressing [...] it's a bit like, you are in another happy world."* This practice is not inherent to these people but can evolve and be triggered following a resolution which will influence a change in behavior. Lola explains it well: *"Before, when I started going to festivals, for example, I made a lot of videos on my phone [...] now, I capture things differently than with my phone."*

All this information clearly shows that Generation Z festival-goers crave and appreciate this disconnection. They want to feel transported to an alternative world and forget their everyday problems. Now, to conclude this section, let's analyze how festivals can provoke a feeling of lasting transformation in festival-goers.

3. Feeling of lasting transformation

Before beginning this analysis, I didn't realize how transformative the effect of festivals could be. This type of event, due to the interactions that occur there, the symbolism that attendees attach to them, and the multitude of adventures they encompass, can radically change habits, attitudes, and life choices. In my panel of respondents, all reported experiencing a change thanks to their festival experiences. These lasting changes linked to memories can manifest themselves in various forms.

First and perhaps the most obvious transformation is the change in listening habits. Almost all the festival-goers interviewed mentioned listening more to artists or styles of music they enjoyed at festivals: *"What impacts me the most is musically speaking, depending on certain artists, artists I discovered at festivals, I listen to them again afterward. I already knew them a little, but I listen to them a lot more."* - Pauline. Others, like Anaïs, say they have noticed a change in listening habits even before a festival: *"But there, for example, this year, I know that Odezenne, Kompromat, Yoa, etc... are performing... So, it also sometimes pushes me to listen to the artists in question a bit crazy, telling myself it's true that I didn't know them that well. I might as well bleed the thing thoroughly beforehand."* Surprisingly, we note that for some festival-goers like Adrien, seeing an artist in concert is akin to an achievement. He said he finds it harder to listen to them afterward so as not to spoil his memories: *"I don't listen to an artist I've seen live, I'm not going to listen to them again, I'm not going to listen to them again. When I hear the sounds, I'm afraid it will erase the memory I have of the concert."* This is also the case for Léane: *"I know that for me, for example, when I see an artist in concert, after so many years of listening to them, I have less of that adrenaline rush after*

listening to them. In fact, I don't even listen to them at all anymore because I've actually seen them, and suddenly it's as if I've accomplished something."

The change in listening habits is the most common but far from the only one for Generation Z. For many festival-goers, having gone to a festival has made them want to repeat the experience in the future: *"It's over, but it doesn't matter, we'll do it again, it'll come back."* - Alex. This is also the case for Lucas, who realized that he had the desire and the physical ability to go to large festivals over several days: *"I was afraid of getting a little bored. I thought, Okay, one or two days, I'm going to see a lot of artists I like. Won't the fatigue make me a little tired? No, because the fatigue wasn't as strong as I expected."* We also see that festivals have the power to permanently change the mood of those who attend. The memories we keep from these types of experiences continue to have an impact on us, even long afterward: *"the euphoria [...] Which still lasts. For Lollapalooza, yeah, it lasted, but because if I think about it, I was impacted by seeing Stray Kids"* - Lina. This is also the case for Alex: *"So, all the memories made me really happy, I'm happy when I leave a festival, I have a lot of memories in my head."* or Clémentine's case: *"if we have worries in life or we are not necessarily very happy, even for no reason, afterwards, we are a little more liberated, we are happy. Yes, it is an impact in the sense that it can make us happier in our daily lives."* It is also not uncommon to see that someone feels a bit of blues after a festival, like a feeling of emptiness or of no longer having a goal. This is what Mathilde explains to us: *"before getting back into a routine or whatever, I really needed a time where I was still in the continuity of the thing. So, I remember that I needed a few days. There was something a bit... Not depressive, but sad."*

Another profoundly transformative aspect that came up a lot was the fact that festivals can make you more sociable. This phenomenon and this awareness were very well explained by Lucas: *"There was a little bit of the fact that I realized that I'm not at all a shy person, but I don't really approach people like that, a bit for no reason. And I realized that there, at a festival, you could really talk to strangers like that, directly, for no real reason [...]* And that, I told myself that I should do it a bit more in life." Even if Lucas confides that he is not a shy person by nature, this is not necessarily the case for everyone: *"Also, socially, like at the festival, you talk a lot to other people, it's a very social event, that can influence. As I am basically a rather shy and withdrawn person, at the festival it allowed me to open up a little."* - Marius. To sum up, festivals are also an opportunity to change, to overcome introversion, and to be satisfied with who we are becoming: *"I was perhaps able to feel more sociable"* - Audrey.

Although they aren't internal changes, festivals are also a good place to evolve in your life by getting closer to people you had lost touch with. I've selected two of these festival stories that have greatly influenced the rest of the lives of the people who responded: *"I saw someone again that I had only seen at one party. I saw her again three years later at Minuit Avant la Nuit where I was working, and she recognized me, that's how we got back in touch. We started to meet... to become more intimate and to develop a little relationship."* - Riad, *"I already find that festivals are something that can really bring people together. So, I would say that it brought me closer to certain people [...] There are people I'd lost touch with, whom I ran into again at the Fête de la Musique, and today, they're my roommate. So, so funny!"* -

Axelle. But, as Axelle says, festivals aren't just an opportunity to see people you'd lost touch with, they're also an opportunity to get closer to the people you love: "What changed, once again, was in the relationship with the people I went with because, of course, a festival brings you closer." - Maxence

For musicians, going to a festival can take on a whole new meaning. This action can prove to be a source of motivation and a desire to perform on stage. This type of event has fueled the dreams of more than one great artist that everyone listens to today. It can push them to practice more, focus on music, and give it their all. This is what *Élisa* explains: *"From a personal point of view, since I'm a musician in a band, it makes me want to do even more concerts on bigger stages and festivals allow you to have bigger stages too [...] it made me want to do festivals as an artist."* This is also roughly what *Wathek* says when asked if the festivals had an impact on him afterwards: *"From a personal point of view, as a musician, it impacts me. How to improve my stage performance, for example, how to bring more to my musical practice, how to vary all that. There is this inspiration, I would say, from the festival. This creative impulse that comes out. There, we witnessed a beautiful event, a creative event, the fruit of a creative journey. It pushes us in this dynamic."*

Festivals can also be an ideal context for looking back on one's life and taking stock of the past year. This then allows us to see what good things we can keep for the future and to know what makes us feel good. This idea is perfectly illustrated by *Anaïs*: *"This year has been quite unusual for me, it really made me question myself, maybe a little too much. [...] It made me think a lot on an existential level about what are the things that matter most to me in life. [...] And so, I also took stock of my life a little bit, of a whole bunch of things. I know it's not just the festival factor, but I know that it contributed enormously because I was able to meet people at those times this summer, who were incredibly important. [...] I know that if I took a break this year, it's partly linked to this festival thing, to the people I met there."*

To finish on this point, going to a festival also seems to be an opportunity to adopt a very specific new behavior: *"There's one thing that really stood out for me. It was a girl who complimented me on the skirt I was wearing. I thought that was really nice. Plus, it was at a festival, so it was with my best friend where I wasn't necessarily feeling my best. It really lifted my spirits. This girl who came up to talk to me like that, spontaneously, who was so nice to me. It made me want to give compliments for free. Because I saw how it can just lift your spirits. In fact, we don't know how people are experiencing their day, their festival even. So, it's bound to be a bonus in their day. It made me want to give compliments."* - *Élisa*. For *Lola*, it's more at the level of attitude that we see a specific awareness: *"Respect, in the sense that I'm not someone disrespectful or anything, but for example, at a festival, we're all stuck together. For me, for example, it shocked me during my first festival, we were really all stuck together and there was absolutely no one who respected [...] but we pay more attention to each other, maybe after that."* Finally, *Quentin's* example seems quite relevant to me to end this part: *"There are festivals, especially Vaour, that have changed my life [...] I was telling you earlier about Seb, the one who writes poetry on the typewriter. He doesn't have a smartphone, he has a bigophone, a touch-tone telephone. [...] And so, we talked a little about telephones, and it inspired me. When I came back from the festival, I bought a touch-tone telephone, I didn't use it for six months. I didn't use it at all, until I broke my phone. And I*

switched back to the touch-tone phone. And now, I've had a touch-tone phone for three years [...] It's a very big change. Honestly, making that switch. I definitely wouldn't have been the same person."

During this analysis, I noticed that all the people interviewed described changes in their lives following the festival. It was interesting to look at the diversity of these changes. Internal transformations or those in our habits mark us; they stay with us for the rest of our lives, or at least for a long time. They are based on our memories and contribute to their evolution. Now that we have studied how memories are perceived and symbolized by festival-goers, we will continue our chronological journey through the memory of festivals.

D. The memorization process

Memories are built and can provoke profound questioning or change in Generation Z festival-goers. However, they are by no means fixed. The process of memorization is long and truly never ends. A memory can tell a completely different story than what was experienced at the time of its creation. In order to continue this journey through the path that festival memories take, we must devote crucial attention to how memory evolves.

1. The evolution of memory

The memories we create at festivals have evolved considerably. We don't remember every detail of what we've experienced, and our perception of them continues to evolve as we grow and change.

First of all, even if for some festival-goers, the memories seem unchanged and as clear as if they happened a short time ago: *"It's still pretty fresh in my mind. [...] I still have a pretty fresh memory, as if it happened a month, two months, or last year ago, whereas now it's six years ago."* - Adrien. This doesn't seem to be the case for some respondents.

There are those who feel they have changed personally and for whom the memories, while still positive, may have been diminished: *"I've grown up in the meantime. It was in 2019, it's 2025. So obviously a lot of time has passed. So yes, the feeling has definitely changed. I don't remember everything and maybe today I would experience a festival differently. As I grew up I liked being with people less and less, oppressed, I like when there's plenty of space. I would experience that kind of thing differently I think [...] it's definitely diminished"* - Audrey. This idea of diminishment is also found in Pauline who says she has lost this "discovery" aspect: *"I think that over time it has evolved enormously, even the highlights have evolved too. [...] Now we're a little familiar with the festival scene, we know how it works, we already know what it's like, we no longer have the thrill of discovering what a festival is like, how it's going to unfold."*

For some, these memories are still just as positive, but the emotions and energy they exuded have subsided a little: *"I think today, I'm less euphoric. I'm more rational. I honestly tell myself that it was a cool moment that I want to do again. But at the time, for two months, I was like a madman, saying to myself, 'Wow, I really have to go now. I have to go back to my experiences.' I felt the emotions deeply."* - Lina, *"Afterwards, if I really have to go back to my*

raw feeling at the time, I think back to it as if it was a great moment. I was filled with joy and happiness. And it remains a very good memory. But it's true that I might talk about it differently than I would the next day, for example." - Lola.

In conducting this analysis, two rather surprising elements also emerged. The first concerns the evolution of our memories depending on the people with whom we shared them. Some festival-goers implied that their view of their festival memories changed depending on the terms they maintained with their classmates afterward. This is an idea that the perceived value and intensity of a moment already spent can be affected by our actions and our current situation: *"I think back on it with a bit of nostalgia, because it was at a time. Now, I'm not at university anymore. At university, I met a lot of people I don't meet anymore, all of whom have now moved on to different horizons, who have gone to Rouen, Lille, to pursue other studies, who have changed their program. And so, I really think about it with a lot of nostalgia. I say to myself, oh, he was there at that moment. It's true that it's nice. Maybe I could, if we see each other again, be able to talk about all that, that those were really moments, great moments between friends." - Alex. Anaïs, also takes a look at this question: "There is often nostalgia or melancholy that can arise when you think back to certain moments, even sometimes things that you may have experienced with certain people who are no longer there, either because you no longer speak or who are simply no longer there." This is the idea that one of the people interviewed will explain in detail based on a personal story he experienced when he went to a festival with a close friend for the first time: "It's a bubble. In the relationship, I said to myself at that moment, it's perhaps the beginning of a bubble that will last a long time. But actually, since it went badly a week or two later, it's just a bubble, a memory that I'm trying to seal off. But that was 2-3 years ago. At the time, when it went badly, for a few days after, I was like: 'Damn, what's this crazy thing?' We're not breaking up, but it's going badly [...] Since the memory is shared, the memory is linked, even now."*

A second surprising fact that I was able to note during this analysis concerns bad memories. A festival is so dense and rich in content that, in this context, something that went wrong at one point is not going to condemn the opinion that festival-goers will have about a festival. It is even one of the first things that participants seem happy to recount. These memories experienced with difficulty at the time become funny and light anecdotes that are easy to tell. This is not an isolated phenomenon, all the people interviewed who told me about negative experiences did so with almost a form of happiness. Here are some of their observations: *"When I was little, at R4, the anecdote that I just told you with the guy who wasn't very well. At the time, I was absolutely terrified, I was afraid of this guy. As time went on, I told myself that it was a funny anecdote" - Marius. Mathilde makes a similar remark: "I didn't have an access route. I wasn't next to the barriers, nor to the right, nor towards the left exit, nor towards the back. I know that at the time, I was in the mode of hoping that it would stop quickly, and that it would only last 45 minutes. [...] I talk about it with a smile because everything ended well." This idea will even be theorized by two of the festival-goers who responded to the interview. Firstly by Axelle: "Something big happens to you in the evening, at a festival for example, and afterwards, just when you tell it once, twice, three times, after a while, it's over. And suddenly, it just turns into a good story, something that ends well. [...] I think that good memories take over from bad ones and bad ones can also be transformed."*

Wathek adds to this analysis by going so far as to express that, for his part, the negative moments end up almost no longer existing: *"I have the impression that, in fact, the general feeling of the concert's emotion becomes the main and absolute feeling afterwards. Basically, to be more specific, for example, I would say that the festivals I really liked, the concerts I really liked, it's a general feeling, let's say. 80% good moments, 20% perhaps a little boring. Over time, I end up eliminating these boring moments. I only end up keeping these moments where I feel alive, these big adrenaline rushes. Ultimately, that's what sticks."*

This analysis gives us a precise idea of how festival memories evolve for Generation Z. Our analyses confirm that a memory is not anchored and continues to evolve even long after its creation. To complete the memorization process, we still need to understand how these memories are narrated and recalled to festival-goers. Let's look at how these stories are told.

2. Recitation of remembrance

Here, we will therefore examine how memories evolve over time and through their retelling. This will help us understand the connection between festival-goers and the various experiences they have had in this context. First, it is interesting to know who the respondents shared their festival memories with.

We note that 95.24% of them discussed them with the people who accompanied them to these events.

We also note that 100% of them have already discussed them with friends who did not attend.

Finally, 57.14% mentioned that they usually discuss them with their family once they return home.

It's now important to focus on the reasons why the people we interviewed talk and recount their experiences so extensively. Why do festivals necessarily involve storytelling? What are

the motivations for doing so? This is what we'll explore now. I've been able to identify five reasons for this.

The first and most important is simply the pleasure of talking about it again with the people who accompanied us. We saw earlier that festivals are absolutely ideal settings for bringing groups of friends or different relationships closer together. It's in these moments that the connection between two people can go beyond the usual and become extraordinary. These types of events serve as rituals and annual gatherings for many of the people we interviewed. It is therefore not surprising that talking about it again can bring back this feeling of inclusion, unity and well-being within a group. *Clémentine* expresses this idea of ritual well: *"We even talk about it very regularly, given that, well, for some festivals, it's a bit of a ritual every year, so inevitably, we remember memories from previous years."* This concept that bringing back these memories is an ingrained habit is also illustrated by *Mathilde*: *"It's a bit like when you have a really good evening, you leave the evening six times in a row, even though you've already experienced it and everyone has experienced the same thing. Everyone knows the evening by heart after a while. I know that I talked about it a lot, for example with my boyfriend."* Finally, within a group of friends or a friendship, talking about memories where everything was going well, where, very often, relationships appeared in their best light, has a comforting effect. This is also what *Anaïs* says: *"We often talk about it among friends, and it's funny because it's a bit like a gentle subject, a bit comforting. A bit... you know that moment when you look at your friends with stars in your eyes! Well, it's also kind of powerful things that I think we share."*

The second reason simply concerns bringing them up naturally in the context of a conversation. Festival experiences can act as icebreakers and bring people together. When we meet someone, we tend to look for common ground. Similar experiences in the context of powerful and emotionally charged events like festivals can be excellent anchors. This also demonstrates the importance that everyone places on these events. This idea of an icebreaker topic is further developed by *Lola*: *"They're conversation starters. For example, 'Oh, have you been to that festival?' 'No, but it was really good.' 'You see, there was such and such a person.' 'It was well organized.' 'No, it wasn't well managed.' 'There was a good sound system.' Anyway. These are really conversation topics that connect me with people."* Talking about festivals allows you to start a conversation with people you've just met. *Léane* told me about a similar experience: *"We saw someone who was also coming back from this festival disappointed, we didn't know him at all, he lives in Roubaix by the way [...] and he too was coming back disappointed so we talked about it together."* *Anaïs* will come to complete these observations by telling us that she even tends to associate people with the festivals that would suit them best: *"of course, I don't say 'Hello, my name is Anaïs, I did such and such a festival,' but it's something that I will quickly address because in fact, I love sharing these kinds of experiences with the people I like. And so, quite quickly, in discussions, it can be meeting someone and saying 'But actually, this person is really the vibe of this festival.'"*

Another reason for wanting to share these festival experiences is simply wanting to share them with loved ones. When you love an experience, you often want to share it with the people you love. This is also the case for music festivals. This is the case, for example, for *Lina*: *"I think I talked about it to all my close friends, especially my best friend. I really*

wanted us to go to one. So I explained it to her a little bit, and she told me if there were any artists I liked, no problem." In these circumstances, the important thing isn't so much to talk about it with festival regulars but also with people you want to bring along and convert to the scene: "But then, if I can go with people who have never been, I like to sell the project too." - Lola.

Another reason that came up several times was the pride of having participated in such an important event. The biggest music festivals in France are, without a doubt, the events that bring together the most people. Participating in one of them often ensures being at the nerve center of music and entertainment for a given time. Moreover, at a festival, seeing artists perform live can also be a source of social recognition and pride depending on the hype surrounding them and their notoriety. This idea is developed by several of the respondents, among them Leila: "I like to say what I saw, because there are lots of artists who are well-known, so it's also a bit of a way of proving myself. In fashion, I saw this person, that person and everything. So, to make people want to go a little bit." She is not the only one to have explicitly mentioned this notion. We also find Lucas: "There was the pride of having experienced these moments. The fact of having wanted, out of pride, to show them what I had experienced. And for me, it made me feel good at the same time to revisit the good times. For my ego, I think it's nice when people say, 'Oh yeah, damn, you did some crazy stuff.' It also boosts my ego at the same time."

Finally, the last reason for re-talking about my festival experiences seems to be simply to tell funny stories that happened there: "with people who weren't there, where I tell the funny anecdotes that happened" - Lison, "At that moment, remember, he fell, it's so funny" - Maxence, "We also talk about the moments that were a bit... Funny, embarrassing moments that we had during that time. Sometimes, you try to talk to people, they completely ignore you, and as a result, you feel a bit embarrassed, but it doesn't matter, it makes for anecdotes" - Alex.

All these reasons seem very different, but they all have a common thread. Whether we talk about them to connect with our group of friends, out of pride, to share funny moments, or

when we're trying to imagine ourselves at a festival with a friend, all these moments bring us a sense of well-being. Revisiting a festival is never a chore, but a pleasure, and that's why 100% of Generation Z festival-goers do it frequently. Festival memories stay with us and fill us with joy even after they have evolved and through the prism of different perceptions. These events are unanimously recognized as enjoyable and allow us to feel part of the festival-going community. That's why we talk about them in groups. That's why it's one of the first topics we connect on with strangers.

By observing the interview transcripts, we see that absolutely all festival-goers talk about their festival experiences. Personally, I don't see any other event or entertainment that resonates more than festivals. They bring people together, and everyone can understand the emotion conveyed by live music, by being with friends, or by being constantly stimulated. But to complete this section on the memorization process, we must now look at how these memories are triggered and what their recall provokes in festival-goers.

3. Remanence of memory

Beyond just talking, keeping track of these festivals remains one of the best ways to remember them. These traces can take various forms (photos, videos, social media posts, or objects). Aside from memories, these are what remain of the experiences we live. In this analysis, it will be interesting to see which ones are most adopted by Generation Z festival-goers.

First of all, the most cited remain photos and videos taken on the spot. 95.24% of respondents said they took them during their festival. These images are then preserved in various ways. While most individuals report frequently consciously revisiting these memories, Whether by regularly consulting their gallery, by keeping these traces on apps that send them notifications every year so they can revisit them: *"with the Snapchat app, you can have memories, that is to say, what happened a year ago, to the day, they will put it in a tab where, precisely, you can review the photos and videos you took a year ago,"* - Riad, or by bringing them out during discussions with loved ones like Antoine: *"when I see groups of friends or my family, for example, and they ask me how it went, I show them photos,"* Generation Z festival-goers particularly appreciate being able to revisit their memories.

Although images are highly valued, I note in this analysis that there is a strong desire on the part of festival-goers of this generation to materialize their memories as much as possible. Even when it comes to photos, several respondents confided that they print them and keep them. This is particularly the case for Quentin: *"Since I don't have a smartphone, I take pictures with my Bigophone, I call it that. I take pictures with it and I print them and I give them to the people I spent time with"* or Axelle who says she keeps each of the most memorable images of her life, carefully stored in an album: *"I'm someone who loves photography, video and everything, so obviously, yes, I have a photo album where there are each of the festivals I've been to, they have their page with the photos."* Finally, and still in the spirit of materializing memory, Léane says she is a fan of scrapbooking: *"I also keep bracelets, parking tickets, etc... to put them in a little notebook. I do scrapbooking, like that, I can print the photos too and it allows me to have a written record not only on the phone."*

But photos and social media aren't the only ways to keep track of the festivals we experience. Objects are also an important source of memorability. And festivals have no shortage of objects. Whether through posters, goodies, eco-cups, wristbands, or personalized clothing, festival-goers seem to want to keep objects related to their experience at all costs. This is also confirmed when analyzing the interview transcripts. More than half of the people interviewed said they kept material souvenirs from the festivals.

However, and above all, I found it interesting during this analysis to note that only one of the people surveyed indicated having ever purchased festival merchandise. This is very low, and it seems to show that Generation Z is not receptive to this type of content. Even for someone like *Élisa*, who usually says, *"I keep everything, anything that's keepable,"* buying this merchandise doesn't seem to be an option for her: *"I don't necessarily buy T-shirts, things like that, bags, because I'm a rat. Tickets are already expensive enough, so I'm not necessarily going to buy even more."*

Wristbands are particularly popular. These are artifacts distributed at the festival entrance so that you don't have to check your tickets at each entrance and exit. These items are the first thing you get when you enter a festival and are unique to each edition. Having them on your wrist signifies that you are part of the festival-going community. It acts a bit like a symbol of group belonging. These collector goodies are often carefully cut out and kept after the festival. *Mathilde* explains: *"I know that when there are bracelets that haven't been lost along the way, I keep them every time. I have a hard time cutting them off every time. But since there are so many bacteria, I take them off."* These festival bracelets can be collected and given special storage: *"The first thing that comes to mind is often the bracelets they put on you. Imagine, I have a little jar in my room at my parents' house and everything, and remember that it's a jar that originally just held my birth bracelet."* - *Anaïs*.

Another recurring theme is cups. At festivals, people are thirsty, and refreshment stands are set up. At most festivals with a small budget, these cups take the form of personalized eco-cups. Thus, these become truly symbolic of the festival and its edition. They represent the good times spent, the artistic direction of the event and can also have information such as the line-up of the day or the location, which makes them real collector's gold mines for lovers of memorial artifacts. *Adrien* tells us here about his passion for these objects: *"I love eco-cups. Eco-cups, 50¢ plastic pints. If there are any at a festival, I leave with them. Right there, under my nose, there is one from Paradis Artificiels, a festival I had in Lille. This afternoon, I drank from an eco-cup from R4, it's a rock festival, the same, in the countryside. I have several from the Ahuri Festival, every festival, if there are eco-cups, I leave with them."* Indeed, these glasses, in addition to having a practical effect also have a strong emotional significance. I was surprised to see that many festival-goers really got attached to them. This is what emerged from several interviews, for example, *Élisa* confided: *"The (festival) cup, sometimes, when it's not at the top of the pile of cups, I'm a bit of a child, so I take that one because I want to, because it's my cup. I like it and I had it at the festival."* We find a very similar testimony from *Lison*: *"on the other hand, the cup, if I'm hesitating between different cups, I'll take that one."* What's interesting about eco-cups is that they are often included in the rotation of glasses used at home by Generation Z. Festival-goers are therefore led to see them often and to think back to the event: *"when I'm out at a party with friends, I need more*

glasses [...] I take out the festival glasses. I look at the glass and it brings back lots of memories." - Marius. This quote provides the perfect transition to complete this point.

Certainly, traces such as photos or objects allow festival-goers of this generation to recall their memories. Now, the important thing is to know what emotion the afterglow of these memories will provoke.

During our interviews, I asked my interviewees directly what emotions they felt when festival memories were rekindled. Although a few people expressed lingering regrets about events that took place in this context: *"I saw such and such an artist, now I like them a little less, or I like this one a little more, I regret not having gone to see that"* - Leila, *"I would have liked to have enjoyed it more. I would have liked to come, maybe a little earlier, to do something else. To be able to eat, because I know I told myself, I'm not going to spend money"* - Lina. There are three emotions whose lexical fields particularly recur.

The first is nostalgia. This word was used directly by a lot of festival-goers interviewed. Even if for some, it can relate somewhat to a feeling of sadness, most speak of a positive nostalgia. A nostalgia that is accompanied by a comforting feeling of having experienced something powerful. Marius expresses it very well in his testimony: *"I can't feel sad thinking about it, even if I could feel sad about not being able to be there anymore, that kind of thing. There is a little bit of nostalgia, but it's nothing too negative. It's essentially just positivity."* But he's not the only one to put words to this sweet nostalgia: *"for me, talking about it again would be mostly nostalgia. It won't be emotions, whether negative or positive. It will just be nostalgia. Especially since I had a good time, it will be positive nostalgia, not negative."* - Maxence. Finally, I think Alex's quote perfectly expresses this idea and feeling: *"It's not just nostalgia. We often associate nostalgia with sadness, but not at all. I associate it with a good time. And it's a good time that can be repeated, and nostalgia is a bit perpetual, because we always think it was good yesterday, but it can be just as good today. We have to keep feeding it."*

The second emotion that comes up in particular is missing something. This is perhaps directly impacted by the nostalgia felt when immersing ourselves in festival memories. Ultimately, more than half of the festival-goers used the word missing when asked how they felt when immersing themselves in their memories. I asked Riad about what he felt when thinking about festivals, and here is his response: *"Emotions, and good ones. Good things are that I want to go back."* He's not the only one, Pauline also expresses this desire when her memories are recalled: *"I think about it, so I remember moments, and yes, it definitely makes me want to go back."* Antoine uses roughly the same terms here: *"It went so well, there were so many problems that it really makes you want to go back."* Going to a festival and remembering it very often gives you the desire to accumulate other festival experiences: *"this 'I'm going to relive that' side. It's an accumulated experience that makes you want to acquire others."* - Wathek

But nostalgia and missing things would not be possible or even conceivable if these experiences had not gone well. Thus, the necessary condition for a festival-goer to want to return to a festival is indeed that they feel happy at the evocation and resurgence of their memories. The lexical field of joy is the one that was most observed among my respondents. Lucas is not the one who would be in contradiction, the simple fact of discussing festivals

seems to greatly animate him: "Now, when I talk to them, it makes me happy to remember this moment that was really cool." For Lison too, the predominant feeling is joy: "It's the joy of having had a good time."

Thus, when festival-goers rediscover the memories they have of festivals, they mostly feel joy, a desire to return, or positive nostalgia. This is surely why so many members of Generation Z place such importance on keeping images or objects from their experiences. This is why so many of them consciously decide to delve into their memories, like *Mathilde*: "I take quite a few small photos, even if the photos are really poorly framed. So, when I look back at the photos, I think it was truly incredible."

But now that we know how festival memories are created, perceived, recounted, and remembered for young people of this generation, there is one more point to consider before looking at their impact on engagement. This point concerns socialization.

E. The role of socialization in the sacralization of memories

As we've seen many times before, festivals are social events. As such, it's not surprising to see that they continue to be so even after they're over. Memories and their afterglow will be subject to a social spectrum that will play a role in their evolution. If we want to trace the complete journey they undertake, including their impact on engagement, it's important not to overlook this point.

1. The ritualization of memories in festivals

We saw earlier that festivals are events that are easy to talk about. But for many festival-goers, these are not simply anecdotes. Festivals also have a significant impact on the socialization of fans. Thus, they are the glue and catalyst for many groups of friends. Going to

a festival therefore becomes a ritual where everyone does their best to free themselves and attend. The stories experienced there then become part of the folklore and culture of these groups of friends. Many of the people who responded to my interviews gave similar accounts.

First of all, many testimonies express the idea that the memories linked to these festivals were so evoked between two people who shared this experience that they ended up becoming part of the history of the relationship. They were internalized by both people and they continue to remind each other of them even long afterward. This is roughly what *Lina* expressed to us with emotion: *"Every time, through messages, we remind each other of them. And really, those are incredible moments. To have lived the same experience with someone. I think it's truly beautiful."* This idea of memories cementing a relationship is also echoed by other respondents. They often talk about certain anecdotes with one or more of the friends who accompanied them. These are personal stories that belong to them and that only they can truly understand, although, in *Adrien's* case, he doesn't hesitate to try to include his listeners: *"Often, I talk about it with the person I went with, and if there's someone else in the room who wasn't there, we'll tell them."*

Although these stories can be shared in pairs, they are omnipresent in the culture of a group of friends who regularly go to a festival. These are powerful and memorable experiences that bring everyone together and are often rekindled. This is what *Mathilde* tells us: *"It's a bit like when you have a really good night out, you talk about the night six times in a row, even though you've already experienced it and everyone has experienced the same thing. Everyone knows the night by heart after a while."* For *Alex* and his friends too, remembering the memories created in these contexts seems to be a routine: *"We also talk about the moments a little... Funny, embarrassing moments that we had during that time [...] it makes anecdotes."* These memories are rich and everyone has their own experience. They therefore represent an almost inexhaustible source of new adventures to tell their friends and this is also why they are mentioned so frequently: *"We remember memories, little moments because, even if we were all together, we didn't experience the same way. We weren't always necessarily in the same place each time, so we told each other a little bit and then it always makes good memories [...] I have no bad memories. So each time, it's often to remember the times we spent" - Antoine.* Here too, he implies that he and his friends remember past moments regularly. Finally, *Clémentine* uses roughly the same themes but also adds the term ritual: *"For those with whom I was able to share these evenings, ah yes, totally. We even talk about it very regularly, given that, for some festivals, it's a bit of a ritual every year, so inevitably, we remember memories from previous years." - Clémentine*

It's not just for friendship groups that festivals represent a good way to strengthen ties or share common stories and experiences. Several festival-goers also mentioned their family as part of the same festival community as them. *Antoine*, speaking of a festival taking place in his town, said: *"Here in my village, it's a good time, it's with my family, with my friends. So there I have a bit of a connection. As soon as there's one, if I can go, I go."* Going to a festival or participating in the organization is an excellent way to get closer. This is also the case for *Anaïs* who, as a child, used to go there with her parents: *"I used to go with my parents when I was a child, like jazz or rock festivals, in small villages. These are things we go to regularly because we know that every year it takes place and it creates a festival that exists in the*

area." There's no doubt that these moments spent together helped shape the history of these families and created lasting memories for them that few others have experienced. But wouldn't another ideal way to truly unite a group be to create a festival together? This is what Alex and his family experienced: *"And so, in my small village in Picardy, we started... My family decided to create a festival together with friends."* We therefore see in this analysis that festivals are ideal events to share in order to bring groups together, and that the socialization that occurs around these events greatly contributes to their impact and memorability.

When I began to analyze this point, I was truly surprised to see the extent to which a group's participation in one of these events was, for regulars, a true sacred ritual. The term "ritual" is important; it was used by many of the people I interviewed. *Clémentine*, again, used this term: *"It's a bit of a ritual every time with friends, we like going there, it's always a time to get together, to enjoy ourselves, to discover artists. So, it's always nice."* But she's far from the only one. *Adrien* uses it here in the same way: *"Yeah, that's it, so for festivals where there's really this established ritual, it's more of a commitment, even with friends, to get together."*

These festivals have even, through habit and ritualization, become unmissable events every year: *"Festivals have now become, for me, a bit of a meeting place" - Quentin.* These events are of capital importance and no one wants to miss them, even if it means having to travel or return to the city of origin on purpose: *"The Minuit Avant la Nuit in Amiens is the same, we know that it falls every year in June and every year with friends from Amiens, we go there. And even those who left Amiens come back to our little town on purpose to see it. You go once and you'll go back next year because you have a great time and you have to make the most of it" - Adrien, "Because it also allows you to meet up with friends who are not necessarily in Amiens because, inevitably, everyone is studying in different cities, so we don't necessarily have the opportunity during the year to see each other regularly. And sometimes, festivals like these allow you to reserve a date where you can simply enjoy getting together, relive moments, and create new memories together." - Clémentine*

For people who have ritualized going to certain festivals, the very content of the latter becomes almost secondary, anecdotal. What they are looking for when they go is not so much to see artists they admire or to be amazed by the installations or the light shows. No, what they expect is to meet up with their friends and the good times they spend there every year. The rendezvous is no longer only with the festival, but with the general atmosphere of the place and the moment. This is what *Anaïs* notes with amusement: *"Minuit Avant la Nuit above all because it is in my hometown of Amiens. And there, for once, we know that we will find our friends who live there every year. Sometimes even other people [...] It's funny because at Minuit Avant la Nuit, there are artists that I really like that I was able to see. But here, the first things that come to mind are memories with friends, with people with whom I was able to share these concerts and this festival."* Of course, the fact that she goes there primarily to meet up with these friends doesn't stop her from wanting to include more and more of the people she cherishes year after year: *"And then, each year, more and more friends came."* Thus, rituals are concepts that can be shared, explained, and spread. As the saying goes, *"the more the merrier."* This is also what Generation Z festival-goers think.

Thus, we see with this analysis that memories are greatly reinforced by ritualization. Festival moments will become etched in stone by being recounted and relived by the people around us. These memories will last from year to year because each member takes the same pleasure in recalling them to others. More than just lasting, this memory will be enriched over the years because, for the group, the festival now represents an unmissable event.

2. Emotional attachment and sense of community

This point will serve as a bridge to the impact of festival memory on attendee engagement. Socialization doesn't just cement groups. When coupled with strong and positive memories, it can also create a powerful emotional attachment to an event or foster a considerable sense of community.

During this analysis, I realized that 80.95% of respondents said they felt an emotional connection and deep attachment to at least one festival. Often, this will be to the small local festival in their region or to their "best" festival experience. Several factors can contribute to this feeling.

First, this deep emotional connection can be created by feeling part of the festival community. Some experiences are so successful at integrating attendees that they feel like they are fully part of it. This is particularly true for many festivals. With this in mind, *Lola* declared: *"I feel attached to these festivals. Completely. I don't know if that's really it, but I feel like there's a sense of belonging. From the moment you go to a festival, that's it, you're part of the people who've been there, so you can talk about it, you know what to expect, etc. So, yes, there's a sense of belonging."* But she's not the only one who expresses this feeling. *Alex*, more implicitly, tells me about the functioning of the Zik en Brousse festival community: *"I'm involved from the first setup to when everything is taken down, and so you really feel a connection. In fact, the festival doesn't really start when the first musician arrives, it starts long before that, it starts when we plant [...] the first stick to make the first bar, that's where it starts, that's where everyone comes together to help. People I didn't know well, people 20 years older than me, and I found myself talking to them until 11 p.m., midnight, 1 a.m., even though we didn't make much progress that day in terms of building. But I discovered people."* Even if it's not clearly stated, here, we understand the community spirit that reigns in this festival and that seems so appreciated. Some festivals have understood the importance of cultivating this community culture. They can put in place different measures to help or encourage the creation of the latter. It's one of these ideas that seems to have struck *Leila*: *"With my best friend, as we did two years in a row. We said to each other every year we're going to go there, we saw elderly people with lots of patches with all the years. We were like, this is going to be us later because we love the music."*

This emotional connection can also arise from the pride we feel in having gone to a festival. These are engaging events that speak to the greatest number of people. When we have already been there, it is normal for our ego to be boosted when we hear someone talk about it. This is particularly what *Léane* expresses when we ask her if she still has an attachment to the Ardentes festival: *"Obviously a little bit because we experienced it, so since human beings are a little selfish, it's as if the Ardentes belong to me in a way."* She is far from being the only

one to feel this type of feeling. *Élisa* also admits to feeling a little ego when talking about her favorite festival: *"For example, I saw posters for Rock en Seine [...] I went there last year. And when people talk about it even though they haven't been there [...] I don't say it of course, I don't have enough ego, but deep down, I'm like, 'I've been there, I know this festival.'"* Beyond the pride of having been to a festival, some also express it regarding the fact of having gone to one edition rather than another: *"If I've experienced the thing before, I have a bit of this privileged thing with the festival, where I tell myself that people are going to have an experience, but I have the impression that mine, since it was done before, is the festival when it was in the old style, I don't know how to explain, but at its prime. I always have the impression of having experienced things at their prime."* - *Mathilde*. This feeling of pride came up several times during my analyses. It has already been described as a trigger for festival memories and one of the motivations for sharing these stories with loved ones. This confirms that participating in a festival is truly a sign of personal accomplishment and that it can greatly positively impact the mood of those who experience it in these contexts.

Another reason that can justify the development of love or attachment to a festival has been mentioned. This is the fact of having grown or evolved with it. Having experienced a festival in its early days and watching it grow from year to year seems to be able to foster a very strong emotional connection with it. *Anaïs* had this experience with one of her favorite festivals: *"Compared to the habit of returning to certain festivals, it's funny because, for example, Minuit Avant la Nuit, the first time I went, it was really quite small. There was a stage, it's striking because with regard to the place, from year to year, it grows a little, so now there are two stages, well even three stages. It evolves too. It evolves and at the same time it's nice."* We understand that she finds that seeing the evolution of a place or an event each year pleases her greatly. But this link between this phenomenon and attachment will be explicitly explained by *Antoine*: *"I feel quite an attachment to the Candas festival because I went there three times in a row. It's a very young festival that has grown a little with us, the people of the village. It evolves more and more, we add a hundred people each year. So it's really nice."* For festival-goers, following the evolution is already pleasant. For someone who participates in the creation of the event as a volunteer, this feeling seems even more intense. *Alex* expresses it very well: *"The links I have with Zik en Brousse are a bit personal. They are things we all created together. It's like having a baby, we want to take care of it, we want it to be beautiful."*

Finally, *Quentin* also explained that he feels a strong connection to festivals because they have been the scene of great change for him: *"They're places where there's a real connection. There are many memories; I've also grown a lot during those moments."*

Thus, attachment to festivals is a recurring phenomenon that impacts almost all Generation Z festival-goers. This attachment and the community spirit that often results from it represent the apotheosis of what festivals seek to offer attendees. They are created when memories align with what festival-goers are looking for when they attend this type of event.

We have now finished analyzing everything that revolves around the creation and evolution of festival memories. We have seen how they can be perceived as memorable, how the retelling of these memories can change them, and the role that socialization can play in this process. It

is now time to complete the journey we've undertaken and tackle the final part. This concerns the consequences that memories and their evolution can have on the commitment of festival-goers after the event.

F. Post-event consequences

The consequences that memories will have on an attendee after a festival are numerous. In an event setting, it is important to analyze them in order to understand how engagement in all its forms can be triggered and encouraged. This is also the final destination of the path we have undertaken to trace regarding festival memories. We are now ready to begin analyzing this final part.

1. Different forms of engagement

First, we will analyze the different types of engagement found among the festival-goers surveyed. This will help us create a comprehensive spectrum of what can be observed in an attendee afterward.

I was surprised to find that the overwhelming majority of festival-goers who have developed an attachment to a festival automatically express some form of engagement with it. This is reflected in the fact that they inquire about the program, the date, or the connection each year, and constantly have the desire to return. Some, like *Lina*, describe being ready to go even if they don't know any of the artists present: *"The following year, I wanted to go straight away, even though there wasn't anyone I was really a fan of."* This is also what *Marius* expresses when he talks about the Zik en Brousse festival. He says he wouldn't even dwell on important organizational details: *"If I had to go, if it were to take place, I wouldn't bother looking at the program."* Thus, the desire to go to a festival you're attached to is permanent, and checking the information each year becomes a ritual: *"By wanting to go back, and if I want to look at what's happening at the festival, I'll look at the date, I'll look at the program, I'll ask myself, 'Hey, am I still available on that date and everything else?'"* - *Lison*

Involvement with a music festival is expressed through recommendations. Absolutely everyone we interviewed mentioned having already recommended people to go to a festival they particularly enjoyed. These recommendations can be made for two distinct reasons. The first is to get people to come with them and accompany them during the event. This is the case for 80.95% of respondents. As seen previously, festivals are also a social process and, therefore, it is not surprising to see festival-goers wanting to bring their loved ones with them: *"I sometimes invite people, typically to R4, because we often go in groups"* - *Marius*. But recommending a festival can also be a way to invite people to be interested in it so that you can go with them when you don't necessarily want to go alone: *"Recommend and especially if I want to go somewhere, to try to get them to come with me"* - *Axelle*. When we recommend, it's often to try to go there too: *"if it's a time when I'm available and they're up for it, let's go together"* - *Mathilde*, *"I sold it a bit in fashion, I just explained that I had a good time there and that if they wanted to go, they should go, because in reality, it's not bad and even if it's a time when I'm available and they're up for it, let's go together."* - *Maxence*.

But when we recommend a festival, it's not just to encourage people to go with us. It can also very well be simply because we know that our interlocutors will appreciate the time spent there. So sometimes, we recommend without necessarily having the desire or availability to go ourselves. This is what 90.48% of the interviewees mention: *"I send a lot of publications of events, festivals that take place in places where my friends live, where I don't necessarily live, telling them, go there, it seems to be great."* - Pauline, *"Look, it exists and I've already been there. It was great, if you're interested, go for it."* - Lison. In this case, it's not criteria such as the festival attendance habits of the person in front of us that motivates us. We can simply be happy and enjoy recommending and sharing experiences related to topics we're passionate about: *"Even people who haven't been to many festivals or who have, I love recommending a festival I enjoyed. It happens to me very, very, very often, honestly."* - Lola

But another form of engagement is promoting the festival on social media. Generation Z has constantly grown up with the presence of these networks. It's therefore not surprising to see that most information circulates on these channels. When you're truly attached to a festival and have very good memories of it, you can sometimes be happy to talk about it again with strangers or to immerse yourself in these memories. Léane explains that after a successful festival, she was happy to share about it and answer questions from internet users who were hesitant to attend: *"On Twitter, when I was there a lot at the time, there were people who asked how it went, and I interacted a lot with people at that time. Each time, I always made a little message saying, 'You have to do it, it was great, it's really worth it.'"* She's not the only one to have shared her social media presence with us about her participation in a festival. Lucas also tells us this: *"I had tweeted positively about the Ardentes, so it's a kind of social media promotion too."* Social media engagement can also involve joining an online community about a festival. This exists in the form of forums, Facebook groups, or even private channels bringing together a large number of participants. However, during this analysis, I was able to observe that no member of Generation Z clearly stated that they were part of one of their virtual communities. The only thing that could be related to this is rather the fact of having followed festival Instagram or TikTok accounts, but in most cases, this seems to be more with a view to following the information, the line-up or to see the photos posted after the event in order to see if we appear there.

But getting involved in a festival isn't just something you do after the fact. When you participate in these types of events, there are endless ways to help co-create the atmosphere or overall spirit of the event. For example, starting chants in the crowd, organizing pogos, or even taking the time to help other festival-goers are all excellent ways to fully commit to the festival. This is what Marius did in the story we saw earlier, where he told us about going up to a small open stage at R4 and starting a jam session with his friends in front of attentive spectators. These are the actions that Antoine explains he does when he feels happy and well-supported at a festival: *"creating pogos, doing things, singing, it's because I'm having a great time, because I'm with artists I like, because I have good friends."* For some people, these types of rituals not only help bring the festival to life but also drastically enhance the experience: *"It also involves a physical outburst, dancing to certain styles, pogoing, or things like that. You really go there to fully enjoy yourself, to externalize your energy, frustration,*

stress, and that kind of thing, and especially to share it with other people. It enhances the experience tenfold." - Wathek.

Finally, the last type of engagement we will discuss often begins before the event and resembles more of a social and cultural adventure than specific actions. It involves participating in the co-creation and organization of the event by joining volunteer teams. Among those surveyed, 38.1% explained that they had already participated voluntarily in this type of exercise. Some, like *Wathek*, explain that they took part in the celebration by playing as an artist: *"It's true that when you're on stage, it's another vision to see people who are having a good time, who are happy to spend this moment, from something that we do, it's particularly stimulating."* Others, like *Alex*, are part of a group that created a festival: *"we created Zik en Brousse where I was a volunteer for 4 years."* But to join these volunteer teams, there's no need to know the organizers in advance. You just have to want to do it and be open to new experiences. In addition to bringing great satisfaction, it allows you to evolve on a human level. This is what is explained very well by *Anaïs* : *"Being a volunteer, I do it, it's with my heart. And it's true that it's funny because you can have this discussion with people who are a million miles away, thinking, 'But I never volunteer, you don't get paid and all that, what do you get out of it?' And in fact, it brings so much."* These different forms of engagement are only possible when a festival has left very good memories for these participants. In these cases, engagement is no longer an energy-consuming or burdensome process; it becomes a true guarantee of happiness and satisfaction. Participating in one way or another in the co-creation of an event that is important to us is an exchange where everyone comes out a winner.

2. The role of memories in activating commitment

But now that we've been able to draw up a complete picture of the forms of engagement that Generation Z can demonstrate, we still need to analyze how memories can play a role in activating them.

As for loyalty and the desire to return to a festival, it's important to have retained good experiences from the festival. When this is the case and the memories are memorable, it's not uncommon to observe an almost instinctive loyalty. *Antoine* expresses this through various quotes: *"It remains such a good memory that I think that over the years, we'll go to the same festival again this year [...] these are such good memories and good times that I can't wait to go back, in fact, I can't wait to do it again. [...] My memories don't deteriorate. That's precisely what makes me want to go. In fact, since I loved all these festivals so much, it makes me want to go back in subsequent years."* It's not the only one, *Audrey* clearly states that immersing herself in these memories provokes this desire: *"It made me want to go back."* It's roughly the same story for *Lina*: *"With what I do, in reality, it makes me really want to go back."* In conclusion: *"Obviously, when you have a good memory of a festival, it makes you want to go back."* - *Clémentine*. Thus, thanks to this analysis, we understand that, thanks to the memories they generate, festivals can trigger a craving in their participants. This engagement is triggered each time festival-goers talk about the festival, revisit traces of it, or simply take the time to reminisce about past moments.

There are many other forms of engagement that are, very often, triggered by memory. We see that having good memories of a festival is the prerequisite for recommendations. If we don't have a positive festival memory of an event, we won't recommend it again. This connection between memories and recommendations is clearly established by *Adrien*: *"I want it to be a great time. If I bring my friends, it's to have a great time with them. So I recommend things to my friends so we all have the same fabulous memory because I know they'll have a better night if we go than if they didn't."* *Lola* also talks about the fact that her perception of a festival and its surroundings will push her to talk about it to as many people as possible: *"Now, I'm going to talk about it to everyone. Of course, if the venue, the location, or the context lends itself to it."* The actions we decide to take during a festival are also greatly impacted by our memories. If we've already done something and enjoyed it, then we're more likely to do it again. This idea is illustrated by a quote from *Axelle*: *"if at some point you start dancing and you see everyone around, you want to do it again."* For *Maxence*, what will make him want to give energy to a festival is that he has had the feeling up until then that the festival also gives him energy: *"if I feel that the festival gives me the energy to want to do it, well, will I do it? There won't be anything else that will... It's the festival that must push me to do that."* Thus, it is the memories of our past actions that condition our desire to reproduce certain gestures.

But the strong point of festival involvement is still being able to sign up as a volunteer. These are the rare events that offer this kind of opportunity. This is for a simple reason, as mentioned previously: festival-goers are happy to get involved. For other types of events, this initiative would be futile because they wouldn't be unifying enough. But for the music and festival community, it's not only an opportunity but also a necessity, without which, nothing would be possible. Even if some people cite financial motivations, particularly for signing up as volunteers for the biggest festivals that sometimes offer a free day in exchange for a day of work: *"Working for free to end up attending a festival for free. All students, of course, want that. It's worth it."* - *Léane*, *"The volunteer thing where you work one evening and then you get the VIP pass for the three days, I thought it was a great compromise. You're not paid, but at the same time you have the pass, and it almost costs less to work than what you would have paid. I thought it was a great initiative."* - *Leila*. Most of the motivations are linked to the perception of the volunteer adventure and the festival.

We will chronologically trace how memories and perceptions impact volunteer involvement at festivals. First of all, one of the necessary conditions is to join the festival. This can be done through different prisms. First, if the festival's values appeal to us or resonate with us: *"Being united with a community, in fact. You go to this festival because you are part of a very specific community, and you support its commitments and values."* - *Audrey*. This idea of value is echoed by several of the interviewees. *Anaïs* puts it quite well when I ask her what might make her want to get involved with an event: *"What the festival is going to offer, what values it wants to convey [...] That's it. Sharing, open-mindedness, the whole human aspect I was talking about earlier, that's going to be very important to me."* *Riad* and *Mathilde* share roughly the same views; for them, values are essential aspects that cement their desire to support the organization of a festival: *"Let the festival convince me first. If I'm completely*

convinced by the festival and fully adhere to its values." - Riad, "I would say that the festival is aligned with my values." - Mathilde

Recognizing oneself in a festival can also come from a strong local connection. For people who grew up in cities where a festival takes place regularly, it may seem natural to get involved at one point or another, especially when, like *Clémentine* and *Antoine*, you grew up participating in one. Here is their response when asked what might make them want to get involved in a festival: *"It's if I'm really passionate about this festival. For example, the small festival, the one in Candas, it's because it's in my village, most of the people who organize it are people I know. So, voluntarily, I would be happy to participate. Whether it's the organization, to set up the stage, to serve there, to prepare, to clean up. On my own, there, I would be happy to participate. Then, for other types of festivals, really, it has to be close to my heart" - Antoine, "The fact that it's really at home, it's our village. It might make you want to promote yourself on social media, with flyers, whatever. So I would say, the fact that it's small, local" - Clémentine*

The personal experience and memories we gain from participating in a festival can greatly influence us to join as a volunteer. For many, it's a way to give back what we've been given. This is what *Lison* explains: *"More so that people have a good time too. A little bit to give back what I was able to have. And then to experience it from the other side too. A little bit to see what it's like backstage."* This motivation is also explored in *Axelle's* responses: *"If I had experienced real emotions, I would really want everyone to experience that, so I would want to participate in that."* Giving back what a festival has given us in the past. This concept is used by several of the respondents. For *Pauline*, it would also be necessary for the experience that connects her to the festival to be strong. For her, this type of commitment comes above all from loyalty and the fact of having participated in numerous editions. When asked what would motivate her to volunteer, she replied: *"It would be being very loyal to a single festival, going to every edition and really feeling a family connection, a real sense of belonging that would encourage me to do more, to become a volunteer."*

The final point that can make us join a festival is when we appreciate its approach from a structural or organizational point of view. Several of the people we interviewed spoke to us about this: *"I know there's one thing that can personally stand out, it's when the festival's community manager really talks to us as if we were his friends. It's a kind of closeness between us. I say to myself, 'OK,' so we want to do some communication about this festival." - Lola.* Another aspect inherent to these events that can be very unifying is the programming: *"I think if I really like the line-up, it would make me want to be there well beforehand, so for example, to volunteer." - Lina.* *Lucas* also brings up this point, directly linked to the artists: *"I really like rap in general, but I don't have one or two favorite rappers. It changes often. I think if I were more of a fan of one or two rappers in particular, I might have more of a desire to be part of the community."* This point is less related to memories and attachments than directly to the perception and image one has of a festival through its operations or program.

However, once you join a festival through one of these processes, you still have to take the plunge and register to fully commit and join the festival's volunteers. Most of the time, this step is taken thanks to a recommendation or someone you already know on the team. This is

the motivation that *Élisa* told me during the interview: *"What made me want to do it was a friend who said to me: 'Yeah, I've already done it. It's so cool. The people are so cool. You party. You go to the concerts you want.' So, that's what made me want to do it."* She's not the only one to emphasize the importance of knowing someone before getting started. When we asked *Marius* what reasons might push him to get involved, he replied: *"I would have said just knowing someone who's participating. Volunteering with someone at the festival is a great experience. Volunteering is much more fun with someone else [...] So, I think that's what it's all about, knowing someone or participating with someone to do something."*

Knowing someone who is already part of the volunteer team is a good thing. But what people who get involved are looking for is to be part of a real community. This community spirit crystallizes the investment and the perception that one will come away with from a volunteer experience. Its importance is highlighted through various testimonies like that of *Audrey*: *"Even being reunited with a community, in fact. You go to this festival, it's because you are part of a very specific community."* This community and social aspect is directly cited by *Élisa*. When asked what drives her to get involved, she immediately answers: *"The human experience, I think."* For *Quentin*, the community is of paramount importance in his motivations: *"For me, it's the fact of building something. And seeing that we built it together, being part of a group of people who built something together. And to see that another group of people, the spectators, the festival-goers, enjoy what we've done. That's an immense pleasure to see the joy we can bring as a group."* These memories of moments experienced in community are the cement of what will later become a ritual. We try to memorize as many social interactions in these settings as possible because they are particularly enjoyable. We seek them out and thrive on them.

But, when the volunteer adventure ends, beyond the memories we take away from the festival or the group, we like to remember that we were useful and that we ourselves participated in creating and embellishing the memory of the festival-goers who took part in the event. Feeling that we are truly involved in the co-creation of a festival and not simply a tool we use greatly contributes to our well-being. The importance of this concept is emphasized by many of the Generation Z festival-goers we interviewed. In *Élisa*, we particularly feel this desire to bring to life the festival for which she is committed: *"Adding my touch [...] being useful. And seeing people's reactions. Bringing something crazy to life. [...] What works for people, amplifying it, working on it even more. Taking ideas from here and there to really make it go well. That's what makes me want to."* In *Mathilde* too, we feel the desire to be able to fully invest in this type of project: *"I think it would be to be able to add my own little touch to the structure. For example, I know that for large-scale events we're not going to choose the color of the garlands, that's not the point. But to be able to share my point of view: 'Me, I would have preferred to put a certain artist at this time etc...' To really be able to have a place as someone who has actively participated, even if I'm not the person who has done the most festivals. Being able to say: 'Well, listen, I have an opinion that can be taken into account, it could be interesting...' So I would say that. It would be to be able to have a part in the festival."* Ultimately, who wouldn't want to feel useful and listened to? Even more so when you get involved in a project as a volunteer.

By conducting this analysis, I realized that no one was opposed to the idea of volunteering to organize a festival. Even if motivations vary, what doesn't change is the desire to spend quality, memorable moments with people you care about. Whether you're a festival-goer or volunteering, ultimately, the only thing that matters is leaving with a head full of memories. We can actually talk about a virtuous circle here. People who have already participated in this type of experience speak only positively about it. Most indicated they would do it again, while others said it was a project and that they would do it again without hesitation when they had more time.

But, as mentioned previously, only 38.1% of the people we surveyed had already participated in volunteer experiences. And, similarly, not all festival-goers expressed feeling sufficiently loyal, attached, or connected to all the festivals they had already attended to return each year, despite a present desire and good memories of previous experiences. In this last point, we will explore what the limits of post-festival engagement are.

3. Barriers to engagement and loyalty

Although engagement was extensively observed and analyzed throughout this study, we must also consider its limitations. Indeed, while everyone enjoys getting involved, how can we explain that not all Generation Z festival-goers necessarily post on social media? How can we explain that some people have never had any experience volunteering at festivals? Finally, how can we explain that, despite all the good memories they have, some festival-goers are not loyal to the festivals they attend? Although the benefits are numerous and well-documented, we must also recognize that barriers to engagement do exist.

To better understand these, I asked Generation Z festival-goers what might motivate them to become loyal or what prevents them from becoming volunteers. Several reasons emerge clearly. By analyzing them, we can understand the barriers to engagement for young people of this generation. First of all, and to draw a parallel with the point raised previously concerning what can push festival-goers to get involved as volunteers, we will focus on the reasons given against participating in creation. We emphasized the importance of knowing other people when you want to join a group in the organization. This crucial importance was highlighted by *Marius*: *"Volunteering is much more fun to do it with someone else. Because being a volunteer alone is a bit boring, you know. So, I think that's what it's all about, knowing someone or participating with someone to do something."* Thus, the fear of being alone seems to be a major obstacle for a large number of Generation Z festival-goers. That's not all, the fear of missing out on the event was also mentioned by several people: *"Volunteering, I've often thought about it, but I would be afraid of missing out on the festival, because I would be in a moment of work more than anything else. I've already thought about it but I'm too selfish to take the plunge I think, even if I volunteer in various associations, but not for a festival. This is a moment that I take for myself, so one day maybe I'll take the plunge" - Adrien.* For her part, even if *Lina* thinks that she would be very happy to participate in an event where artists that she particularly appreciate are programmed, she still has some doubts about enjoying it as she would like: *"Afterwards, maybe it wouldn't be the opportunity to see them so close."* Another limitation to commitment concerns larger festivals. Even though *Antoine*

particularly enjoyed his experience as a festival-goer, he doubts his real usefulness as a volunteer at such a major event: *"I don't see myself volunteering, for example, at the huge festival in Brussels, because for me, there's no point. In Brussels, there are a lot of people. It's more of a source of stress than pleasure, rather than giving of myself."*

Now, regarding loyalty and returning to the same festivals every year, the respondents gave some ideas that could encourage them. We will analyze and list them. First of all, the most common reason is the artistic direction of a festival. For half of the respondents, this reason is central to their loyalty. If they feel that a festival is moving away from its identity or what differentiates it from others, they will be reluctant to engage with it and return. According to *Pauline*, the key to engaging them is that there are: *"activities or experiences that can be had, in quotes, only at that festival."* *Léane* picks up on this idea by expressing her dissatisfaction with a festival that she had really enjoyed when she went there: *"I take the example of the Ardentes, which was basically a rap festival, or a bit more R'n'B too. But now, we're starting to highlight other artists, a bit more pop, etc. And I can understand the frustration of the audience, who were really expecting rap and nothing else. So, sticking more to your basic artistic direction."* *Lison* also understands the importance of maintaining a clear direction to avoid losing her loyal festival-goers: *"You can say diversify the style of music [...] But the festival would lose its very essence. For the most loyal festival-goers, I don't think that would work."* Thus, one of the obstacles to engagement or loyalty lies in knowing how to communicate with your audience. You mustn't lose them or stray too far from those who made you known. A festival-goer who no longer identifies with an event will lose all connection and all form of commitment to it.

Another reason that came up a lot of times is poor logistics. As seen throughout this thesis, even negative experiences tend to become funny anecdotes that almost end up bringing back positive emotions when they are recalled. But what festival-goers do not forgive is adequate logistics. This forms the solid and inevitable basis of commitment or attachment to a festival. Participants will remember for a long time a problem with drinking water, food stalls or toilets. Problems like these represent a significant obstacle to commitment: *"Okay, I paid a lot, but it's not a big deal, it was worth it. Water was accessible in many places, it was perfect."* - *Leila*. Organizational problems are also cited by *Antoine*: *"Then, if there were organizational issues, some problems that were brought up, if people see that in the following years, they have been improved, it's the same."* As previously mentioned, *Lucas* also told us that one of his experiences was marred by sound problems, which discouraged him from returning to the festival in question. So, before thinking about anything else, festivals must first take care of their logistics in order to hope to retain attendees.

Another obstacle to engagement is if the festival fails to take care of its communication. Many festival-goers highlighted in their interviews the importance of good communication in their attachment to a festival or event. *Élisa* offers several communication tips that can, according to her, play a role in loyalty: *"You reserve your place with your email address. That being said, they send you emails for the next edition [...] So send emails. It allows you to be informed of new faces, the date, to also remember that this festival is on and that you might need to reserve this slot to return. Then, be active on social media for people who want to subscribe."* We have seen throughout this analysis how important memories are. For *Wathek*,

communication is an excellent way to use them and bring them back to the surface: *"I think social media is very important. So, for the festival to have a personal account, I think that's important. Don't hesitate to regularly post videos of these events, different angles, photos, and things like that that can help complete the memory puzzle. And also create an emotional connection with the person, of course, by reminding them daily, or at least regularly, of their past experiences at the festival."* Quentin also seems to agree on the importance of communication: *"All the communication that comes after, before, and during. It can build loyalty."* In an ultra-connected age and with a generation omnipresent on social media, not knowing how to communicate now represents an almost insurmountable barrier to attracting this segment of the population.

Another aspect that has come up a lot is the festival's programming itself. If it's not popular, some festival-goers may feel immediately disengaged from the event, and even regulars may sometimes be reluctant to return. In some more extreme cases, poorly managed programming can completely turn festival-goers off an event. This is what Léane explains to us: *"You also have to listen to the artists in relation to the setlist. Because many have complained. For example, having included artists who have been accused of sexual assault on their list, there is the public who is not necessarily in favor."* Creating a program is a difficult exercise. You have to juggle between the budget and the desires. It is also necessary to clearly identify the artistic direction of the festival you are organizing and the expectations of our loyal festival-goers. This is what Axelle expresses: *"that they have a real artistic direction, that it is not just a festival that invites this, that, that person, that there is a real choice of artists that justifies why. And that the entire artistic direction is organized in relation to that."* To succeed with a program, you also have to be careful to diversify in order to satisfy several types of people. You must not hesitate to mix genres a little and take risks: *"you can say diversify the style of music. For example, listening to techno for several hours after a while, personally, I get a bit fed up with it."* - Lison.

One of the limitations to loyalty is specific to almost all environments and all forms of entertainment: simply the lack of money for participants. Festivals still have the opportunity to have an impact, however minimal, on this point. Several of the festival-goers interviewed explained that money was one of the factors preventing them from attending as many festivals as possible. However, they also proposed ideas that could help create a sense of resilience in the face of this lack. Riad, for example, puts forward an idea that, in addition to helping lower the cost of festivals, could allow them to anticipate the budget for future years and create a strong sense of community among their participants: *"Perhaps something like tickets but for several years. That is to say, instead of buying one ticket for one year, buy five which, ultimately, would be cheaper but for five years."* Clémentine, for her part, points to a financial effort that was made by a festival in her city. She then goes on to propose an innovative idea, inspired by what she has observed in several bars: *"At Minuit Avant la Nuit, the fact that they offer tickets for 5 euros for one of the two days of the festival is still not insignificant. Because the basic prices, even if there are discounts, are still quite expensive, especially for students [...] It makes it more accessible to more people, especially students. [...] I know that in some bars they do it, so why not, at a festival. If you paid for a ticket that is 30, sometimes even 50 euros, and sometimes even more, why not have a discount on a drink or a meal."* Lola also

suggests an idea that would strengthen the feeling of belonging to a festival: *"They can send an email or something. It still plays on the feeling of belonging, but 'you are one of the people who were there last year. Thank you very much for that. You win 20 euros on the next ticket with this link.' It's a small pass, something that allows you to get a ticket to the next festival for less."* As we can see, while money may be an inevitable obstacle for anyone who wants to create a paid event, festivals nevertheless have the opportunity to reduce its importance. It is therefore up to them to circumvent it with innovative solutions that could even strengthen the sense of community.

One of the limitations of souvenirs would be that they are perishable. If this happens, then the festival drastically reduces its chances of having its audience return. We saw previously that thanks in particular to socialization and collective memory, festival souvenirs were often prolonged for a very long time. To ensure that these are reactivated frequently and that their preservation is not an obstacle, some of the people interviewed proposed their solution. This is particularly the case for *Axelle*: *"I would say that we need to find something that will change, in other words, an added value. Like, the person leaves with their photo. It will be hung at home, every evening, they will see it, they will say to themselves, we really have to go back. Try to ensure that everyone has a truly memorable memory of the festival."* This idea of goodies to remember and build loyalty is also explored by *Maxence*: *"Having an object that you can take home, which is unique to this year's festival. For example, releasing something special, a bit of a collector's item, let's say. So that it's only really available during that festival. That year, there will be that, and after that, it will never be available for sale again (during other editions)."* While the longevity of festival memories is very important, we shouldn't neglect the forgettable nature of souvenirs. Goodies can therefore be an opportunity to reduce this limit.

Finally, some festival-goers believe that the worst thing that could happen to a festival is that its community doesn't feel listened to. If that were the case, loyal customers could end up disappointed and turn away from the event. Several have proposed ideas to overcome this obstacle: *"Conduct surveys on the artists that the majority of people would like to see at the festival. And then, if possible, listen to this survey and invite those artists. It's really something that can make a lasting impression and bring as many people as possible back. Above all, if they see that they were listened to one year and that they had a great time, they go back next year, and then the year after that."* - *Antoine*. This idea of investigation and polling also comes up in *Leila's* testimony: *"There could be more thoughtful things like, I don't know, a survey at the entrance."* Ultimately, what is needed is: *"just listen in general to the public who complains."* - *Léane*. By proceeding in this way, festivals can avoid participants feeling disrespected and being reluctant to return to the event.

Thus, the limits and obstacles that can hinder engagement and loyalty are numerous but not insurmountable. What if, ultimately, the solution wasn't simply to try to provide festival-goers with the best possible memories? At least, that's what *Lina* thinks: *"I think that music lovers want to go when we like it. If something is done qualitatively, we'll definitely want to go back."* So, first, we should try to create the best possible moments for all festival-goers so that they come away with positive emotions: *"Create emotions, I think. Really create emotions, create atmospheres that make people want to come back, that inspire people. And so that people talk about the festival by saying, 'Yeah, it was really something, we really experienced something crazy.'"* - *Pauline*.

I'll conclude this point on the limits to engagement and loyalty by quoting *Quentin*: *"Build loyalty? [...] I don't think that organizers should have that in mind to put on a festival. I think it should come in relation to another goal. It's like, for example, if my goal in life is to be happy. It's the snake biting its own tail. You can't be happy if you have that goal in life. That's what I think. It's a bit of the same idea in the sense that, to build loyalty, if their goal is to build loyalty, there's a little unhealthy side [...] It's one of the steps on the way, but not the final goal [...] I think that's the best way to build loyalty to a festival, is to make it memorable."*

Thus, we come to the end of this journey, which aims to chronologically retrace the path taken by Generation Z's festival memories. Ultimately, if all of the people interviewed felt joy in recounting their experiences, it is above all because these events are linked to so many positive emotions and memories for each of them. Now, we finally have a clear and comprehensive look at this memorization process.

PART 5 – Conclusion

Now that we have finalized this analysis section, it is time to review the knowledge already acquired on the subject of festival souvenirs. In order to carry out this study, I had the opportunity to read and analyze a large number of academic articles. We will now compare the results of my studies with those of other researchers. This discussion section will be divided into 3 distinct parts. First, I will discuss the knowledge that my analyses allow us to validate. Second, I will examine the concepts that my research qualifies. Then, I will analyze the studies that contradict my research and, finally, we will try to discern on which subjects the studies I have carried out are innovative.

A. The articles that my research supports

There is a wealth of research on festival memories. It is therefore natural that the research conducted as part of this study also builds on knowledge already established by other researchers in this field.

Several articles in our literature review mentioned that festivals can truly act as vectors of personal transformation for festival-goers who enjoyed the event. The memories left by these memories continue to accompany participants, and the people we interviewed all noted changes in themselves after a memorable and immersive festival. This identity and emotional impact was also observed by Neuhofer et al. in their article: "Experience design and the dimensions of transformative festival experiences." Thus, many festival-goers go beyond the purely hedonic aspect of these experiences. Festivals can be a trigger for changes in social behavior. During our studies, we observed that these experiences can profoundly impact participants' preferences or certain aspects of their personality (helping them to be less shy, for example). These observations confirm the studies conducted by Robertson et al. in: "Event Design in Outdoor Music Festival Audience Behavior." Thus, transformation seems possible when a festival-goer breaks away from their daily routine, when they find themselves in an alternative setting during an intense sensory and social experience. This confirms what Neuhofer et al. mentioned this time in the article: "Designing experiences in the age of human transformation: An analysis of Burning Man."

But these behavioral transformations are not the only ones observed during my analyses. A large number of festival-goers also reported feeling happy and calm for a long time after the event. Others expressed feeling joyful emotions or positive nostalgia when they recall their festival memories. During a festival, we observe positive emotions, a form of total engagement, or a significant social aspect. I also noticed that many of the people interviewed also mentioned a sense of pride or accomplishment in having attended these types of events, in having participated in co-creation, or finally, in having seen certain artists. Also noted during the analysis, many of them attach an existential value to the event. The model I have just described, as well as the observed consequences on well-being, strongly resemble what Martin Seligman put forward in his model on positive psychology: "Flourish: a visionary new understanding of happiness and well-being." This model is also taken up by Tran et al. in: "From customer value co-creation behavior to customer perceived value." He explains that

participating in co-creation generates a feeling of usefulness, recognition, and satisfaction that reinforces the positive memory. We were also able to observe this phenomenon in our analysis.

Attending a festival means accepting that you experience a variety of emotions throughout the event. This emotional complexity was strongly observed during the interviews I conducted. This echoes the idea raised by Oliva in "An emotional perspective of music festival experience evaluation: a new model of emotional analysis." The presence of surprise and numerous strong and rare emotions in my interviewees' quotes reinforces the importance of a nuanced approach to mapping the emotions experienced at festivals. We also note in the responses that Generation Z's emotions are often linked to social interactions or the people around them. The idea that being in a group is a powerful trigger for emotions and memorability is echoed by Randall Collins's theory on "Interaction ritual chains." My interviews showed numerous examples of collective rituals such as dances or pogos. These had a profound impact on festival-goers. Many of them used terms such as communion with the audience. We also note that these moments can generate a lasting emotion reactivated by memory or by other festival-goers afterward. The principle of emotional synchrony, developed by Wood in: "I Remember How We All Felt: Perceived Emotional Synchrony through Tourist Memory Sharing," is very present in the observed testimonies. The fact of being several members of the same group sharing an event or emotions together seems to be a concept cherished by a large number of festival-goers. Some speak of the pleasure of volunteering together, others of attending concerts or even simply sitting together on the grass facing a sunset. These elements may have amplified the memory of the moment. This also allows these memories to be reactivated by sharing and storytelling among peers. In my corpus, synchrony is also seen as a fundamental marker of the intensity of a festival experience. The sharing of a collective emotional state emerges several times in my interviews. There is also talk of mutual emotional feedback between festival-goers. Thus, everyone is drawn into a surge of collective emotion and excitement. This is also what Sterchele develops in his article: "Memorable Tourism Experiences and Their Consequences: An Interaction Ritual (IR) Theory Approach."

Everyone has their own unique experience at a festival. Participants are free to take whatever actions they wish. They can decide to attend one concert rather than another. They can eat where and when they want. If they choose, they can very well go and talk to the people around them. In short, a festival-goer is not guided in their actions. This aspect is developed by Andrades and Dimanche in: "Co-creation of Experience Value: A Tourist Behavior Approach." He explains that festival-goers are actors in their own experience and fully participate in the construction of the event. Thus, they are the sole guarantors of the quality of what they experience. The idea of thinking of these events primarily as playgrounds is also mentioned by Kjeldgaard et al. in: "Broadening the brandfest: play and ludic agency." This article expresses the fact that each participant is the creator of the meaning they want to give to the event and its actions. Perception and personal interpretation are also important aspects of my corpus. I was able to observe that festival-goers interpreted the adventures they experience in this type of event differently. I also noticed that, during these moments,

participants found themselves, reinvented themselves far from the norms or social roles of everyday life.

Memories are linked to and impacted by a huge number of factors throughout a festival. One of the most prominent factors in my analyses concerns the overall context of the event. Contextual immersion is strongly described in many of the collected testimonies. Thus, elements such as the location, the weather, the general atmosphere, and even the crowd present are all factors that can influence the memorability of one of these events. Thus, it is possible that moments remain memorable, not because of an artistic performance, but rather because festival-goers feel fully connected to the overall context. This is what Oklevik et al. express in their article: "Contextual engagement in event visitors' experience and satisfaction." Thus, in addition to immersion, emotion, and active participation, analyzing the interview transcripts reveals that it is important for many of the interviewees that the aesthetic context be strong. This also contributes to festival-goers feeling a break from their everyday lives. This greatly contributes to creating lasting and impactful memories that will help to create a strong attachment to the event among festival-goers. This is what will make participants return or recommend a festival. Thus, the memorable experience will help to generate loyalty. Of course, memorability is not the only factor to take into account because there are very real limits and obstacles to the latter. However, memorability remains an essential aspect for an individual to return to a festival. This is what we observed but it is also what Manthiou et al. explain in the article: "The experience economy approach to festival marketing: vivid memory and attendee loyalty." But creating an overall context conducive to memorability is not easy. It is also necessary to take into account the expectations and motivations of each individual. Although my study found that festival-goers are often interested and driven by many different motivations, given the diversity of activities offered by a festival, some will still have preferences. For example, some attendees will be more likely to appreciate a smaller festival, while others seek the excitement of being part of a huge crowd. This attention, which must be paid to the expectations expressed by festival-goers before considering staging, is highlighted by Pegg and Patterson in the article: "Rethinking Music Festivals as a Staged Event: Gaining Insights from Understanding Visitor Motivations and the Experiences They Seek."

The engagement observed after an event represents a highlight of my body of work. Here too, my research validates studies already conducted on this topic. We found that memories from intense festival experiences had a huge impact on retention. These positive memories will also be recounted and mentally relived by festival-goers. This will therefore have an impact on recommendations. This is the idea that Bagheri et al. develops in the article: "From Tourist Experience to Satisfaction and Loyalty: Exploring the Role of a Sense of Well-Being." The idea that memories remain very present and greatly influence loyalty was also put on paper by Al-Azzam et al. who also explains in the article: "THE INFLUENCE OF MEMORABLE FESTIVAL EXPERIENCES ON ARAB VISITORS' REVISIT INTENTION TO THE JERASH FESTIVAL OF CULTURE AND ARTS (JFCA) IN JORDAN" that festival-goers will want to return to a festival in order to rediscover emotions associated with the well-being they felt the first time. Finally, regarding engagement, we were also able to see that forms of active participation such as volunteering helped to create a real attachment to a festival and

therefore encouraged participants to share it or return. This idea was taken up by Koenig-Lewis et al. in the article: "Linking engagement at cultural festivals to legacy impacts."

B. The articles that my research qualifies:

Now that we've analyzed the articles my research supported, it's time to look at those that the studies conducted during my thesis qualify.

During our interviews, we heard a great deal of testimony about the memorable memories festival-goers had experienced at festivals. While we did observe that Generation Z festival-goers generally remembered a few specific, emotionally charged moments more clearly than the entire experience, nothing allows us to say that the final moments of a festival are particularly memorable. Participants didn't specifically tell us about moments related to the final flourish of a festival. Of course, there were a few, but this doesn't represent a generalization. In this respect, my research contrasts with that conducted by Wood in his article: "How we think we felt: The importance of recollected experience and how to capture it," where the "peak end rule" was developed. This rule is also present in the article by Ellis et al.: "A theory of structured experience." But this is not the only point that our analyses qualify in this article. When we go to a festival, we know in advance that our senses will be greatly stimulated. This is part of the motivation to come to this type of event where the services offered and the possible experiences are numerous and diverse. Although this article also mentions the importance of a multisensory experience, it ranks the senses with similar importance. However, in our observations, we found that some, such as hearing and sight, contributed much more to making a festival memory memorable than others, such as taste or smell. This is also how we can qualify the results of the research by De Geus et al. in the article: "Conceptualization and Operationalization of Event and Festival Experiences: Creation of an Event Experience Scale."

Although our research also confirms the importance of playful and collective experiences (such as pogos or dances) in creating memorable festival memories, most of the testimonies we collected make no mention of clear mechanisms implemented by a festival to encourage them. These appear in the form of spontaneous and improvised games, unstructured by an explicit design. This is where my results differ from those obtained by Raftopoulos et al. in the article: "Designing events as gameful and playful experiences."

Another point we observed concerns the use of social media by Generation Z festival-goers. Analyzing the results, we see that they are primarily informational. Very few of the people I interviewed mentioned clearly following post-event communication. Furthermore, none of them are actually part of an online community. So, while we do indeed observe that sharing memories and images taken during a festival strengthens memory and attachment to the event, this process seems to occur primarily in the private, intimate sphere, through spoken word. There is no evidence that the use of social media prolongs the event for Generation Z festival-goers. This is the nuance we can add to the article: "Engaging community members with digitally curated social media content at an arts festival" by Shih et al. And while we also observe that reviewing images of a festival experience can rekindle emotions, once again,

social media is not an integral part of the process, contrary to what MacKay et al. suggested in their article: "Social media activity in a festival context: temporal and content analysis."

During this thesis, we saw that some participants may attach a symbolic or cultural dimension to their participation in a festival. Some say they feel particularly in tune with the values of the events they attend. Sometimes, festival recommendations can even be made based on the energy the speaker exudes. However, among Generation Z festival-goers, ecological values have never returned. We will rather speak of open-mindedness and tolerance. Thus, this is where our results differ from those put forward by Yen in the article: "How the Experience Designs of Sustainable Festive Events Affect Cultural Emotion, Travel Motivation, and Behavioral Intention. Sustainability." Here, the eco-responsible practices of festivals or those related to sustainability were not retained as a criterion contributing to the engagement or attendance of the festival-goers interviewed and none of them mentioned a post-festival change in behavior tending towards this ideology.

Memories and memorability are influenced by a huge number of factors. This is what we observed during our study. A key point for the satisfaction one gets from a festival to fully flourish concerns the logistical and functional aspects. We concluded during these interviews that, even if the latter is not necessarily striking in itself, it constitutes an essential basis for retaining a positive image of an event of this type. Marković's article: "How Festival Experience Quality Influence Visitor Satisfaction? A Quantitative Approach" also places great importance on these aspects. We are qualifying it here because, according to the testimonies collected, even if good logistics will limit the risk of bad memories, it is not directly what will drastically impact the satisfaction one leaves with from a festival. The article: "Making memories: a consumer-based model of authenticity applied to living history sites" by Kesgin et al. also mentions the importance of the festival setting. However, the research conducted during this thesis qualifies this by allowing the unexpected to be a key factor in the memorability and satisfaction felt after a festival.

Finally, a nuance should also be made regarding the article: "Effect of Festival Satisfaction on Destination Loyalty through Destination Overall Image: The Case of Alaçatı Herb Festival." by Özkan and Yıldız. According to them, the satisfaction derived from a festival has a direct effect on destination loyalty by influencing the overall image of the venue. We also found that satisfaction had a strong impact on commitment, but in our study, it directly concerns the festival and not the venue. Moreover, the effect we observed is less direct and is primarily influenced by a large number of factors such as memory reconstruction, its evolution, and socialization. In addition, there are many obstacles and limits to loyalty that are important to take into account.

C. The articles invalidated

There are also studies that my results contradict, and it's important to note this. Sometimes, these are concepts or technologies that were simply not observed during my analysis. In other cases, they involve theories that contradict what I observed.

The first of these articles is Ellis and Rossman's: "Creating Value for Participants through Experience Staging: Parks, Recreation, and Tourism in the Experience Industry." While many

of our participants also appreciated the staging elements such as lighting and scenography, this does not represent the majority of the memorable memories we recorded during this study. While it is always important to take care with festival staging, our observations show that this is not where memory is primarily built. Rather, we observed that it more often came from spontaneous and unforeseen events. Thus, this study calls into question the notion that experiential value is entirely designed by the organizers.

There are also articles that cannot be applied to our study because none of the festival-goers mentioned that any of the festivals they attended had used technology-based design. This could be for several reasons. Either it was not significant for the festival-goers, or it is because music festivals have not yet sufficiently embraced these new practices. Thus, we cannot support or qualify the results of various articles such as that by Dieck et al.: "Determining visitor engagement through augmented reality at science festivals: An experience economy perspective," or that by Olya et al.: "Engaging visitors of science festivals using augmented reality: asymmetrical modeling."

This is also the case for other concepts developed in certain articles. For example, we cannot build on the article: "From "clone towns" to "slow towns": examining festival legacies." by Duignan et al. because we cannot know for sure whether the festival-goers interviewed did not mention the legacy of a festival in a place because they did not notice it or because it did not mark them.

PART 6 – Theoretical contributions and managerial implications

A. Theoretical contributions

Although the literature on festival memorability and the evolution of festival memories is dense, I believe my research allows for the establishment of new theories, based on observations that have never been analyzed before.

First of all, during my analysis, I noticed that a large number of festival-goers mentioned feeling proud of having attended a festival. This sense of personal accomplishment is expressed through different moments. First, there is the pride of being present at a festival that one has often heard about. There is also the pride one feels following various adventures that may have befallen oneself during the event. One can be proud of having spoken to strangers, proud of knowing an artist's lyrics better than the people around us, proud of introducing one of one's favorite singers to one's friends, or even proud after having survived a turbulent concert. This sense of accomplishment resurfaced in various accounts of memorable memories. But this emotion also manifests itself after the festival is over. Some of the interviewees expressed pride in showing their friends videos of what they experienced. Similarly, some feel joy when someone mentions a festival they have previously attended. Finally, volunteers, once the event is over, often say they feel proud to have contributed to its success.

Another aspect we observed, which has never been described in existing literature, is the importance of the first festival. The vast majority of the people we interviewed spoke of their first festival experience as one of their most memorable memories. This experience will continue to stay with them, and they will recall it throughout their festival-going experience. This first festival therefore holds a significant emotional place among festival-goers and seems never to be truly forgotten. A good first experience also seems to ensure that the person who experienced it will continue to attend this type of event. Throughout our analysis of the journey festival memories take, we realized that many factors can influence memorability. However, one of the most common factors has never been described in the literature studied. This is the surprise factor of an event. Based on our observations and transcriptions, surprise appears to be a central trigger for memorability. Several of our festival-goers described surprising social interactions, unexpected contexts (such as magnificent sunsets or horses roaming freely near a group of volunteers), or unexpectedly changing atmospheres as some of their most memorable festival moments. We know that strong emotions are important vectors of memory, and it seems that surprising festival-goers with elements they hadn't imagined can be one of the keys to a memorable experience.

During this study, we were also able to observe a surprising fact about the bad memories experienced at festivals. When we talk about memorable memories, we instinctively think of wild concerts, funny interactions, or magical moments. However, the memorability of negative events within an overall positive framework also seems to be very important. Thus, many festival-goers cited mixed experiences among their most memorable festival memories. However, what is interesting to note is that these more negative memories were almost systematically recounted in a light, almost joyful manner. When I questioned the respondents

about this, they told me that the negative emotions that were attached to the anecdote were now far away. Unlike positive memories, which reactivate pleasant emotions, when it comes to bad memories, there are now only funny stories that festival-goers enjoy telling. This shows that inconveniences, when they aren't significant enough to completely remove festival-goers from the festival's inner bubble (such as the cancellation of a day or a poor sound system), can become a basis for engaging in conversation about a festival. And, as explained previously, these stories will be told in a light-hearted and humorous manner. Thus, they will become a source of reactivation of positive memories. Since these anecdotes are particularly striking, they will contribute to the festival's memorability, and in a positive way.

There is another point we noted during this analysis that doesn't seem to have been previously studied. This is the feeling we experience when we see a familiar place completely reinvented in a festival setting. Several of the people we interviewed told us they were affected by discovering the vacant lot, park, or village of their childhood converted to host a festival. This experience seems to be particularly memorable and enjoyable, and it also accentuates the attachment these festival-goers feel to the festival. In our study, these temporary adaptations are even the primary factor in memorability, which relates to a festival venue.

An original memorability factor was also raised during the interviews. Several festival-goers mentioned being particularly touched and impacted by micro-spaces installed within the festival. This does not concern the venue as a whole, but simply a specific location within the event. This could be a stage, a relaxation area, a booth, or simply a place with a beautiful view of the sunset or the crowd. Some participants expressed that they remembered a micro-space better than the festival venue as a whole.

Finally, the literature primarily explores memory in cognitive, emotional, or social terms. During my analysis, I noted that, for many festival-goers, the body played a role as a memory tracer. Festival-goers spoke in detail about how they felt at certain points during the festival. The vast majority of respondents mentioned feeling tired or sore after a concert or a pogo. Some even recalled being high on adrenaline. Thus, it seems that the body and its sensations can truly anchor memories.

Thus, we took the time to compare the results of our analyses with existing literature. While most of our observations support existing research, it is interesting to note that we can also add nuances. The innovative ideas revealed during this study are theories to explore and compare in future research. It is now time to examine how all the points discovered during this research allow organizers to develop new strategies in the context of practical application.

B. Managerial Implications

The observations we analyzed in this thesis cover a full spectrum of the pathways festival memories take. The conclusions we drew can be directly useful to professionals in this field through concrete actions. In this section, we will detail solutions related to the studies we conducted that can enable organizers of this type of event to leverage festival memories among Generation Z festival-goers so that they can encourage their engagement.

The first recommendations will focus on how to generate lasting memories among festival-goers.

Generation Z seems particularly attentive to the theming of these events. It seems that lighting effects or scenography are no longer the only vectors of memories in this regard. Festivals must now ensure immersive decors tied to a coherent theme. One of the people we interviewed, for example, was deeply affected by an event inspired by the Halloween theme. Others also mentioned a similar event about the circus world. This can take many forms. Original and well-designed micro-spaces can also leave lasting memories. One festival appreciated for its rustic atmosphere has set up wooden seating on grassy areas. This advice applies to all festivals of all sizes. The key to creating lasting memories is also surprising festival-goers. Therefore, don't be afraid to think outside the box and take risks. For example, it's possible to vary the format of the concerts you offer. Surprise shows, street performances on the festival grounds, hidden stages, artists announced at the last minute, etc. There are plenty of imaginable possibilities to vary your offerings.

The feeling of escape and a break from everyday life is an excellent phenomenon to exploit to ensure the memorable nature of your festival. To generate these feelings, you need to consider all possibilities. Some festival-goers have explained that they experienced these emotions while watching a sunset over a plain, gazing at the stars, or simply entering unique and symbolic festival venues (such as a citadel, for example). Using space can be an excellent way for all festivals to generate lasting memories. This can be expressed in a variety of ways. For example, if the event is taking place on a grassy expanse, opt for barriers that reveal the west-facing landscape so that festival-goers can enjoy the view of the setting sun. If the festival is taking place along a cliff, why not try setting up a small stage in a rocky cavity? These arrangements will greatly contribute to making Generation Z festival-goers feel transported. Although the impact of social media is not strongly observed in this study, photos still seem to be particularly appreciated by festival-goers. Therefore, creating aesthetically pleasing settings that respect the spirit of the venue or festival can be an excellent idea to encourage festival-goers to pose for a quick snap. This will reinforce the festival's image when the photos are shown and shared, and it will contribute to the lasting memories of the festival-goers who took them.

We also noted the importance of stimulating emotional and sensory intensity. Here too, this study offers concrete examples of practical applications.

Festival-goers repeatedly recounted that their entry into the festival was a defining moment. It can be interesting to greatly stimulate the senses at this precise moment. This can be done in various ways. For example, one could imagine bright and striking settings, such as arches or androids that would welcome festival-goers once their tickets have been checked. To make these arrangements, one could draw inspiration from the festival's overall theme. Imagine a festival centered on the circus world; one could play enigmatic welcome messages delivered by a ringmaster. If a festival focuses on the protection of the sea or oceans, one could diffuse the scent of chlorine at the ticket checkpoint. Regardless, the possibilities are endless. The important thing is that the senses are stimulated.

To create lasting memories through sensory intensity, organizers could also consider creating and implementing sensorium zones. These would be spaces where all the senses would be

stimulated simultaneously. These spaces could exist through hidden areas or with controlled access. They could be located in a clearing, under a big top, in a rocky cavity, behind vegetation, etc. Anything is possible. Festival-goers lucky enough to enter them would then have a memorable and original experience that would etch them into their memories.

It is also possible to imagine happenings that would surprise festival-goers' senses. This would combine the effects of sensory stimulation and the element of surprise, often mentioned by the festival-goers interviewed. These events could take various forms. For example, all the lights on a stage or festival would go out simultaneously for a few seconds to simulate a breakdown or technical incident before they all suddenly come back on, accompanied by a huge drop in music. This could also take the form of a light parade that would wander unannounced through the middle of the festival. Here again, the possibilities are numerous.

We observed that collective synchrony had a strong impact on festival-goers' memories of an event. Although these demonstrations most often arise from spontaneous and improvised movements, organizers could, through innovative practices, find a way to stimulate it.

Some festivals have rituals and practices that are repeated year after year. These rituals then become inseparable from the festival and are recognizable even by people who have never been to the event. Although it is not an entirely musical festival, this type of ritual can be observed in Dunkirk during the rigodon. It is a traditional dance from the region that is performed by all festival-goers each year. This moment of communion is often described as one of the peaks of the festival. Thus, during music festivals, organizers could also implement rituals. Let's imagine that every year, at the same time, festival goodies are thrown from a specific location. Then, little by little, festival-goers would end up making it a tradition and more and more people would go there each year to participate in this ritual. Similarly, if the festival always shares a certain type of crowd movement (for example, a wall of death) on its networks, then it would not be uncommon to see new festival-goers want to reproduce it. These rituals would then form strong and impactful memories for anyone who participated.

Similarly, it might be interesting for organizers to establish habits that would form collective customs. These could, for example, take place during the entrance and exit of the festival. If, during the exits, the same music is played every year, the group effect would surely push festival-goers to all sing it together as they walk towards the exits. This music would then become a symbol of the festival, and the songs would act as a rallying cry. This would energize the sense of community among festival-goers and would undoubtedly create strong memories.

Staging moments with a strong collective emotional impact could also be a good option to energize the synchrony felt by festival-goers. Let's imagine that once night falls, festival volunteers organize to give lanterns to attendees who want them and thus release them on the festival grounds. This moment would represent a group action led by people who share the same emotions. These people would be boosted by sharing and the sense of community. Thus, this memory would undoubtedly remain etched in their memories.

During this study, we also noticed that the feeling of having participated in the co-creation of the event greatly impacts the satisfaction one feels after a festival. Therefore, finding a way to

make festival-goers feel this way could be a major challenge for organizers. Various solutions can be found.

It's always worthwhile to try to involve event participants as much as possible in its creative process. In the context of a music festival, what better way than to offer festival-goers the opportunity to bring instruments? Thus, it could be highly symbolic to offer a free stage or jam sessions open to all. In this way, in addition to respecting the artistic direction of the event, festival-goers who participated in these activities would undoubtedly take away lasting and very positive memories.

Another solution to encourage co-creation is the setting up of participatory booths or workshops. In the context of an arts festival, one can imagine that festival-goers would be delighted to have the opportunity to practice customizing t-shirts, badges, or even visuals related to the artists present at the festival. These workshops, in addition to enhancing memorability, could offer festival-goers the opportunity to take home their creations. These tangible souvenirs would be kept and cherished by participants and would subsequently contribute to the lasting memories of the festivals that hosted these booths.

Finally, events could establish spaces for free expression within the festival. These spaces, in addition to contributing to the decoration of the venue, preserving the festival spirit, and the sense of community felt by festival-goers, could allow participants to express their creativity and feel fully part of the event's creations. These spaces could take various forms. A wall of memories, a huge tarpaulin with spray paint available, wishing trees, etc. The important thing would be for these to be truly freely available to festival-goers so that everyone can dare to participate in their creation or development.

As seen during the analysis, a sense of pride and accomplishment is particularly present among festival-goers. It might be interesting to try to stimulate this feeling.

First, organizers could reward their most loyal festival-goers with symbolic objects or artifacts. One of the people we interviewed said she was impressed when she saw former participants come to an event with badges representing each of the previous editions. Thus, creating easily identifiable and retrievable collector's items could provide additional motivation to not miss any of the festival's editions. This would also boost the sense of community and would represent objects related to the festival that participants would want to show their loved ones.

It could also be possible to create original challenges to complete during the festival. Successful completion of these challenges could result in gifts or goodies related to the festival. These challenges could be filmed to verify their completion and be linked to the co-creation of the event. This could include, for example, creating a pogo, participating in workshops at the booths, taking photos with strangers, participating in a jam session, etc. These challenges would create a sense of pride for the festival-goers who completed them, and this would energize the overall atmosphere of the festival.

Finally, it could be possible to give festival-goers the opportunity to share their highlights during interviews conducted after the festival. These videos could then be shared on the festival's account during post-event communications. This would help ensure that festival-goers can remember the event through the stories of others. Similarly, this could make the

respondents feel even more connected to the festival, thus strengthening their sense of belonging and the community spirit of the event.

But asking festival-goers to share their stories isn't the only interesting aspect to develop when it comes to maintaining connections with participants after the festival.

Sending emails to share information about future editions is a common occurrence. However, participants don't always open them and prefer to check out social media. One solution to encourage them to pay attention to emails would be to send them photos at the same time. Let's imagine that, at the festival venue, a booth with a free, professional photographer offers to take portraits of festival-goers. This way, participants could come to see him in groups and get souvenir photos of their experience. Email addresses would then be collected, and when the festival sends out the first information about the next edition, it could then attach the photos taken by the photographer to the appropriate email addresses. Festival-goers also indicated that they only follow post-event communications to find photos or videos in which they might appear. It might therefore be interesting for festivals to include a link to global photo albums in each of their emails. This would maximize anticipation, boost email open rates, and allow festival-goers to revisit their memories several times a year.

Generation Z festival-goers also mentioned never joining real online communities related to a festival. This is largely due to the fact that these communities are rare and don't really exist for festivals that appeal to this age group. It is also known that these attendees primarily use the social network Instagram. To try to create a community related to the festival, it would therefore be interesting to try using this platform. Festivals could promote group discussions involving different festival-goers. During planned marketing events, organizers could also allow people who wish to do so to be randomly placed in discussion groups with other attendees. This would allow people who fear being alone to meet people before the festival and would boost the sense of community.

To maintain contact with festival-goers after the event, a good way would be to organize events related to the previous edition. For example, there could be a free exhibition featuring photos or collectibles from the previous edition. These photos could be taken by photographers or simply by festival-goers. The items presented could be fun found objects, artist accessories, or simply collectible goodies. This type of event would extend the festival experience and allow attendees to reminisce about their memories at different times of the year.

Finally, it may be worth considering solutions that could encourage post-event engagement. Given the limitations and obstacles expressed, innovative solutions should be found.

First, we could imagine a festival ambassador program. These ambassadors would register directly on the festival website and receive a promo code in their name to purchase tickets. This code would allow those who use it to receive a few euros in discounts. This allows the festival to ensure that active members of their community recommend the event to their friends and family. For festival ambassadors, the benefits could be numerous. Each ticket sold using their code could earn them points that could then be used in exchange for perks at the event. These could include a free meal, a video signing from one of their favorite artists, the opportunity to visit backstage, a skip-the-line pass, or discounts on their ticket the following year.

We noted during the analysis that the cost of tickets represents a significant obstacle to retaining Generation Z. In certain cases, related to engagement, this cost could be reduced so that both festival-goers and festivals benefit. For example, ticket prices could be reduced for festival-goers who have shared photos or videos of the festival on their social media multiple times throughout the year. We could also see the introduction of new rates under certain conditions. For example, a formula where tickets for several editions of a festival would be purchased at once. For example, if a ticket for one edition costs 100 euros, festival-goers would be offered the option of purchasing their tickets for the next 3 for 250 euros. In a modern model where festivals are finding it increasingly difficult to forecast their budgets, due to the evolving consumption habits of festival-goers, who now book their tickets at the last minute, this process would allow for a win-win compromise. Finally, we have observed that the group effect was one of the major reasons why festival-goers came to these events. Thus, we could imagine that if a group of several people all returned from one year to the next, they would be entitled to discounts. This would encourage the members of these groups to convince themselves to return to the festival together. In addition, we have seen that collective memory greatly accentuates the importance and impact of memories.

Finally, to boost the sense of belonging and accomplishment, festivals could try to identify and reward their first festival-goers. This could simply be by recognizing their loyalty or granting them alumni status. There could also be the introduction of goodies, badges, or collector t-shirts given out once certain milestones are reached. For example, a special t-shirt for every 5th festival, a badge for every 7th, and a hat for every 10th. This would strengthen the community aspect and the loyalty of fans.

As we've seen, there are many practices or solutions that can be considered to create memories for festival-goers, make them last, and boost engagement. Festivals are dense events, and the practices that can be associated with them are, consequently, extremely numerous.

PART 7 – Limitations and Future Research

A. Limitations

Although this study aims to be rigorous and as comprehensive as possible, numerous limitations remain, related to the methodology used or practical possibilities. In this section, we will review them.

First, this study focuses on a specific generation (Generation Z). This choice, while allowing for a focused and coherent analysis that stands out from the literature, limits the generalizability of the results found to other age groups or overly heterogeneous audiences. It is conceivable that the interview responses would have been quite different, and that the observed memory drivers and mechanisms would not have been the same with older generations, particularly with regard to the relationship to time, memories, community, or the use of social media.

Another limitation of this study concerns the number of people interviewed. Although the respondents were selected using strict criteria (they had to belong to Generation Z and have previously attended festivals), it may seem presumptuous to make an absolute generalization from the responses of 21 people. Perhaps a larger number of participants would have allowed for the emergence of other types of memories, connections, or post-festival behaviors.

It would be interesting to compare the results obtained in this study with the opinions of industry professionals. Although we took care to select and interview diverse festival-goer profiles (we included more or less repeat festival-goers, artists, service providers, and volunteers), we did not compare our results or our questions with a proven festival-goer professional. This prevents us from examining the gap between the design imagined by the organizers and the actual experience of festival-goers.

In this study, I targeted music festivals as a whole. However, I did not focus specifically on a specific type or format. It would have been possible to interview only festival-goers who had attended local, small events. It would have been possible to focus solely on large festivals attracting tens of thousands of attendees. Also, attention could have been focused on independent or community-created events. In this study, these segments were not included. This allows us to address festival memories as a whole but limits the study's accuracy.

Another major limitation concerns the lack of data recorded during a festival. To accurately observe how memories evolve, it would have been interesting to interview festival-goers during or directly after the festival about the memories that particularly stood out to them. This would have allowed us to follow up and re-interview them about these memories several months or years later. Furthermore, it would have been very interesting to observe how they engaged with the festival. We could have taken into account whether the person spoke about it often, whether they signed up as a volunteer, or whether they shared photos on social media. However, this method would have been too costly in terms of time and resources. It was not possible for me to see the evolution of memories in such a short time.

We did not conduct cross-data observation as part of this study. By comparing interview transcripts and participants' statements about their behavior toward festivals, we might have been able to observe interesting details. Perhaps one of the participants had already recommended the festival on their Twitter account but didn't remember doing so. Perhaps by studying ticketing websites, we could have compared some of the results of our analyses. This was not done due to a lack of time, opportunities, and resources.

One limitation could also be a focus on the French-speaking world or even the French. Although the festival-goers interviewed indicated having attended events in different countries, or even continents, all of the interviewees were French-speaking. This may be viewed positively in the search for a specific answer, but it prevents us from generalizing too broadly.

During the interviews, I noted that some of the concepts mentioned by other researchers were completely absent from the festival-goers' accounts. This is particularly the case when discussing the use of advanced technologies such as virtual reality or the presence of digital applications related to festivals. The fact that these are not mentioned by anyone could mean several things. Either the festivals cited have not yet considered these innovations, or they are not as impactful or significant as those claimed by the authors. However, our study does not have the necessary data to resolve this question.

Furthermore, our research does not address any gendered or intersectional analysis. Our study places all respondents on the same level and does not take into account differences such as gender, social class, sexual orientation, or any other demographic criteria. Perhaps by examining this issue, it would have been possible to observe repeated patterns based on certain criteria. Since this thesis already focuses on a generational criterion, I preferred to opt for a homogeneous view, and only characteristics directly related to festivals were observed (characteristics such as motivations or the number of festivals attended).

A limitation I haven't yet mentioned concerns my relationship with music festivals. I express this in my methodology: I am passionate about this world and this environment. In recent years, I have attended dozens of different festivals. This passion has even led me to organize this type of event myself or to orient my professional career in this direction. Thus, it is natural that I have already formed my own idea of what a memorable and engaging festival experience is. Although, during this thesis, I paid extreme attention to being objective and not overinterpreting or influencing the responses of the festival-goers I interviewed, it is not entirely impossible that I may have sometimes lacked clarity.

Finally, the last limitation concerns the subjectivity of the people I interviewed. This study relied heavily on the stories of festival-goers. I asked them to share their experiences and their own opinions. Although the transcripts were reviewed, it is possible that some respondents may have wanted, even unconsciously, to embellish their memories or conceal certain negative aspects in order to present a positive image of themselves or the festivals they love. Although the interviews were conducted in a climate of trust and lightness, these biases can sometimes be difficult to avoid. In addition, some festival-goers may have felt obliged to respond to my questions or give me certain answers because they believed deep down that this was what I expected of them.

Now that we have reviewed some of the limitations specific to this study, it is time to provide suggestions for future research that would be interesting to conduct in order to complement, confirm, or refute the results of this study.

B. Suggestions for further research

Although this study was able to present specific ideas and concepts regarding festival memorability for Generation Z, these represent only one step in the quest for knowledge around these notions. Future studies may complement or invalidate the results we obtained. In this section, I will suggest potential research questions that would be interesting to answer in future dissertations on this topic.

First, it would be interesting to conduct the same study as this one across other generations. Thus, a research question such as: "What is the complete journey of Generation X's festival memories? From their creation to their impact on engagement?" could advance knowledge on this topic in the same way. It would then be possible to compare and contrast the results of this study with those of this dissertation to determine whether there are any notable differences between generations.

Secondly, it would be possible to conduct a comparable study on populations other than the French-speaking world. This could lead to a question such as: "How do Asian/African/American festival-goers experience, remember, and recount their festival experiences?" Such a study would allow us to examine the cultural dimension in the construction of festival memories. It would also be possible to test the universality or otherwise of the concepts of memorability, synchrony, or post-event engagement discussed in this study.

An interesting topic of study could concern the evolution of memories within specific time frames. It would be possible to investigate how festival memories evolve over a month, a quarter, a year, etc. This could provide valuable information on the process of crystallization, forgetting, or remanence of memories over time. The research question could be: "How do festival memories evolve after a year for the same individual, and which elements remain most persistent in memory?"

One of the limitations of this thesis is the fact that I did not combine different methodological approaches. By combining the responses obtained during the interviews with behavioral observations, particularly regarding engagement, even more precise and efficient conclusions could have been drawn. To address this issue, the following question could be adapted: "How does the addition of data from the observation of engagement change the understanding of festival memories reported during interviews?"

Also, research similar to the one we undertook could focus on specific types of festivals. For example, it might be interesting to compare the general data I obtained regarding Generation Z with data focusing on techno, rap, or other musical styles. Similarly, it would be interesting to understand whether the size of festivals or their ambitions could have an impact on festivalgoers' perceptions of their memories there afterward.

During our study, we observed that unpleasant experiences at festivals often became humorous anecdotes that were told with great lightness. These anecdotes also serve as excellent openings when festival-goers decide to talk about or recommend events. This theoretical contribution has not yet been observed by other authors and could be explored further through a research question such as: "How are negative memories experienced at festivals reinterpreted over time, and to what extent can they become vectors of positive memorability?"

Continuing with theoretical contributions, we also noted that pride or a sense of accomplishment played important roles in the memorability of festivals and their narration. This connection could be explored through the question: "How does the sense of pride felt by festival-goers contribute to the construction and persistence of festival memories?"

We were also able to note that the first festival experience was a source of positive and memorable memories for most of the participants interviewed. We also saw that the impact of this first experience could be significant. An individual who enjoyed their first event will tend to want to repeat it. Research on this topic could be further developed to determine for sure whether this link is inherent to all festival-goers or whether the observed data are simply the result of chance. The research question: "How does the first festival experience constitute a unique memory anchor in the journey of festival-goers and how does it influence their future behavior?"

The importance and memory impact of surprising, spontaneous, or unforeseen events appear to be particularly important. A study aimed at isolating surprise as a specific emotional and cognitive trigger could provide new knowledge. Thus, this trigger could also be compared to other universally recognized triggers such as emotional intensity, immersion, or socialization. In this way, a study on the topic "How do elements of surprise experienced at festivals influence the memorability of memories and their emotional impact?" would be relevant.

The people we interviewed who had the opportunity to rediscover a familiar venue as part of a festival all reported significant attachment and memory impact. Here again, it would be interesting to compare this notion with specific research to verify its validity. The question posed could be the following: "What is the impact of the temporary transformation of familiar festival spaces on the memorability and attachment of attendees?"

Although the literature focuses on the importance of staging and the overall scenography of a festival, no article actually addresses the possibility of installing specifically designed micro-spaces within a festival venue. Several of our respondents, however, described these as potentially memorable and engaging. The topic could be explored through this research question: "How do the micro-spaces staged in festivals participate in the construction of memorable memories?"

One of the final theoretical contributions of this study concerns the direct relationship with the body and the link it can have with memories. Many people seem to have been affected by phenomena directly related to the physical, such as hunger, exhaustion, adrenaline, rest, or pain following crowd movements. These feelings seem to be able to permanently anchor memories in the mind. It would be interesting to explore this relationship; to do so, a question such as:

"What role do bodily sensations play in consolidating memories related to the festival experience?" would be appropriate.

Finally, a large part of my topic focuses on engagement. As part of this thesis, I was able to interview volunteers and ask them about their memories. Some of them reported that their memories as volunteers were particularly striking. Thus, it would be interesting, through a study, to explore the difference between the festival memories of volunteers and those of "ordinary" participants. To do this, I devised the following question: "How do volunteers' memories differ from those of ordinary festival-goers, and how do these memories influence their sense of belonging to the event?"

This concludes the suggestions for future research. All of the ideas mentioned above could serve as a basis for studies on the topic of festival memories. The goal remains the pursuit of knowledge. Some of the proposed topics could be excellent foundations for potential future managerial implications.

This is also where this research paper ends. I sincerely hope that the research conducted here will inspire other researchers in future thesis topics to better understand the world of festival souvenirs.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Interview guide

1. Festival-goer's background (context)

Place the person in his or her overall relationship with festivals.

1. Can you tell me about your relationship with music festivals in general?
2. What attracts you to music festivals?
3. Do you remember a particular festival that left a lasting impression on you?

2. Remembering the experience (narration)

Exploring how memory is reconstructed, told, emotionally charged, and meaningful.

4. If you had to tell someone who wasn't there about this festival, what would you start with?
5. Can you describe one or more very memorable moments that you experienced?
6. What do you think makes these memory(s) so memorable?
7. Has this memory changed over time? Do you see it differently today?
8. Were there elements in the atmosphere or the place that left a lasting impression on you?
9. Did you feel like you were in another "other world" or in a special space? Why?

3. Shared memory, emotions and attachment

Highlight the social and affective dynamics of memory.

10. Did you talk about it with other people after the festival?
11. Does this memory still cause you an emotion today? Which one?
12. Do you feel attached to this festival or to this moment?
13. Do you keep any traces of this moment (photos, videos, objects, publications)?
14. Do you sometimes look at them again?

4. Communication

15. What means do you use to learn about festivals beforehand or to follow up on post-event communication?
16. Have you ever joined any online communities related to a festival?

5. Post-event consequences (engagement)

Understand how memory influences engagement.

17. Did this memory have an impact on you after the festival?
18. Would you like to go back? Why?
19. Did you talk about it around you, recommend this festival?
20. Would you say this memory influenced your relationship with festivals in general?

6. Recommendations

21. In your experience, what makes a festival truly memorable?
22. What could organizers do to retain their audiences?
23. What makes you want to participate more actively in a festival?

7. Conclusion

24. Is there an aspect of your memory that you find important and that we haven't talked about yet?
25. Do you have any questions or comments about this interview?

Appendix 2: List of all interview participants

Name	Job title	Age	Role in the festival
Lina	Luxury Marketing Assistant	22	Festival-goer/ Volunteer
Marius	Student	22	Festival-goer/ Musician/ Volunteer
Lola	Seasonal	23	Festival-goer
Lison	Student	22	Festival-goer
Leïla	Cultural Mediator	23	Festival-goer/ Volunteer
Axelle	Student	23	Festival-goer
Audrey	Bank Employee	24	Festival-goer
Anaïs	Artistic Production	23	Festival-goer/ Volunteer
Alex	Department Council Employee	22	Festival-goer/ Volunteer
Riad	Hypnotist	23	Festival-goer/ Provider
Antoine	Oenologist	24	Festival-goer
Quentin	Seasonal	23	Festival-goer/ Volunteer
Elisa	Student	20	Festival-goer/ Musician/ Volunteer
Mathilde	Psychologist	23	Festival-goer
Adrien	Student	23	Festival-goer
Lucas	Student	24	Festival-goer
Léane	Event Production	24	Festival-goer
Clémentine	Student	23	Festival-goer
Pauline	Seasonal	24	Festival-goer
Maxence	Student	23	Festival-goer
Wathek	Student	24	Festival-goer/ Volunteer Musician